

6572

ANNUAL REPORT
OF THE
ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT
GWALIOR STATE.
FOR SAMVAT 1980
YEAR 1923-24.

GWALIOR
ALIJAH DARBAR PRESS.

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF THE
ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT, GWALIOR STATE,
FOR THE
YEAR ENDING 30th JUNE 1924, SAMVAT 1980.

PART I.

Office Notes.

Charge.—During the year of report the undersigned held the charge of the Department except between the 19th of May and the 30th of June while he was on privilege leave. During the period of leave the charge of the current duties of the post remained with Mr. R. S. Saxena, the Archaeological Overseer.

Leave.—The Superintendent availed himself of two months' privilege leave from the 19th of May to the 18th of July, out of which one month and twelve days fall within the year of report.

Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows :—

- (a) *Archæological Overseer.*—Privilege leave of 12 days from the 22nd October to the 2nd November and again of 14 days from the 18th to the 31st December 1923.
- (b) *Photographer-Draftsman.*—Privilege leave of 23 days from the 12th May to the 8th June and sick leave on Medical Certificate from the 9th to 30th June 1924.
- (c) *General Assistant.*—Privilege leave of one month and five days from the 26th May to the 30th July 1924.
- (d) *Officer Accounts.*—Privilege leave of 15 days from the 24th July to the 8th August 1923.

General.—All the office staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

II. Circulars and Orders.

No Circulars or Departmental Orders with special reference to this Department were issued in the year of report.

III. Work at Headquarters.

In addition to the ordinary routine of office the following work was done during the Headquarter season :—

- (a) A resume of the conservation and exploration work accomplished by the Department in the year 1922-23. (Samvat 1979) was prepared and contributed to the *Annual Report of the All-India Archaeological Survey.*

- (b) An illustrated article on *Mandasor the ancient Dasapura* was contributed to the Birthday Special Number of the *Jayaji Pratap*.
- (c) As the first edition of the *Gwalior Fort Album* was exhausted by distribution and sale, the second edition of the same was carried through the press and published.
- (d) A number of lantern slides was prepared for being shown at the Departmental 'At Home.'
- (e) A manuscript of a classified list of some 1,300 photographic negatives prepared and stocked in this office during the last ten years, arranged alphabetically under districts and villages was under preparation.
- (f) An up-to-date alphabetical list of ancient monuments arranged under districts and villages was under preparation.
- (g) An Archaeological Map of the State was prepared for easy reference.
- (h) New acquisitions brought into the Archaeological Museum were arranged and labelled.
- (i) A pamphlet on '*Archæology in Gwalior*' giving a brief account of the Archæological work in Gwalior up-to-date was compiled and published.

IV. Tours.

During the year under report I spent 106 days in camp partly for supervising and directing the works of conservation in progress, for annual inspection of the principal groups of monuments conserved already, for supervising the special work of copying the ancient frescoes at Bagh, for preparing estimates of conservation works about to be undertaken, and partly for listing ancient monuments. (See Appendix A.)

I paid visits of annual inspection to the monuments at Surwaya, Gwalior, Chanderi, Ranod, Badoh, Bhilsa, Besnagar, Udaygiri and Bagh. I supervised and directed the conservation works in progress at Ranod (District Narwar), Badoh and Udaypur (District Bhilsa) and Bagh (District Amjhera). I visited Chanderi and Narwar for preparing estimates of repairs to the tomb known as Bahadurjika Mazar at Chanderi and to the old building known as Kachehri on Narwar Fort. I spent about a fortnight at Bagh directing the work of copying the ancient frescoes.

The following places were visited for listing ancient monuments :—

Mohana (District Gird), Satanwada, Jharna, Pipriah, Narwar, Sikandar-pura and Kachhaua (District Narwar), and Amera or Murtizanagar, Udaypur, Sunari, Pathari and Chirodia (District Bhilsa), and Chanderi and Goona (District Esagarh).

V. Conservation.

During the year of report conservation of ancient monuments was carried out chiefly at Bagh (District Amjhera), Ranod (District Narwar) and at Badoh and Udaypur (District Bhilsa). The list of conservation works in the year is shown in Appendix B.

(Bagh.)

At Bagh the work of freeing the *rock-cut caves* from the enormous mass of their own debris with which they are choked was continued further.

The joint verandah of Caves Nos. 4 and 5 extending over a total length of about 225 feet was cleared up excluding a small mound which was left over since it served as a scaffolding for copying the frescoes on the upper portion of the back wall of this verandah. The copying work having now been completed, the mound will be dug up and removed as soon as the clearance work is resumed next year.

Inside of Cave No. 5 which measures approximately 96' by 44' and which was covered all over with debris about 4' high was cleared up completely.

Three of the four aisles of the large hall of Cave No. 4 was also freed from debris.

The greater portion of Caves Nos. 3 and 4 still remains to be cleared and it is hoped that the work of clearance will be completed next season.

Repairs to the decaying pillars and walls and the construction of masonry supports will be taken up next.

(Ranod.)

The *Khokhai Hindu Monastery* at Ranod is under repairs for the last more than two years. The conservation of the main building had been almost completed last year. In addition to the few items that remained to be done here, the corridors, the courtyard and the precincts of the monument were attended to, in the year of report. In the main building the damaged edge of the stone floor of the verandah was renewed. The cracks in the roof slabs were repaired with country *masala* to render them water-proof. The pavement of the courtyard made up of heavy stone slabs had sunk in several places probably in consequence of huge stones from the upper storey having fallen upon it with a crash. The sunken paving slabs were raised and reset and lime *kankar* was rammed in gaps caused by missing slabs. A lintel in the northern corridor which had cracked was supported on a stone post and another in the west corridor which was dislocated was pushed back into its right position. Three heavy ceiling slabs in the north corridor had fallen down. They were lifted up and reset. A small dilapidated mosque near the monastery was freed from jungle and tidied up. The accretions of earth and rubbish which concealed the base of the monument on the exterior were dug up and removed. The heaps of debris and rubbish which disfigured the precincts of the building were dug away and the ground roughly levelled up. A Hindi summary of the contents of the large Sanskrit inscription on the monument was framed and hung up near the original for the information of the literate visitors to the monument.

(Badoh.)

At Badoh the repairs to the *Gadarmal* temple commenced last year were concluded during the year of report. The items carried out are :

The front face of the high platform on which the chief temple with its attendant shrines stands, was restored with original carved stones which had been dislodged but were lying buried in earth just near their position. The

restored face now shows mouldings and sculpture niches as they originally adorned the face of the platform. As a large number of stones in the other faces of the platform were missing these faces were roughly repaired with promiscuous blocks of stone picked from the debris so as to form a retaining wall to support the edges of the platform. The stepped approach to the platform was exposed by digging away the earth which concealed it and was restored with old stone. The top of the platform was repaved so far as possible with old paving slabs available in the debris and the remaining portion was metalled.

The existing portion of the two front attendant shrines had sagged badly. They were dismantled and properly reset.

The big carved blocks of stone picked from the debris were arranged into a sort of compound wall around the platform at a distance of 60 feet from its sides.

The entrance to the original compound was cleared and tidied up. The pillars of the porches at this entrance were reset plumb.

Some of the better preserved sculptures unearthed from the debris were arranged in order on both sides of the approach road between the outer entrance and the stairs of the platform.

Further, three more monuments at Badoh, namely, (1) the pillared hall known as Solahkhambi, (2) the Jaina temple, and (3) the group of Vaishnav temples received attention.

Solahkhambi as its name implies, is an open hall with a flat roof supported on sixteen pillars arranged in four rows, the whole set on a high plinth on the northern bank of a lake. The hall was evidently meant as a pleasure resort for enjoying fresh air and the view of the lake with its pretty lotuses. Judging from the shape of its pillars the building may be as old as the 9th century A. C. or even a little earlier. The repairs to this monument chiefly consisted in the clearance of jungle, the proper resetting of some of the pillars which were leaning out of plumb, and of the brackets, beams, and roof slabs, etc., which they carried, the underpinning of the undermined bases of a few pillars, the filling up of a deep pit inside and finishing the floor with *murum* rammed hard, the construction of steps to get up to the floor and lastly the throwing up of earth to conceal and strengthen the exposed foundations of the plinth.

The Jaina temple is a group of some twenty different shrines enclosing an oblong courtyard. The individual shrines are not all contemporary but appear to have been constructed at different times ranging from the 9th to the 12th century. Some of these are flat-roofed, others have domes and still others are crowned with *sikharas*. The monument was overgrown with a very dense jungle so much so that it was almost concealed from view. The jungle was cleared up completely although the roots of some of the bigger trees will require attention for some time to come before they are thoroughly eradicated. The interior of the courtyard and the shrines was freed from heaps of debris. The ground inside was dug up till the original floor pavements were exposed. Stone or masonry supports were set up in some places where they were necessary and petty repairs including underpinning were done to the rubble masonry of walls of the shrines and parapets.

The *Vaishnava temples* at Badoh are in an advanced condition of ruin. Originally there may have been more than a dozen temples in this group but at present only three of them are standing and these too in such a tottering condition that hardly anything can be done now to rescue them. The rest have been reduced to mere heaps of debris.

The whole site was enveloped in thick jungle. This was cleared up so as to render the ruins accessible to visitors. Important sculptures lying scattered in the ruins were picked up and arranged so as to form a small open air museum round one of the temples.

(Udaypur.)

Perhaps the most important monument taken up for conservation during the year of report is a great Siva temple known as *Nilakanthesvara* or *Uddyesvara* at Udaypur (District Bhilsa). The date of the temple is definitely known from the numerous stone records which it has the good fortune to possess. It was constructed between V. S. 1116 and 1137 (= A. C. 1059 and 1080) by Udayaditya, the well known Paramara king. It consists of a shrine room with a lofty and elegant spire, a hall, and entrance porches on its three sides. It is situated in a spacious rectangular compound with attendant shrines at corners and mid-points of its sides and a peculiar flat roofed structure in front of the chief entrance to the temple known as *vedi* which was probably used as a sacrificial room or a room for the reciting of the Vedas. The temple is built of large blocks of red sandstone which serves to enhance its effect. The temple itself is still structurally sound although one and all of the numerous figure sculptures with which the exterior facing was decorated have been mutilated and disfigured. This temple has been described by Fergusson (*History of Architecture*, Vol. II, page 147) who rightly admires the great beauty and elegance of the design of its *sikhara*. This is certainly the finest and the best preserved example of a mediæval Hindu temple in Gwalior State and perhaps so in the whole of Central India.

In the same compound is a mosque built by Muhammad II Ibn Tughlaq with material taken from a Hindu temple which to judge from the material was probably a companion of the Udayesvara temple.

Although the temple is in a comparatively fair state of preservation nevertheless its body and surroundings need a good deal of clearance and repairs. For instance, the village people have encroached into the original compound of the temple by building a number of *kachcha* houses which have disfigured the view of the monument and which it is necessary to clear off. The proposal of acquiring these houses has made a fair progress and the acquisition is hoped to be an accomplished fact in a few months.

The following items of conservation were carried out here in the year of report :—

The temple and its precincts were freed from small jungle and vegetation. A big *pipal* tree growing on the *vedi* and a *bel* tree growing on the steps of the eastern porch of the temple were cut off and completely eradicated. In doing so a portion of masonry had to be dismantled which was afterwards re-built. The *kachcha* rubble work put in later times at the principal entrance to the temple was dismantled and the steps were repaired in carefully dressed

blocks of stone so as to match the original work. Leakages in the pyramidal roof of the hall were repaired. Later rubble accretions made to the *vedi* were cleared away.

The whole compound in general and the mosque behind the temple in particular were freed from the heaps of rubbish and earth. The pavement in the compound had sunk in a few places, the damaged patches were made good. A dilapidated rubble structure over the main entrance to the compound was dismantled and removed. A terrace roof was put over the entrance. The terrace roof of the mosque leaked in several places. A fresh 6" coat of stone concrete in good lime was therefore put over it so as to render it water proof. The main entrance was provided with an iron gate. The old doors of the main temple and its porches had badly decayed. They were replaced with decent teak wood shutters in Indian pattern so as to be in keeping with the merits of the building.

The Home Member accompanied by the Suba Bhilsa, and Tehsildar Basoda, was good enough to pay an inspection visit to this monument on the 18th April 1924 in the course of his tour in the District.

Narwar Fort.

In obedience of oral orders of H. H. the Maharaja Sahib the old Mahal known as Kachehri in the Narwar Fort was carefully examined and a conservation note and estimates of clearing up the building and converting a part of it into a Dak Bungalow, of repairing a fallen bastion and of improving the approach road were prepared and submitted to H. H. The old Mahals in the Narwar Fort are extensive and interesting buildings which have reached an advanced condition of decay. To repair the whole lot is out of question. But at least more important portions of them deserve to be tidied up and provided with convenient footpaths to enable visitors to take a round through the ruins.

VI. ANNUAL UPKEEP.

Besides the special repairs detailed above, all monuments already conserved were inspected and jungle clearance and other petty measures of annual upkeep were carried out there.

VII. EXPLORATION.

(a) Excavations.

No excavations were undertaken in the year. It had been originally proposed to carry out trial excavations at Pawaya, the site of Padmavati, but as the legal procedure preliminary to the acquisition of the desired plots of land could not be completed before the winter season had well nigh expired the proposed excavations had to be postponed to the next field season.

(b) Listing of Monuments.

Sixty-one monuments situated in 15 different places, namely, Mohana (District Gird), Satanwada, Jharna, Pipriah, Narwar, Sikandarpura and Kachhaua (District Narwar), Amera or Murtizanagar, Udaypur, Sunari, Pathari and Chirodia (District Bhilsa) and Goona and Chanderi (District Esagarh) were added to the list in the year of report. They chiefly comprise sculptures, inscriptions and ruins of mediæval temples, tombs and mosques.

Appendix C shows a list of the newly listed monuments. They may be described briefly as under :—

(District Bhilsa.)

Village Amera or Murtizanagar.—The village is about $1\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the south of Udaypur in the Basoda Pargana. A short distance to the north-east of the village at the foot of a small hill is an old ruined tank with dam built of stone. The dam is now very much ruined and the tank is full of silt and consequently dried up. A stone inscription found lying loose on the slope of the adjoining hill presumably belongs to this tank. It records its construction by a Brahmana named (Vi) krama in V. S. 1151 (= A. C. 1094) during the reign of Naravarma (a Paramara king of Malwa).

On the slope of the hill a few hundred yards to the east of the tank stand the ruins of a small temple which appears to have consisted of a shrine with a porch in front. The shrine measures 6'6" in length and 5'8" in breadth, while the porch is 5'9" by 5'8". The temple is popularly known as Vedi.

About half a mile to the west of the village are the remains of what appears to be a pillared hall. The building also bears the popular name of Vedi. (People in the locality believe that the builder of the Udayesvara temple built also 12 Vedis, 3 in each direction of the great temple and so they have named all ruins of temples in the vicinity as Vedis even though they have nothing to do with the great Udayesvara temple.) On plan the building is almost square, measuring as it does 13'3" by 13'9" externally. It is a 12 pillared hall with 12 short pillars set on the dwarf compound wall which is 4' high and carries on its top a line of coping which served as a line of seats. There is a line of socket holes in this coping which evidently held back rests. The pillars, architraves and the exterior faces of the compound walls bear carvings. The ceiling consists of diminishing squares placed diagonally one within another. The north, south and east walls are pierced each with a passage opening.

Condition.—The building is very much shaken. The foundations have sunk. The walls and the pillars are leaning inside. The floor which was originally paved has lost its flag stones. The roof slabs also have been displaced.

In view of several buildings of this type existing in the locality this monument does not deserve more than mere preservation.

Udaypur.—About three quarters of a mile towards the south of the village on the slope of a hill there is a gigantic unfinished sculpture carved in a single boulder of rock. The figure is lying horizontally. It is 26' tall, 12'7" broad across the chest and hands and 4'6" thick. It is six-handed. One of the right hands holds a sword, another a *Damaru* and the third an unfinished object, probably a *Trisula*. One of the left hands holds a skull-crowned mace, another points a finger towards its left foot and the third is held in the *Abhaya mudra*. The feet are in a dancing posture. A human figure (some demon) is trampled under the left foot. A serpent which is entwined round the neck has its hood on the chest and the coils of its body hanging down. The head of the figure is covered with matted hair shaped

like a crown with the sign of crescent moon on it. The sculpture is locally known as Ravana but in fact it represents a terrific form of Siva.

Sunari.—Near this village by the side of the cart track leading from Udaypur to Basoda are the bare remains of a shrine in which are sheltered two badly mutilated sculptures. One of them represents the Baudha Avatara of Vishnu and the other Lakshmi-Narayana.

Chirodia.—This village is about 3 miles to the east of Bhilsa. Outside the village, towards the east, under a tamarind tree, there is a site of an old temple now converted into a *kachcha* platform where some of the old carvings are standing or lying about. Among these there are two rather good sculptures of Ganesa and Yama.

Badoh.—During the clearance of debris with which the Gadarmal temple and its precincts were choked, a number of mutilated images of goddesses were found. Under the base of each of these images is a tenon. On clearing the debris in the shrine of the principal temple it was found that there is a line of raised pedestals or seats touching the walls, evidently intended to support idols. On examination the seats were found to have socket holes corresponding to the tenons of the sculptures referred to above. From their style the sculptures are referable to the 9th century or thereabout which is also the date of the original temple which has been repaired later on. This original temple, sheltered the aforesaid sculptures and therefore, was dedicated to a goddess or goddesses. The image of a goddess on the dedicatory block of the shrine doorway further corroborates this view which is still further supported by the fact that a large and beautiful (though mutilated) sculpture of a mother goddess with a child was found in the shrine room lying loose in the debris, which was probably the principal idol in the temple. The mothers or female energies in the universe were common objects of worship in the Gupta and Mediæval periods. They are generally found as adjuncts of Saiva temples. But separate temples of goddesses such as the Chonsat Jogini temple at Khajuraha and Jubbulpore are also met with. The Gadarmal temple was such a temple dedicated to the Mothers.

After the original temple had suffered mutilation at the hands of Muhammedan invaders, an attempt was made to repair it. But the operations appear to have been left incomplete. The huge mass of rough rubble platforms with which the temple was enveloped were built most probably to serve as scaffolding during the repairs. As the operations broke up in the middle the scaffolding was not dismantled and cleared up. Its existence till of late cannot perhaps be explained satisfactorily in any other way.

Up to the top of the walls of the shrine the original temple has survived, the structure above including the *sikhara* is clearly a later repair which accounts for the promiscuous employment of all sorts of carvings. Some Jaina sculptures are used in these repairs which perhaps indicates that the temple was repaired by the Jains.

About a quarter of a mile to the N. W. of the Gadarmal temple stands a Jaina temple consisting of 19 cells arranged on three sides of a rectangular courtyard. The images of Tirthankaras sheltered in the cells beginning at the north-east corner and proceeding to the right are as follow.

Cell No.	Name of Tirthankara.	Pose.	Lanchhana or mark,
1	Unidentified	Standing.	No mark.
2	{ Mahavira	Seated,	Lion.
	{ Mallinatha (?)	Standing.	Water-jar (?)
3	{ Ajitnatha (polished)	Elephant.
	{ Unidentified height 7' 8" biggest of the three (polished).	Standing.	Broken off.
	{ Sambhavanath (polished)	"	Horse.
4	Two images, bigger of the two is 9' tall.	"	...
5	{ Sambhavanatha	"	Horse.
	{ Rashbhanatha height 9'	"	Bull.
	{ Ajitanatha	"	Elephant.
6	{ Unidentified	"	Broken.
	{ Santinatha	"	Antelope.
	{ Parsvanatha	"	Serpant.
	{ Unidentified	"	Hidden under ground.
	{ Rishabhanatha	Seated.	Bull.
	{ Unidentified	"	Unidentified.
	{ Two small images in a niche	"	No mark.
7	An empty cell for passage
8	A large image height 9'	Standing.	Hidden under ground.
9	A big image height 11' 3" (this is the principal shrine).	"	"
10	{ Five images	Seated.	In the case of one water-jar is visible. The marks of the rest are hidden.
	{ Three images... ..	"	
11	{ Rishabhanatha	Standing.	Bull.
	{ Parsvanatha... ..	Seated.	Serpant.
	{ A third image	"	No mark.
	{ Outside this cell there are two standing images of <i>Tirthankaras</i> ,	"	...

Cell No.	Name of Tirthamkarā.	Pose.	Lanchhana or mark.
12	A big image	Standing	Mark broken off.
13	Contains a standing image of Bhujavalli with 19 small seated images of <i>Tirthamkaras</i> on the back ground and a 20th figure of a goddess with child.	"	"
14	Unidentified	"	"
15	{ Parsvanatha	Seated	Serpant.
	{ Two images of Santinatha	Standing	Antelope.
16	Unidentified	Seated	No mark.
17	A small image	Standing	"
18	Unidentified	Seated	"
19	A Chaumukha	Standing	"

There are two pilgrims' records on the door jambs of cells of this temple. One of them is dated in V. Samvat 1134 and the other in V. Samvat 13 which certainly omits the figure showing the century and is perhaps to be read V. Samvat 1113. Two of the images also bear short inscriptions.

Pathari.—A large monolithic pillar stands in the eastern part of the village. Its approximate height above ground is between 40 to 45 feet. Besides, it is probably a few feet deep under the ground level. It has a square base 8' above ground each side of which measures 2'9" wide, the upper portion is round with a diametre of 2'6". It has a capital in the shape of an *amalasila* surmounted by a square abacus and not a bell-shaped capital as observed by Cunningham (*Arch. Surv. of India Report*, Vol. X, page 70 where the pillar is briefly described). The pillar is crowned with a double faced standing figure of a god now only partially preserved. The pillar bears a large inscription in 38 lines of good Sanskrit language which records that a temple of Sauri or Krishna was constructed here by Parabala, a king of some branch of the Rashtrakuta dynasty in Vikrama Samvat 917 = A. C. 861 (*vide Epigraphia India*, Vol. IX, pp. 248-56).

Half a mile to the east of the pillar is a gigantic unfinished sculpture of Varaha Avatara carved out of a single boulder of rock. It was probably left unfinished and abandoned owing to some flaw in the stone. The sculpture is now in a prostrate position half buried in earth. It is 13' long, 11' high excluding a cubical block on the neck which is about 1' high but including the pedestal which is 1'3" in thickness.

Udaygiri.—A new point which suggested itself to me during the last annual inspection of the Jaina Cave (No. 20) is this. The inscription on the cave speaks of the installation of an image of Parsvanatha at the mouth of the cave. The inscription flanks the mouth of the cave on one side and on the other are two rock-cut images of Jaina *Tirthamkaras* one of which is that of Parsva. In the inscription the image of Jaina (*Jinakritim*) is qualified by

the adjective *sphhata-vikato-thatam* which Dr. Fleet (*Gupta Inscriptions*, page 259) renders by 'richly endowed with the expanded hoods of a snake and an attendant female deity'. Of course, the hoods of the snake are present in the rock sculpture referred to above, but the female attendant is not. This however can be very easily accounted for. Because the natural interpretation of the qualifying phrase quoted above is "mighty and fierce on account of the hoods of a snake." This description fits in very well with the rock-cut images in question and I am inclined to think that the inscription refers to this image rather than (as held by Dr. Fleet) to some other loose image which has disappeared now. Further from the style of sculpture the image is referable to the same period (5th century A. C.) to which the inscription belongs. Moreover the view is corroborated by the word *achikarat* occurring in the inscription which would refer to the 'making or chiselling' of an image (in rock) rather than to the 'installation' of a loose image.

(District Esagarh.)

Chanderi.—A tomb known as Bahadurjika Mazar stands about a mile to the south of the town, between the Dhobi Talao and the Pan Baodi. A descendent of the person whose remains are sheltered by the tomb informed me that the present generation in the family is the sixth from the man buried. So the tomb is about 150 years old. It possesses no interest either from the architectural or historical view point. It is one of the many ordinary tombs which stand scattered round about Chanderi.

The tomb is a dome rising from the octagonal base supported on 12 pillars arranged on four sides of a square. The frame work of the dome is made up of brick and is plastered inside and outside. It is crowned with a high stone (?) pinnacle. The rest of the structure is built of stone. The tomb is set on a double plinth. The bases of pillars, the architraves and the brackets supporting them are of the Hindu pattern. The base and the top of the shafts are four-sided, the intervening portion being made into eight sides by chamfering the corners. The line of eave slabs (*Chhajja*) going round the base of the dome is supported on wavy brackets which are common to many other old buildings in the locality. Rosettes and mihrabs are employed in the building as decorative devices.

The upper plinth supports three tomb stones. The central appears to be the original one, the remaining have been added later on. The central and the eastern tomb stones bear inscriptions perhaps Qoranic texts. The lower plinth also bears a number of tomb stones evidently of members of the same family. The lower plinth measures 47' 4" square and 5' 5" to 6' 8" high. The upper plinth is 21' 4" square and 1' 10" high.

A few feet to the west of the tomb is an interesting Sati stone lying prostrate on the ground. The stone is 6' 2" high, 1' 5" broad and 10" thick. It bears no inscription but the sculpture is interesting. The lower portion of the stone is plain. In the upper portion there are two panels of sculpture one above the other. The upper panel contains the usual figures of the hand, the sun, the moon and the stars. But the lower panel is noteworthy for the rather unusual representation of the cremated husband and wife as transformed into Siva and Parvati riding on the bull and the lion, respectively. Siva is four-armed and holds a snake in one of his left hands. Both figures wear crowns.

Goona.—My attention was called to the circuit house (formerly Commanding Officer's Bungalow) at Goona. Most of the material such as pillars, arches, cave slabs, etc., employed in the construction of the verandah of the building has been borrowed from the ruins of some Vaishnavite temple two to three centuries old. Among the figure sculptures on the brackets are the images of Vishnu, Hanumat, Karttikeya, Mahalakshmi and Gajalakshmi and many gods and saints who hold rosaries of beads in their hands. One of the brackets consists of two good figures of peacocks. There are two detached sculptures of caparisoned elephants placed so as to flank the entrance. An inscription in crude Nagari characters is seen under an image of Mahalakshmi. It reads *Pratima Mahalakshmi*. Another inscription exists under a male figure but is mostly illegible. Some sculptures have been built in the walls inside the Bungalow. Among them Vishnu, Nrisimha and a group of Rama and Lakshmana may be recognised. The artistic worth of the carvings is however small. The work is dull, shallow and stereotyped. I was told that these stones were brought from a place in the Sironj District of the Tonk State, some 17 miles from Goona.

(District Gird.)

Mohana.—In a field about one furlong to the north of the Dak Bungalow there are three Sati pillars, all bearing inscriptions which are very much damaged. One of these is somewhat legible and is dated in Vikrama Samvat 1462.

(District Narwar.)

Kachhaua.—This is now a small village about 5 miles to the north of Pichhore. A quarter of a mile to the east of the present village lie the ruins of a fortified town, which has long disappeared. Traditionally the town is attributed to the Bundela Rajas of Orchha. Sivacharan Dube of Pichhore related the following story:—

"Raja Indrajit, a grandson of Virasimhadeva of Orchha, reigned at Kachhaua. His queen whose name was Padmavati was very beautiful. The fame of her beauty excited the cupidty of Emperor Shahjahan who besieged the town. There was no sign of surrender even after a full year's seige. A tracherous washer-woman suggested that the dam of the tank which supplied water to the garrison should be breached. This device was successful, the town was captured and the king and the queen taken prisoners. In reply to the advances of the Emperor the queen sent an ingeneous reply expressed in a verse which ran :—

*Vinati mo paravin ki suniyo Sah Sujan,
Jhuti patal vo bhake ek Kauva ek Svan.*

The queen was proficient in the art of music. She sang a song of Malhara Raga and at once it began to rain. The Emperor was extremely pleased and he restored the royal couple to freedom. It is said that Pichhore was built by Rudrasimha, a brother of Indrajit, after Kachhaua had fallen."

What now exists are mere traces of the town wall with ruins of bastions here and there, remains of a gateway, ruins of a large two storeyed building the upper storey of, which has totally disappeared and glimpses of the lower storey of which can be had through stray holes in the domed roofs, traces of a well and a tank and last but not least a building which is variously styled as a

Mahal, Madhaiya, Sarai, or Masjid. Like all other buildings in the locality it is built of rubble in lime. Originally it was plastered over and some of the rooms bear traces of paintings also.

The building faces the east. On plan it consists of an open rectangular courtyard which is entered through a projecting entrance porch in the centre of the east side, and is lined with a series of rooms on the other three sides. Excluding the four rooms at the corners there are three rooms on each of the three sides. Thus in all there are 14 rooms (see sketch plan).

Each room except the two corner rooms in the back row open into the courtyard by a single door. The two corner rooms have two doors opening into the adjacent rooms. Each of the remaining rooms also communicates with the adjacent room or rooms. All doorways are in the shape of broad pointed arches. The roof of each room is in the form of a semi-circular dome of the Pathan style. The courtyard measures 65' east to west and 50' north to south. Excluding the projecting entrance porch the building measures 93' by 93' externally. Just behind the central room in the back

row there is a projection on the exterior. The general features and lay out of the building indicate that it is a mosque.

Qazi Moajuddin of Pichhore who claims to be the owner of the mosque told me that he has got a *sanad* granted by Akbar relating to the mosque and some piece of land attached to the same. I am sorry I did not find time to see the *sanad* and verify the Qazi's assertions.

Satanwara.—Half a furlong to the north-east of the village is an old Siva temple with plain walls of fairly large sized blocks of stone, and a carved doorway. The sculpture on the doorway is rude and indicates a late date (15th or 16th century) for the existing temple. But there are some fragments of carving (*e. g.*, an *amalasila*) belonging to an 11th century temple lying about near this building which appear to show that the present temple has been built on the site of an old temple of about the 11th century. An old well about the same date (11th century) is seen in front of the temple.

On the west of the village half buried in the boundary dam of a paddy field is a carved memorial pillar, only the top of which is now exposed to view.

In a wall of a house on the north-west outskirts of the village is a stone inscription in Hindi (not yet copied) which goes back to the reign of Emperor Shah Jahan.

On the eastern outskirts of the village is a small tank on the bank of which stands a stone slab on which a pair of serpent gods (*Nagadevatas*) are carved in relief.

Nearby is the remnant of a Vishnu temple of about the 10th or 11th century. The doorway and four pillars of the *Mandapa* carrying the beams of the ceiling are all that has survived.

Close by is the site of another temple.

In a modern room which is only a few feet to the west of the Vishnu temple are stored some fragments of old well carved sculptures. Some similar fragments are also lying outside this room.

Carved pillars and architectural pieces belonging to old temples are seen built up in modern houses and platforms and a few are also lying strewn about on the northern outskirts of the village.

A memorial pillar carved in the usual way is lying prostrate about 300 yards to the north-east of the village.

Jharna.—Towards the end of the fourth mile from Satanwada, on the Satanwada-Narwar Road, is a place called *Jharna* in the jungle. Here there are two natural springs of water from which a brook takes its rise. The water of the springs is crystal pure and shelters fishes. There is an ample shade of trees and on the whole it is a charming spot. About half a furlong towards the south-west of the road, near the upper spring lies a huge pile of carved stones which once composed a large temple or perhaps temples as old as the 11th or 12th century, which are no more standing.

Pipriah.—The old road from Narwar to Shivpuri passes through this place (*Jharna*). Ascending the *Ghati* by this road which is now a mere foot-path one comes to a table land at about $\frac{1}{2}$ mile from the *Jharna*. Here within the limits of the village Pipriah are standing two life size statues of

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Parabala, another to Paramara Naravarman, still another to Paramara Jayasimha, two other to Jayasimha of Jayapur and another to Sikandarshah Lodi of Delhi. The rest mention no king or dynasty. One of these, records the construction of a tank, another of a well, a third of a mosque, a fourth of a temple, two other register charity grants, two record the making of guns, three are epitaphs of Sati, two are pilgrims' records, seven are epitaphs on tombs, one is a mason's mark and the rest are illegible or unintelligible.

One of the new epigraphical discoveries is of historical importance. (Appendix D. No. 1.). It is a stone inscription found lying loose on the slope of a hill in the vicinity of an old ruined tank about $1\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the south of Udaypur (District Bhilsa). The inscription is in 23 lines of Nagari characters and Sanskrit language and records the construction of a tank (evidently the one near which the stone was found) by a Brahmana named (Vi) krama during the rule of Naravarman, a Paramara king, in V. S. 1151 = A. C. 1094. The numerous records at Udaypur have already proved that in those days this locality was under the Paramaras. The historical value of this record lies in this that it gives us a date for Naravarman 10 years earlier than any known hitherto (*e. g.*, from the Nagpur Prasasti) and thus puts back the probable beginning of his reign by ten years.

IX. NUMISMATICS.

Three hundred and thirty-one coins were examined in the year of report. Of these 330 were of silver and one of copper. All these coins came from a treasure-trove find at Ghataoda, a village in the Dasai Jagir, District Amjhera. The silver coins were all of the type known as Gadhiya which is found in south-west Rajputana, Malwa and Gujarat. It is a degenerate copy of Indo-Sassanian coinage, bearing as it does on the obverse a rude imitation of king's bust to right and on the reverse lines and dots suggesting the Sassanian fire-altar. It is not yet certain as to what dynasty or dynasties issued this coin. Numismatists assign it roughly to the 11th century A. C. (*J. M. C.*, page 233).

One copper coin found in the same lot is a punch marked piece showing on the obverse the rayed sun and a crude human figure and on the reverse some indistinct marks (see Appendix E).

X. ARCHÆOLOGICAL MUSEUM.

A Sanskrit inscription of the 11th century A. C., 45 stone sculptures of various gods of the Hindu pantheon, 5 copies in colour and 8 drawings in outline of Bagh frescoes, an old miniature painting in the Mughal style and 1 copper and 12 silver coins were added to the Archæological Museum in the year of report. Some of the sculptures notably that of Siva slaying Gajasura from Kotah, the Buddha Avatara of Vishnu from Sumari and some beautiful busts of goddesses from Badoh are among the more interesting acquisitions for the Museum. But by far the most important are the copies of Bagh frescoes. (The acquisitions are detailed in Appendix F.)

The Museum is steadily gaining in popularity. 830 visitors have signed their names in the visitors' book this year, but the actual number of visitors was much larger as many of them being illiterate could not put

in their signatures, while others who came in groups were content by giving the signature of their leader or representative only.

The number of European and American visitors exceeded one hundred, the countries represented being England, France, Germany, Italy, Norway, Canada, U. S. A., India and Ceylon. The addresses of Indian visitors represent almost all the provinces of India, including Punjab, U. P., Bengal, C. P., Bombay, Gujrat, C. I., Rajputana and Madras.

Among distinguished visitors of the year may be mentioned Sir Alexander Muddiman, the present Home Member of the Government of India, and some Indian Members of the Indian Legislature,

XI. COPYING OF BAGH FRESCOS.

The copying of the valuable but fast fading frescoes on the Buddhist Caves at Bagh was undertaken and a greater portion of it carried out in the year 1920. In the meantime the work fell into abeyance as suitable artists were not forthcoming to complete it. Fortunately in the year of report Capt. W. E. Gladstone Soloman, the Principal of Sir J. J. School of Arts, Bombay, who takes special interest in ancient Indian Paintings, deputed Messrs. Bhonsle and Apte, two of his advanced students to do the work at Bagh. These artists assisted by Mr. Bhand, a promising art student of Gwalior, were able to do water colour copies of the remaining figure paintings and outlines of representative specimens of the floral and geometrical decorations on the interior of Cave No. 4. Equal size copies both in outline and in water colour of all the important frescoes that have survived at Bagh have thus been completed. Further the plan to publish them in a convenient book form through the India Society of London is under contemplation and it is hoped that it will materialise in the near future, thus supplying a long felt want.

XII. AT HOME.

The function of Departmental 'At Home' inaugurated last year was repeated this year. This year the Department was 'At Home' to meet His Highness at the Race Course grounds on the 19th of March. Sardars, high Officers of Government and respectable gentry in the city and His Highness' guests who had assembled for the races were invited. The copies of Bagh frescoes which were exhibited among other archaeological exhibits in a small pavilion for the inspection of guests were greatly admired. A brochure giving the brief history of the work accomplished by the Archaeological Department during the last ten years was distributed among the guests. But the special feature of this year's 'At Home' was a magic lantern display in which nearly a hundred slides illustrating the principal archaeological buildings in the State were shown. This last item made a very favourable impression on the audience and it effectively brought them into touch with the work which this Department has been doing. Thus the usefulness of this function and the desirability of repeating it from year to year is established beyond doubt.

XIII. PUBLICATIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS.

Second edition of 300 copies of the *Gwalior Fort Album* was brought out.

A pamphlet of 40 pages giving a brief account of the archaeological work in Gwalior and entitled '*Archæology in Gwalior*' was published.

A resume of the Exploration and Conservation work in the State was contributed to the *All-India Archaeological Survey Report*.

An illustrated article on '*Mandasor the ancient Dasapura*' was contributed to the Birthday Special Number of the *Jayaji Pratap*.

XIV. PHOTOGRAPHS AND DRAWINGS.

One hundred and twenty-nine photographic negatives and one hundred and nine magic lantern slides were prepared in the year of report. (See Appendices H and I.)

Ten drawings and sketches were made in the year (see Appendix J).

An alphabetical list of photo negatives in this Office which number nearly 1,500 is now ready in manuscript and is about to be published for the benefit of the public to whom prints are supplied on payment of a nominal price.

XV. OFFICE LIBRARY.

One hundred and thirty-four volumes on Archæology, Architecture, Art, History and allied subjects were acquired for the Office Library in the year under report (see Appendix K). Out of these ninety-four were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and Governments of Indian States to whom our thanks are due.

XVI. INCOME AND EXPENDITURE.

The budget of the Department is the same (namely, Rs. 25,000) as it has been for the last five years. Statements of income and expenditure are set forth in Appendices L and M from which it will be seen that the income in the year amounted to Rs. 433-10-7 and expenditure was Rs. 26,565-0-11.

XVII. CONCLUDING REMARKS.

The Darbar were graciously pleased to confer on me a *poshak* on the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Birthday in the year of report. I am deeply grateful for this gracious appreciation on the part of the Darbar of the humble work which I was able to put in their service. I have also to thank Sardar Major Maloji Rao Sahib Sitole for the interest he took in the work of this Department while he officiated as Home Member and especially for the ready and generous help he rendered to the Department at the time of 'At Home.' In conclusion, I beg to acknowledge my indebtedness to our Home Member Shrimant Khase Sahib Powar for the unfailing courtesies and the valuable advice with which he has continued to favour me in discharging the duties of my office.

MOTIMARAL, GWALIOR,

15th October 1924.

M. B. GARDE,
Superintendent of Archæology,
Gwalior State.

PART II.

APPENDIX A.

The Tour Diary of the Superintendent of Archaeology,
for Samvat 1980.

Year and month.	Date.	Movements and Halts.
1923.		
July ...	16th-17th	Gwalior to Badoh <i>via</i> Kalhar.
	18th-19th	Halt at Badoh.
	20th-21st	Badoh to Gwalior <i>via</i> Kalhar.
August --	28th	Gwalior to Shivpuri
	29th	Halt at Shivpuri.
	30th	Shivpuri to Surwaya and back.
	31st	Halt at Shivpuri.
September.	1st	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
	16th	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
	17th	Halt at Shivpuri.
	18th	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
	30th	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
October ...	1st-2nd	Halt at Shivpuri.
	3rd	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
	25th	Gwalior to Dabra.
	26th	Dabra to Dhumeswar.
	27th	Dhumeswar to Pawaya.
	28th	Pawaya to Dabra.
	Do.	Dabra to Gwalior.
November.	4th	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
	5th	Halt at Shivpuri.
	6th	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
	27th	Gwalior to Agra and back.
	28th	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
	29th	Shivpuri to Kolaras.
	30th	Kolaras to Ranod.
December.	1st	Halt at Ranod.
	2nd	Ranod to Mayapur.
	3rd	Mayapur to Pichhore.
	4th	Pichhore to Kachhaua and back.
	5th	Pichhore to Basai.
	6th	Basai to Kalhar.
	Do.	Kalhar to Badoh.
	7th	Halt at Badoh.
	8th-9th	Badoh to Gwalior <i>via</i> Kalhar.
	9th	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
	10th	Halt at Shivpuri.
	11th	Shivpuri to Narwar and back.
	12th	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
	14th-15th	Gwalior to Mhow.
15th	Mhow to Sardarpur.	
16th	Sardarpur to Tanda.	
17th	Tanda to Bagh.	

Year and month.	Date.	Movements and Halts.
1923.		
December.	18th-19th	Halt at Bagh.
	20th	Bagh to Sardarpur.
	21st	Sardarpur to Mhow.
	22nd-23rd	Mhow to Gwalior.
1924.		
January ...	11th	Gwalior to Satanwada.
	12th	Satanwada to Narwar.
	13th-14th	Halt at Narwar.
	15th	Narwar to Satanwada.
	16th	Satanwada to Mohana.
	17th	Mohana to Gwalior.
	22nd	Gwalior to Agra.
	23rd	Agra to Gwalior.
	Do.	Gwalior to Satanwada.
	24th	Satanwada to Narwar.
	25th-27th	Halt at Narwar.
	28th	Narwar to Satanwada.
	29th	Satanwada to Gwalior.
February.	2nd-3rd	Gwalior to Badoh and back to Kalhar.
	4th	Kalhar to Ujjain.
	5th	Ujjain to Kaliadeh and back.
	6th	Ujjain to Sardarpur <i>via</i> Mhow.
	7th	Sardarpur to Tanda.
	8th	Tanda to Bagh.
	9th-15th	Halt at Bagh.
	16th	Bagh to Tanda.
	17th	Tanda to Sardarpur.
	18th	Sardarpur to Mhow.
	18th-19th	Mhow to Bhilsa <i>via</i> Ujjain.
	19th	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.
	20th	Bhilsa to Gwalior.
April ...	9th-10th	Gwalior to Chanderi <i>via</i> Lalitpur.
	11th	Halt at Chanderi.
	12th	Chanderi to Futehabad and back.
	13th	Chanderi to Bhilsa <i>via</i> Lalitpur.
	14th	Bhilsa to Chirodia and back.
	15th	Bhilsa to Udaypur <i>via</i> Baret.
	16th	Halt at Udaypur.
	17th	Udaypur to Basoda.
	18th	Basoda to Udaypur.
	19th	Udaypur to Badoh.
	20th	Halt at Badoh.
	21st-22nd	Badoh to Gwalior <i>via</i> Kalhar.
	27th-28th	Gwalior to Goona.
	29th	Halt at Goona.
	30th	Goona to Shivpuri.
May ...	1st	Shivpuri to Surwaya.
	2nd	Surwaya to Shivpuri.
	3rd	Shivpuri to Gwalior.

APPENDIX B.

Statement of Monuments conserved in Samvat 1980.

Serial No.	Place.	Name of monument.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.			AMOUNT SPENT.			REMARKS.
			Current year.	Last year.	Total.	Current year.	Last year.	Total.	
			Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	
1	Badoh	Gadarnal Temple	618 0 0	1,977 15 6	2,595 15 6	542 8 6	1,975 12 3	2,518 4 9	
2	Ranod	Khokhai Monastery	299 8 3	1,544 15 0	1,844 7 3	299 8 3	1,503 5 0	1,802 13 3	
3	Bagh	Copying Frescoes	2,700 0 0	736 5 3	3,436 5 3	2,355 15 5	736 5 3	3,092 4 8	
4	"	Clearance of Caves	1,210 0 0	...	1,210 0 0	1,205 2 9	...	1,205 2 9	
5	Bhilsa	Udaygiri Caves	10 0 0	...	10 0 0	9 3 0	...	9 3 0	
6	Udaypur	Udayeswar Temple	4,571 0 0	...	4,571 0 0	2,342 6 3	...	2,342 6 3	
7	Badoh	Dassavatar Temple	96 0 0	...	96 0 0	95 10 0	...	95 10 0	
8	Bhilsa	Khamb-Baba	8 0 0	...	8 0 0	8 0 0	...	8 0 0	
9	Badoh	Solakhambi	187 0 0	...	187 0 0	167 9 6	...	167 9 6	
10	"	Jain Temple	350 0 0	...	350 0 0	315 10 6	...	315 10 6	
11	Bhilsa	Gumabazka Muqbara	10 0 0	...	*10 0 0	3 11 6	...	3 11 6	
12	Surwaya	Gadhi ...	25 0 0	...	25 0 0	24 11 6	...	24 11 6	
		TOTAL	10,084 8 3	4,359 3 9	14,343 12 0	7,370 0 11	4,215 6 6	11,585 7 5	

APPENDIX C.

Statement of Monuments Listed in Samvat 1980.

No.	District.	Place.	Name of Monument.	Class.	Remarks.
1	Bhilsa.	Amera or Murtizana-gar (near Udaypur).	An old tank with stone built dam.	III.	
2	"	"	A Sanskrit inscription belonging to this tank but now lying loose on the slope of hill close by.	I.	Removed to Museum.
3	"	"	A small ruined shrine known as Vedi on the slope of hill near the above named tank.	III.	
4	"	"	Remains of another temple also known as Vedi about $\frac{1}{2}$ mile to the north-west of the village.	III.	
5	"	Chirodia.	Site of an old mediæval temple now converted into a <i>kacheha</i> platform where some old carvings are placed.	II.	
6	"	"	Two rather good sculptures of Ganesa and Yama on the platform mentioned above.	II.	Worth being removed to Museum.
7	"	Pathari.	A monolithic pillar (inscribed)	I.	
8	"	"	A monolithic gigantic boar unfinished	II.	
9	"	Sunari.	Two loose sculptures :—(1) Buddha Avatara of Vishnu and (2) Lakshmi Narayana near the ruins of a shrine on the north outskirts of village on the road side.	II.	The sculpture of Buddha Avatara is removed to Museum.
10	"	Udaypur.	A small ruined shrine near Sitala Mata Mandir.	III.	
11	"	"	A huge but unfinished sculpture on a boulder of rock locally known Rawan Tor (रवण टोर) about a mile to south of village near a stone quarry.	II.	
12	Esagarh.	Chandari.	Tomb known as Bahadurjika Mazar on the road to Katighati (on the bank of the Dhobi Talao).	III.	
13	"	"	An interesting Sati stone near above	II.	
13A	"	Goona.	Rest house in which a few sculptures of an old Rama or Vishnu temple have been built.	III.	
14	Gwl.-Gird	Mobana.	Three inscribed Sati pillars one of which is dated in V. Samvat 1462.	III.	
15	Narwar	Kachhaua.	Vestiges of a fortified village or town	III.	
16	"	"	An old Masjid	II.	
17	"	Narwar Fort	Building known as Kachehri	II.	

No.	District.	Place.	Name of Monument.	Class.	Remarks.
18	Narwar.	Narwar Fort.	Ladau Bungala	II.	
19	"	"	Chhip Mahal	II.	
20	"	"	Makaradhvaj Tal with an interesting slab of sculpture.	II.	
21	"	"	Badi Masjid with three Persian and five Hindi inscriptions.	II.	
22	"	"	Roman Catholic chapel and cemetery ...	II.	
23	"	"	Rewa Kund	II.	
24	"	"	Sagar Tal	II.	
25	"	"	Chandan Talaiya	II.	
26	"	"	A small mosque	II.	
27	"	"	Devi's temple	II.	
28	"	"	Madarshah ki Dargah	II.	
29	"	"	Mahals in the southern portion of the Fort...	II.	
30	"	"	A mosque near Hawa Paur	II.	
31	"	"	An old gun (No. 18) known as Fateh Jung. length 10'10", diameter near mouth 10½" bears a Hindi inscription in 4 lines.	I.	
32	"	"	An old gun named Ramaban, length 10', needle at back 1'6", circumference 3'8", diameter of aperture 4½".	I.	
33	"	"	An old gun named Narwarban length 16'6" including needle, circumference near mouth 3'10½" and near eye 6", diameter of aperture 5½".	I.	
34	"	"	Alamgiri Darwaza ...	II.	} on the eastern road.
35	"	"	Saiyadonka " ...	II.	
36	"	"	Piran Paur ...	II.	
37	"	"	Hawa Paur ...	II.	
38	"	"	Dholya or Dulha gate on the western side, now not in use.	II.	
19	"	"	Urwahi gate on the western road ...	II.	
0	"	"	A Gaumukha near above	II.	
1	"	"	A shaking kiosque known as Halna Bungala	III.	
2	"	"	A kiosque on the western rampart known as Rewa Chhatri.	III.	
3	"	"	An old gun near Rewa Chhatri (No. 33) with a tiger's face, length 10'10", diameter near mouth 1', bears a Hindi inscription in 7 lines which gives 'Sattru-Samhar' as the name of the gun.	I.	

No	District.	Place.	Name of Monument.	Class.	Remarks.
44	Narwar.	Narwar Fort.	An inscribed Sati stone on the southern bank of the Makaradhvaj Tal, dated V. Samvat 169 (3).	III.	
45	"	"	A <i>Baodi</i> or step well near Makaradhvaj Tal, diameter 27' bears an inscription, dated in V. Samvat 1687.	III.	
46	"	Town.	An Armenian tomb with Portuguese (?), Persian and Hindi inscriptions in a field belonging to Bhagwanlal Panda near the eastern city wall.	II.	
47	"	Pipria.	(About $\frac{1}{2}$ mile north from the <i>Jharna</i> on the table-land above the <i>Ghati</i> through which the old road between Narwar and Shivpuri passes). Two images of Hanumat (life size) out of which one is well carved.	III.	
48	"	"	Ruins of shrine among which is a mutilated but well-carved image of Trimurti.	III.	
49	"	Satanwada.	An old empty (Mahadeo) temple with plain masonry to the north-east of village.	II.	
50	"	"	An old well in front of the above temple ...	III.	
51	"	"	An old memorial pillar half buried in ground on the boundary dam of a paddy field to the west of village.	III.	
52	"	"	A Hindi inscription of the reign of Shah Jahan stuck up in a house on the north-west outskirts of village.	II.	
53	"	"	Sculpture in relief of a pair of Nagas on a slab on the bank of a small old tank on the eastern outskirts of the village.	II.	Removed to Museum.
54	"	"	Remnants of a Vishnu temple of about the 10th or 11th century. The door frame and four pillars of the Mandapa are standing carrying beams.	III.	
55	"	"	Site of another temple near above ...	III.	
56	"	"	Some old sculptures (well carved but now mutilated) collected in a modern room a few feet to the west of the Vishnu temple.	III.	
57	"	"	Some fragments of sculptures lying scattered outside the room.	III.	
58	"	"	Carved pillars and other architectural pieces strewn about in the village and its northern outskirts.	III.	
59	"	"	A memorial pillar carved in the usual way, lying prostrate about 300 yards towards the north-east of the village.	III.	

District.	Place.	Name of Monument.	Class.	Remarks.
Narwar.	Satanwada.	Four Sati stones about 1½ mile to the south-west of village on road to Shivpuri. One bears inscription, dated V. Samvat 1521.	III.	
"	Sikandarpura 1 mile north of Narwar Town.	Two ruined Armenian tombs with Portuguese (?) and Persian inscriptions in a field owned by Kharga Kachhi, to the right of the road to Magroni.	II.	
"	Jharna on the Satanwada Narwar Road 4 miles from Satanwada.	Pile of ruins of a huge 11th century temple probably with a number of attendant shrines. There is an image of Hanumat standing on a platform, and a number of half mutilated carvings in the debris.	III.	

APPENDIX D.

List of Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1980.

Serial No.	District.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Number of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of Ruler.	Purport.	REMARKS.
1	Bhilsa.	Amerna.	A loose stone lying on the slope of a hill near an old ruined tank.	23+1 =24	Old Nagari	Sanskrit.	V. S. 1151 Ashadha Sudi 7 = Friday, 23rd June 1094	Naravarmān (Paramara).	Records the construction of a tank by a Brahmana named [VI] krama.	23 lines are engraved regularly. Another line only is engraved at the end. (This stone is now removed to Gwalior Arch. Museum). This record is engraved on the raised border of the same stone as No. 1. But the two inscriptions are separate. Their languages also differ. But to judge from characters they are contemporary. The date evidently omits the figures expressing the century. It is perhaps to be read as ५, ११३.
2	"	"	On the raised border of the same stone as above.	4	"	Prakrit.	...	"	Purport not intelligible.	
3	"	Badoh	On a door jamb of a cell in Jaina temple.	4	"	Sanskrit.	V. S. [11] 13	...	Is a pilgrim's record. It reads ॐ सतिश्री दादस [क] मंडके आचार्य केवलि [देदिने] मूचंद्रस्य ॥ स. १३ [स] मे.	
4	"	"	On another door jamb of a cell in Jaina temple.	3	"	"	V. S. 1134.	...	Is also a pilgrim's record. Text: सति श्रीचंद्र आचार्य मंत्र वादिन संमत ११३४.	
5	"	Udaypur.	On a Sati stone.	7	Nagari	Hindi.	V. S. 1698. Saka 1563.	...	Rudely written. Illegible, appears to record a Sati in the family of a <i>chaudhari</i> at Udaypur.	Both these inscriptions are engraved on the same stone but are in different hands.
6										

8	"	Udaypur.	On a stone built into a wall outside the east entrance to the compound of the Udayesvar temple.	12	"	"	V. S. 13 [1] 1.	Jayasimba of Malwa.	As the latter half of the inscription is very much damaged the later portion is illegible. It appears to have registered a grant.	Noticed by Prof. Kielhorn in <i>Ind. Ant.</i> , Vol. XVIII, p. 341, and again in <i>Ibid.</i> , Vol. XX, p. 84 footnote.
9	"	"	On a pillar in the east Porch of the Udayesvar temple.	5	"	"	V. S. 1222	...	Registers grants by Thakur Sri Chananda on the occasion of अग्रयण उत्सवा.	This inscription is similar to but distinct from inscription B. edited by Prof. Kielhorn on pp. 343-44 of <i>Ind. Ant.</i> , Vol. XVIII.
10	"	"	On a fragment of stone found during the clearance of the temple precincts.	13	"	"	This is a mere fragment of an inscription. The object of the record cannot be made out from this small piece. The date is not available in the existing portion. The characters are Nagari of the 11th or 12th century.	
11	Gird	Mohana.	On a Sati pillar near Dak Bungalow.	...	Sanskrit.	Nagari.	V. S. 1462.	...	Mentions रामराज, चंड, [रं] बाहिल्य, शिरसिह.	Not copied being mostly illegible.

Serial No.	District.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Number of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of Ruler.	Purport.	REMARKS.
12	Gird.	Narwar Fort.	On a gun near Rewa Chhatri.	7	Nagori.	Hindi.	V. S. 1753.	Jayasimha (of Jaipur)	Text:—श्री महाराजाविराज [श्री] राजा जयसिंजु देव की सरकार [हैं] कान मख्त [१] श्री की तोप का नाउ सवुंखार अमहन सुव १२ संवत १७५३.	
13	"	"	On a stone slab in a <i>Baodi</i> near Makara-dhvaj Tal.	...	"	Hindi.	V. S. 1687.	
14	"	Narwar Fort.	On a gun ...	4	"	Hindi.	V. S. 1753.	Jayasimha (of Jaipur).	Text:—श्री महाराजाविराज श्रीराज जैसिंजु देव की सारावा में (सरकार है) तोप को नाउ फतेजंग संवत १७५३ कुवर सुदी १०.	
15	"	Satanwada.	On a Sati stone lying prostrate about 1½ miles to south-west of village near Shivpuri road.	...	"	Sanskrit.	V. S. 1521.	...	Mentions <i>सत्तावा</i> as the name of village. The names of the Sati and her husband are given but are illegible. The full date is संवत १५२१ बेट व. १० सोमवार.	
15 (A)	"	Narwar Fort.	Over the niches in the main hall of the big mosque.	...	Naskh.	Persian.	A. H. 912 ?	Sikandar Shah Lodi.	There are three inscriptions. One of these (central) is a Quran text. That on the right is in prose and that on the left is in poetry. They are thickly covered with lichens and therefore are not quite legible at present. One records the construction of the mosque in commemoration of vic-	Not copied.

17	"	Sikandar-pura hamlet 1 mile north of Narwar.	On a tomb	Nastaliq.	Persian.	...	names of masons who dressed them.	سليمان بيگ بيگ ولد مظفر	...	No; copied or deciphered yet.
18	"	"	"	Portugese	...	" Sulaimanbeg s/o. Muzaffarbeg.	...	" Sulaimanbeg s/o. Muzaffarbeg.	...	
19	"	"	On another tomb	Persian.	A.H. 1179 = A. C. 1766.	The inscription is in 3 parts. The first part is not legible. The second is eulogy of God and the third records that the tomb is sacred to the memory of Mary, wife of Sulaimanbeg Armani (Armenian), who died on the 15th Ramzan A. H. 1179 (Saturday, 15th February 1766 A. C.)	...	The same as above (?)	...	
20	"	"	On the same tomb as above.	Portugese	...	Do.	...	Do. (?)	...	
21	"	Narwar Town.	On a tomb inside the east city wall in a field owned by Baghwanlal Panda.	Portugese	
22	"	"	Do, on top	...	Nastaliq.	Persian.	...	Text:— بسم الله خواجه محمد از روح بزرگان پايی	Not yet copied.

Trans. In the name of God, Invoke help and it shall come from the soul of ancestors.

Serial No.	District.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Number of lines	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of Ruler.	Purport.	REMARKS.
22 A	Narwar.	Narwar Town.	On the same tomb on the right side.	Persian.	A. H. 1153 = 1740 A. C.	...	Text:— تبر از اکيل بن پروغوس چلمای پادری عيسویان ارمني که در نمازخانه شاهالی بسوزدند از آنجا به اتفاقات در شهر سنه ۱۱۵۳ هجری به هندوستان در نور رسيدند و بعد استقامت ده سال در عمر	
22 B	"	"	On the base of the same tomb as above.	...	Nastaliq.	Persian.	A. H. 1163 = A. C. 1750.	...	Text:— هفتاد و دو در سال ۱۱۶۳ هجری به هند ماه جهادی الثاني مطابق سنه ۱۷۵۰	
22 C	"	"	On the left side of the same Armenian tomb	...	"	"	"	"	Trans. 72 in the year 1163 A. H. 17th of the month Jamadi-us-sani correspond-	

کرد پرواز از تشمن خاک
 روح پاکش باوج چایلمین
 و پسرانش جسم این
 بزرگوار تاب شش صاه
 در این مزار داشته درهنگی
 بنمدر رسانیدند. و این
 نشان باقی است
 Trans.—from the birth of
 Jesus Christ flew from the
 earthen home the holy soul
 to the enlightened high, His
 sons after keeping the re-
 mains for six months in this
 tomb sent them to the
 Hoogly port and left this
 as a memorial.
 [१] तर अष्टकैळ बटा पोएस का
 जळमाई असनीयो क गाद्री [नमाज-
 खाने] साबळी में हमेसा रहे, सं
 १७९७ में हिंदुस्थान में आये बरस
 इस नरतर में रहे सम्वत १८०७ में
 बहत्र ७२ बरस के उमर में [२] देह
 छोडी और महिता ६ इनका ताबत
 इस कबर में रहा, फिर इनके (बटो) ने
 इस ताबत को डगळी कदर को
 पडुंवाया और यादगारी के वास्ते यह
 जगह इनका नीसान बना रहा है ॥

tomb.

On the sides of the same tomb as above.

Hindi.

APPENDIX E.

List of Coins examined, in Samvat 1980.

No.	King or Dynasty.	Description.	Metal.	Number of Coins Examined.	Remarks.
1	...	<p style="text-align: center;">Obverse.</p> <p>Rude imitation of king's bust to right.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Reverse.</p> <p>Lines and dots suggesting the Sassanian fire-altar.</p>	Silver.	330	The coins found as Tre trove at v Ghataoda in Jagir. There are 3 different s.
2	...	<p>Punch marked</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Obverse.</p> <p>Rayed sun and a rude human figure ...</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Reverse.</p> <p>Marks are indistinct</p>	Copper.	1	Found in same lot, as e

List of Antiquities added to Archaeological Museum in Samvat 1980.

o.	Find Spot.	Description.	Remarks.
1	Amera near Udaypur (Dist. Bhilsa)	A stone inscription in Sanskrit, dated Vikram Samvat 1151.	2'7" × 3' including border.
2	Badoh (Dist. Bhilsa),	Piece of an ornamental frame of a sculpture of Vishnu.	2'6" × 6"
3	"	Another sculpture of Vishnu	2'2" × 1'7"
4	"	Bust of Indra holding Vajra in one surviving hand.	1'9" × 1'6"
5	"	Upper half of an image of Siva	2'5" × 2'
6	"	A mother and child	2' × 1
7	"	A musician playing on a tabor	3'8" × 1'4"
8	"	A figure of a soldier wielding sword and shield perhaps a fragment of bigger sculpture of the sun god.	1' × 8"
9	"	Bust of a woman	1'2" × 1'
10	"	" " without head	1' × 1'
11	"	A dog's head	10" × 8"
12	"	Bust of a woman	1'7" × 1'5"
13	"	Bust of Varahi	1'3" × 1'4"
14	"	Bust of a woman with a halo behind it ...	1'6" × 1'5"
15	"	Torso of a woman... ..	2'6" × 1'
16	"	" "	1'6" × 1'5"
17	"	Fragment of an image of Kubera... ..	1'6" × 8"
18	"	Torso of a man	1'6" × 8"
19	"	An archer (fragment of a bigger sculpture) of the sun god.	1' × 1"
20	"	A conch (fragment of a moon stone ?) ...	1'5" × 1'
21	"	A bracket with dwarfs	1'2" × 8" × 7"
22	"	A slab with the eight Dikpalas carved in relief.	7'1" × 1'10"
23	"	A hunting scene	5'3" × 1'
24	"	Head of a woman	9"
25	"	Head of a buffalo	7"
26	"	Head of a lion	4"

No.	Find Spot.	Description.	Remarks.
27	Badoh (Dist. Bhilsa).	Head of an animal... ..	4"
28	"	Torso of a woman	9"
29	"	Bust of a woman	7"
30	"	Figure of Garuda	11"
31	Kota (Udhamdeka) (Dist. Narwar).	Kartikeya standing	3'9" × 1'10"
32	"	Siva in his terrific form (Rudra) ...	6' × 2'10"
33	"	Siva standing	4'3" × 1'10"
34	"	A standing goddess with traces of three heads which have broken off (probably Mahesvari, one of the seven mothers).	4'2" × 1'8"
35	"	Kaumari	4' × 1'9"
36	Narwar Fort.	A sculpture of Vishnu standing with an ornamental frame with the ten <i>Avataras</i> in miniature.	4' × 2'5"
37	Padhavli (Dist. Tawarghar).	Surya seated	2'7" × 1'7"
38	"	Bust of Trimurti (in a panel)	3'7" × 3'7"
39	"	Ganesa dancing (in a panel)	2'10" × 2'
40	"	Wedding of Siva and Parvati (in a panel).	3'7" × 3'7"
41	"	Back rest of a seat with an elephant's head	2'4" × 2'5" × 1
42	"	A carved ceiling slab	3'8" × 1'6"
43	"	Pinnacle (in the form of a jar) of a Sikhara.	3'9" × 1'6"
44	"	Upper portion of Parvati practising penance.	1'7" × 1'7"
45	Satanwada (Dist. Narwar).	A Naga sculpture	5'9" × 11"
46	Sunari near Udaypur (Dist. Bhilsa).	A sculpture of Buddha-Avatara (Hindu)...	4'7" × 2'5"

Paintings.

Five coloured copies of Bagh frescoes. (For details see Appendix G.)

Eight drawings in outline of " " " "

One miniature Mughal painting having for its subject a musical dance (natch) before Muhammadan prince attended by courtiers and a servant. Size 14½" by 10½".

Coins.

Twelve Silver coins known as Gadhiya four each of three different sizes. (See Appendix E).
One Copper coin punch marked.

APPENDIX G.

List of Copies of Frescoes at Bagh Made in Samvat 1980.

Description showing locality and subject.	Dimensions.	Artist who copied.
Copies in Colour.		
1 Music in the air from the wall of verandah Cave No. 4 ...	4' 11" × 2' 11"	M. S. Bhand.
Elephant procession " " " ...	9' 9½" × 4' 6¾"	Mainly by A.B. Bhonsle, assisted by Apte, Bhand and Wankar.
Musical dance " " " ...	4' 7½" × 3' 8"	Bhonsle.
Horse procession " " " ...	8' 4" × 4' 6¾"	Apte.
A discourse " " " ...	4' 6" × 2' 6"	"
Copies in Outline		
Part of frieze on right wall, interior Cave No. 4 ...	4' 7" × 2' 6½"	Apte.
Decoration on a pillar " " " ...	3' 4" × 11"	Wankar.
Part of frieze on left wall " " " ...	3' 2" × 2' 2½"	Apte.
Two decorative patterns from a pillar, interior Cave No. 4...	4' 6½" × 1' 9½"	"
Three panels of ceiling decorations and Figure of a worshipper on a cell in Cave No. 3.	2' 11" × 2' 9"	"
Two decorative patterns on a pillar in Cave No. 4 ...	4' 6½" × 4"	"
Decorative pattern on a pillar in Cave No. 4 ...	2' 6" × 11"	Wankar.
Part of frieze with two bulls on left wall, interior Cave No. 4	8' 9" × 4"	Apte.

APPENDIX H.

List of Photographs taken in Samvat 1980.

Serial No.	Local No.	Locality.	Subject.	S Neg
District Bhilsa-				
1	1	Badoh ...	Jain temple before conservation, showing jungle, etc, from South-West.	F
2	2	" ...	North-West. " " " " "	
3	3	" ...	" " interior, before conservation from North-West...	
4	4	" ...	" " " after conservation, from North ...	
5	5	" ...	Solah Khambi showing jungle, etc, before conservation from South-West.	
6	6	" ...	Solah Khambi after conservation, from South-West ...	
7	7	" ...	Gadarnal temple, general view after repairs from North-West.	
8	8	" ...	" " general view after repairs from North...	
9	9	" ...	" " main temple from North-East ...	
10	10	" ...	" " showing porch and basement of main temple from East.	
11	11	" ...	" " " " " from West	
12	1	Pathari ...	Monolith (pillar) from West ...	
13	2	" ...	Unfinished sculpture of Varaha to the east of village ...	
14	1	Jajon ...	Memorial pillar near custom post on road ...	H
15	1	Murtizanagar ...	A ruined shrine known as Vedi ...	
16	1	Udaypur ...	Udayesvar (Nilkantheswar) temple, back view from West ...	
17	2	" ...	" " before repairs, showing trees growing on porch and Vedi.	
District Esagarh.				
18	1	Chanderi ...	Bahadurjika Mazar, general view from North-West ...	
19	2	" ...	Sati stone in compound of Bahadurjika Mazar ...	
20	1	Fatehabad ...	Koshak Mahal interior from West...-	
21	2	" ...	" " showing arches and ceiling on ground floor ...	Ft
22	3	" ...	" " " " " " " "	
23	4	" ...	" " " " " " " " 1st floor.	

Local No.	Locality.	Subject.	Size.
5	Fatehabad.	Koshak Mahal interior showing arches, and ceiling 2nd floor.	Full.
	District Gird.		
1	Gwalior ...	Muhammad Ghaus' tomb, general view from North-East ...	"
1	" Fort ...	Gujari Mahal, interior view of North-West corner ...	"
1	" Museum.	Elephant with rider, from Besnagar ...	"
2	" " ...	Vishnu and Lakshmi riding on Garuda, from Gwalior Fort.	"
3	" " ...	Ashtabhuj Devi standing, from Besnagar ...	"
4	" " ...	Lion capital, from Udaygiri ...	"
5	" " ...	" " " " another view ...	"
6	" " ...	Yogini standing, from Kota ...	"
7	" " ...	Buddha seated, from Kota ...	"
8	" " ...	Parvati standing, from Rairu ...	"
9	" " ...	Maheshvari with baby, from Mohanpur ...	"
10	" " ...	Outline of fresco painting on Bagh Caves— scene of sorrow.	"
11	" " ...	" " discourse ...	"
12	" " ...	" " music in the air ...	"
13	" " ...	" " dance No. 1 ...	"
14	" " ...	" " dance No. 2 ...	"
15	" " ...	" " horse procession ...	"
16	" " ...	" " elephant procession ...	"
17	" " ...	" " supplement of horse procession ...	"
18	" " ...	" " " of elephant procession ...	"
19	" " ...	" " Chaitya ...	"
20	" " ...	" " patterns on pillars ...	"
21	" " ...	" " a wall frieze ...	"
22	" " ...	" " another " ...	Half.
23	" " ...	" " ceiling and frieze ...	"
24	" " ...	" " ceiling only ...	"
25	" " ...	A (painted) copy of Bagh fresco ...	"

Local No.	Locality.	Subject.	Size of Negative.
4	Narwar Fort.	Kachehri, northern portion from South-West ...	Full.
5	"	" an arched doorway ,,	"
6	"	" interior view from inside	"
7	"	" back view	"
8	"	" a ceiling doorway	Half.
9	"	" a corner showing niches	"
10	"	" a pattern on a side wall of an arch	"
11	"	" the portion proposed for Dak Bungalow showing East face.	Full.
12	"	" " interior showing arcade	"
13	"	" " showing detail of plaster work	"
14	"	" " showing detail of jali work	Half.
15	"	" Makaradhvaj Tal, showing a room on top having a sculpture, view from East.	Full.
16	"	" a sculpture from North-West	"
17	"	" one half of a sculptured slab	"
18	"	" the other half of the above slab	"
19	"	" another sculptured slab	Half.
20	"	Katora Tal, from North-East	Full.
21	"	Portuguese church, general view from S. East.	"
22	"	Prostrate goddess	"
23	"	A gun (known as Norwarban)	"
24	"	A large mosque, near Kachehri from North-East	"
25	"	Ladau Bungalow from North-East	"
26	"	Hawa Paur from North-East	"
27	"	The fallen Burj with steps and debris from East	"
28	"	Chhip	Half.
29	"	Map of Narwar Fort	Full.
30	"	" " "	Half.
31	Narwar Town.	Narwar Town, Bird's-eye-view from Fort	Full.
32	"	Ek-khambi Masjid	Half.

Serial No.	Local No.	Locality.	Subject.	Neg
110	33	Nawar Town.	Jait Khamb	E
111	34	"	Chaukoni Baodi from South-West	F
112	35	Between Narwar and Magroni.	Mughal bridge over the Sindh, from North-East ...	
113	36	Between Narwar and Satanwada.	Another bridge over the Sindh, Bird's-eye-view showing valley and bridge from top of hill.	
114	37	"	" showing detail of arched openings of bridge.	
115	1	Ranod.	Khokhai monastery after repair from North-East ...	
116	2	"	" " " " " North-West ...	
117	3	"	" " inscription	
118	1	Satanwada.	Mahadeva temple from North-West	Ha
119	2	"	Vishnu temple from North-West	
District Ujjain.				
120	1	Kaliadeh.	Kaliadeh palace, view from South-East	Ha
121	2	"	" " " from South-West	
122	3	"	" " " from North-West	
123	4	"	A bridge over the Sipra river from North-West ...	
124	1	Ujjain.	Jaisingh's Observatory after repairs, general view from West.	Ha
125	2	"	" " " " " from South.	"
126	3	"	" " " " " from North.	"
127	4	"	" " Digamsa Yantra	"
Miscellaneous.				
128	1	Mathura Museum.	Fragment of Gandhara sculptures	Ful
129	2	" "	Bust of Bodhisatva, a Gandhara sculpture	"

List of Lantern Slides made in Samvat 1980.

Serial No.	Object No.	Particulars.
Stupas.		
1	1	Stupa No. 2 at Sanchi.
2	2	" 3 "
3	3	Stupa at Rajapur.
4	4	Dagoba at Khejadia Bhop.
5	5	Parts of Stupa Rail at Besnagar.
Gateways.		
6-7	1-2	North gateway of great Stupa at Sanchi (Duplicate).
8	3	Torana pillar at Khilchipura.
9-10	4-5	Chhekhamba at Gyaspur (Duplicate).
1	6	Torana at Terhai.
2	7	Elephant gate (Man Mandir).
3	8	Badal Mahal at Chanderi.
Monoliths.		
1	1	Asoka pillar Lauria Nandangarh.
2	2	Heliodorus Garuda pillar before repairs.
3-17	3-4	" " " after "
3	5	Yashodharman pillar A. at Sondni.
4	6	" " B.
5	7	Pillar at Pathari.
Capitals.		
1	1	Palm Capital, Pawaya.
2	2	" " Besnagar.
3	3	Bell and rail capital at Besnagar.
4	4	Fish capital "
5	5	Bell and Lion capital at Udaygiri.
6	6	" " " Sarnath.

Serial No.	Object No.	Particulars.
Rock-cut Caves.		
27	1	Chaitya Hall, Karli.
28	2	,, Cave No. 2, Bagh.
29	3	,, ,, ,, ,,
30	4	Dagoba ,, ,, ,,
31	5	Plan of Cave No. 4 at Bagh.
32	6	Pillar and frieze of Cave No. 4.
33	7	Restored pillar ,, ,,
34-35	8-9	Outline of painting ,, ,, (Duplicate).
36	10	Interior of Cave No. 5.
37	11	General view of caves at Udaygiri.
38	12	Caves Nos. 5 and 6 ,,
39	13	Cave No. 19 ,,
40	14	Door frame of Cave No. 4 at Bagh.
Temples.		
41	1	Gupta Temple at Sanchi.
42	2	Model of Indo-Aryan Temple.
43	3	Mahadeva Temple, Jamli.
44	4	,, ,, at Mahua.
45	5	Lakshmi Temple at Nimthur.
46-47	6-7	Temple at Udaypur (Duplicate),
48	8	,, ,, back view
49	9	Bajra Math, Gyaspur.
50	10	Athkhamba ,, interior view.
51	11	Gadarmal Temple, Badoh.
52	12	Sahdeva's Rath at Mamallapuram.
53-54	13-14	Telika Mandir, Gwalior (Duplicate).
55	15	Large Sas Bahu Temple, Gwalior.
56	16	,, Doorway.
57	17	,, Ceiling.

rial o.	Object No.	Particulars.
18		Temple No. 1 at Surwaya before repairs.
19		" " " after "
20		" 2 " " "
21		Doorway of temple No. 1 "
22		Ceiling " "
23		Temple at Kadwaha.
Inscriptions.		
1		Inscription on Heliodorus pillar, Besnagar.
2		" Udaygiri Caves.
3		" Khokhai Matha, Ranod.
4		" " (part only).
Buddhist Sculptures.		
1		Buddha and his attendants
2		Dvarapalas.
Hindu Sculptures.		
1		Rudra Avatara.
2		Kartikeya.
3		Siva image from Mandasor.
Hindu Monasteries.		
1		Surwaya monastery.
2		" "
3		" "
4-5		Ranod monastery (Duplicate).
6		" "
Sati and Memorial Pillars.		
1		Sati stone, Kolaras.
2		Memorial pillar, Gadhi Barod.
Wells and Step-Wells.		
1		Battisi Baodi, Chanderi.
2		Chopra, Ranod.

Serial No.	Object No.	Particulars.
83	3	Makaradhvaj Tal.
		Forts.
84	1	Atter.
85	2	Narwar.
86	3	Gwalior.
87	4	Chanderi.
88	5	Pichhore (Narwar) Gadhi.
		Palaces and Mahals.
89	1	Koshak Mahal, Fatehabad.
90	2	" " "
91	3	Panchannagar Palace.
92	4	Man Mandir, Gwalior Fort.
93	5	" Interior, "
		Mosques.
94	1	Jamah Masjid at Chanderi.
95	2	" Kolaras.
96	3	Jhinjharla Masjid, Ranod.
97	4	Jamah Masjid at Gwalior.
98	5	Masjid at Kachhaua.
99	6	Bijamandal Masjid at Bhilsa.
		Tombs.
100	1	Tomb of Muhammad Ghaus, Gwalior.
101	2	Rajaka Maqbara, Chanderi.
102	3	Bada Madarsa at "
103	4	Tomb Stone at Ranod.
104-05	1-2	Bridge on the Sindh between Satanwada and Narwar.
106	3	Confluence of the Sindh and Parwati.
		Miscellaneous.
107	4	Welcome.
108	5	Good night.
109	6	Chhip in Narwar Fort.

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89	1	Koshak Mahal, Fatehabad.
90	2	" " "
91	3	Panchamnagar Palace.
92	4	Man Mandir, Gwalior Fort.
93	5	" Interior, "
Mosques.		
94	1	Jamah Masjid at Chanderi.
95	2	" Kolaras.
96	3	Jhinjharia Masjid, Ranod.
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106	3	Confluence of the Sindh and Parwati.
Miscellaneous.		
107	4	Welcome.
108	5	Good night.
109	6	Chhip in Narwar Fort.

APPENDIX J.

List of Drawings Plotted during Sam vat 1980.

Place.	Description.	Scale.
District Bhilsa.		
Badoh	Gadarmal Temple, block plan including attendant shrines, compound, etc.	12' = 1"
"	" " main temple... ..	3' = 1"
"	Solah Khambi, plan	6" = 1"
"	Jain temple, block plan	6' = 1"
Udaypur	Udayeswar temple, sketch site plan.	"
District Narwar.		
Narwar Fort	Kachehri buildings, block plan	8' = 1"
"	Building proposed for Dak Bungalow, G. F. plan	4' = 1"
"	" " " " 1st floor plan	4' = 1"
"	Chhip or stone reservoir, ground plan	2' = 1"
Narwar Town	Dehra or a covered hall containing Jain sculptures (sketch).	

List of Books added to the Office Library in Samvat 1980.

Serial No.	Title.	Remarks
Archæological Survey Reports and Memoirs.		
1	Annual Report of the Archæological Department, Jammu and Kashmir State, for Samvat 1977	Presente
2	Archæological Survey of India, Annual Report, for 1920-21	"
3	" " Ceylon, " " 1921-22	"
4	Report of the Superintendent, Archæological Survey of Burma, for the year ending 31st March 1923.	"
5	Annual Report of the Mysore Archæological Department for 1923	"
6	" " Watson Museum of Antiquities for 1922-23	"
7	Memoirs of the Archæological Survey of India No. 14.	"
8	Report of the India Society for 1923	"
Chronology.		
9	Khare Jantri athava Sivakalina Sampurna Sakavali	Purchase
Epigraphy.		
10	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XVI, Part VII	Presented.
11	" " XVII " II	"
12	" " " " V	"
13	" " " " VI	"
14	" " " " VII	"
15	" " XVIII " IV	"
16	" Carnatica, Vol. II	"
17	" Indo-Moslemica for 1913-14	Purchased.
18	Annual Report on Epigraphy for the year 1921-22	Presented.
19	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XVI, Part VI	"
20	Inscriptions at Shravana Belgola by R. Narsimhacharya	"
21	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XVII, Part I, 1923	"
22	" " " II	"
23	Annual Report on South Indian Epigraphy for 1923.	"
Dictionary.		
24	English and Marathi Dictionary by G. V. Lele	Purchased.

Serial No.	Title.	Remarks.
Art.		
25	Introduction to Indian Art by A. K. Coomarswami	Purchased.
26	The Women of the Ajanta Caves by W. E. G. Soloman	"
27	Examples of Indian Sculptures at the British Museum	Presented.
History.		
28	Eminent Orientalists	Purchased.
29	Marathi Riyashat, Part II, by G. C. Sardesai	"
30	" " III	"
31	The Light of Asia by Sir E. Arnold	"
32	Indian Teachers of the Buddhist Universities by Phanindra Nath Bose	"
33	Tutankhaman and Discovery of his Tomb by G. E. Smith	"
34	Three Years in Tibet by S. E. Kawaguchi	"
35	The Dravidian Element in Indian Culture by G. Slater	"
36	A Short History of India from the Earliest Times to the Present Day by E.B. Havell.	"
37	Shree Harsha of Kanauj by K. M. Panikkar	"
38	Tutankhaman by Sir E. A. Wallis Budge	"
39	A Peep into the Early History of India by Sir R. G. Bhandarkar	"
Journals.		
40	Index to Vols. I to L (1872-1921) Indian Antiquary, Part I, by L. M. Anstey.	"
1-51	Indian Antiquary from June 1923 to April 1924	"
2-57	Modern Review from January 1924 to June 1924	"
58	Index to Vols. I to L (1872-1921) Indian Antiquary, Part II & III, by L. M. Anstey.	"
59	Index to Indian Antiquary, Vol. LII, 1923	"
60	Burlington Magazine for October 1923	"
61	The Quarterly Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XIII, No. 4	"
2-64	" " " " XIV, Nos. 1 to 3	"
5-76	Rupam Nos. 1, 2, 4, and 9 to 17	"
77	Proceedings of the Asiatic Society of Bengal, No. II, February 1888	"
78	Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland, 3rd quarter, July 1923.	"

Serial No.	Title.	Remark
79	Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland, 4th quarter, October 1923.	Purchase
80	Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland, 2nd quarter, April 1924.	"
81	Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal, Vol. LVIII, Part I, No. I, 1889 ...	"
82	" " " " " II ...	"
83	" " " " " III ...	"
84	Luzac's Oriental List of Book Reviews, Vol. XXXIV, October-December, 1923.	"
Literature.		
85	Brihat Samhita by Varahmihir, Vol. X, Part I	"
86	" " " II	"
87	Mayamata of Mayamuni by Ganpati Sastri	"
88	Kothasaritsagar by Somadeva Bhatta	"
89	Shri Shankaracharya ani tyancha Sampradaya by M. R. Bodas	"
90	Essey on Gunadhya and Brahatkatha	"
Miscellaneous.		
91	The Ancient Monuments Preservation Regulation of Jammu and Kashmir States.	Presented
Architecture.		
92	A summary of the Manasara by P. K. Acharya	"
Numismatics.		
93	Supplementary Catalogue of the Coins in the Indian Museum, Calcutta, Vol. V, by B. B. Bidya Binod.	"
State Publications.		
94	Annual Administration Report of the Department of Economic Development Board of the Gwalior State for 1978.	"
95	Administration of the Gwalior State during the year 1920-21	"
96	Catalogue of Books in the Secretariat General Library, Part I	"
97	" " " " " " II	"
98	Commercial Directory of the Gwalior State	"
99	Guide to Gwalior and Shivpuri, by B. F. Cavanaugh	Purchased
100	Darbar Policy (General)	"
101	Policy Home Department	"

Serial No.	Title.	Remarks.
102	Correspondence Manual	Purchased.
103	Accounts Manual	"
104	Civil Service Rules	"
105	H. H. Maharaja Scindia's Speeches, Vol. I, by R. D. Vaishya ...	"
106	" " " II, " " ...	"
107	Directory of Chironji Block	Presented.
108	Engineering Code, Part I	Purchased.
109	General Statistics of the Gwalior State for Samvat 1930	Presented.
10-25	Memorandum Nos. 1, 2, 5, 5, 11 to 15 and 16 to 22	Purchased.
26-31	Memorandum Nos. 24-29	Presented.
132	" No. 30	"
33-34	" Nos. 10 and 23	Purchased.

APPENDIX L.

Statement of Income realised in Samvat 1980.

No.	Head.	Amount.			Remar
		Rs.	a.	p.	
1	By sale of stone images (duplicates)	350	0	0	
2	„ Guide to Surwaya	20	1	5	
3	„ Gwalior Fort Album	43	8	0	
4	„ Photo prints	13	6	2	
5	Miscellaneous	6	11	0	
	TOTAL	433	10	7	

APPENDIX M.

Statement of Expenditure incurred in Samvat 1980.

No.	Head.	Amount current year.			Amount last year.			Total Amount
		Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	p.	
1	Salaries	8,370	6	3	Nil.			8,370 6
2	Travelling allowances	2,259	3	0	„			2,259 3
3	Contingencies	1,484	10	9	„			1,484 10
4	Books	313	3	6	„			313 3
5	Museum	901	12	10	127	8	0	1,029 4
6	Works—							
	(a) Conservation proper	7,370	0	11	4,215	6	6	11,585 7
	(b) Sending copies of frescoes to England	135	5	3	Nil.			135 5
	(c) Publication of Gwalior Fort Album ...	299	11	8	„			299 11
	(d) Salaries of staff charged to works ...	398	11	0	„			398 11
7	Miscellaneous head	494	1	3	„			494 1
8	Expenditure over and above budget grant,	195	0	6	„			195 0
	TOTAL	22,222	2	5	4,342	14	6	26,565 0 1

(a) Khokhai Hindu Monastery at Ranod, after repair.

(b) Gadarmal Temple at Badoh.
General view from N. E. after clearance and repair.

PLATE II.

(b) Inscribed monolithic Pillar, Pathari.

(a) Udayeswar Temple, Udaypur : back view.

(a) Buddha incarnation of Vishnu, from Sunari.

(b) Siva, from Kota.

(c) A dancing goddess, from Mandasor.

(d) Agni, from Kota.

(a) Trimurti, from Padhavli.

(b) Busts of Varahi and another goddess, from Badoh.

(c) Siva, from Badoh.

(d) Indrani, from Kota.

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF THE
ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT, GWALIOR STATE

FOR
The Year ending 30th June 1925, Samvat 1981.

P A R T I.

I. OFFICE NOTES.

1. **Charge.**—During the year of report the undersigned held charge of the Department except from the 1st to the 19th of July, while he was on privilege leave. During the period of leave, the charge of the current duties of the post remained with R. S. Saksena, the Archæological Overseer.

2. **Leave.**—The Superintendent availed himself of 19 days' privilege leave in continuation of similar leave which he enjoyed at the end of the preceding year.

Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows :—

- (a) Photographer-Draughtsman—privilege leave of 22 days from the 9th to the 30th June 1925 and sick leave on medical certificate for 9 days from the 1st to the 9th July 1924.
- (b) General Assistant—privilege leave for 30 days from the 1st to the 9th July and from the 14th November to the 4th December 1924.
- (c) Officer Sarishta—privilege leave for 17 days in all, in the months of July, August and September 1924.

3. **New Post.**—Hitherto one and the same clerk used to manage the correspondence and record work in this office. But with the increase of work this task began to prove increasingly difficult and systematic work became almost impossible. In response to my representation the Darbar were pleased to sanction a record-keeper's post in the year of report.

4. **General.**—All the office staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

Home Member Sahib inspected this office on the 4th of May and the general impression he carried as a result of the inspection is recorded by him in the Inspection Book as follows:—

दफ्तर का काम मैंने अच्छा पाया. सुपरिन्टेण्डेंट साहब काम में दिव्यचस्वी और मेहनत करते हैं. इनका अमला भी होशियार और मेहनती मादम हुआ, खास करके इनका एहक़ार खंडाकर यह काबिच तरकी है. किसी दूसरे महक़मे में जगह ज्यादा मुशाहिरें की खाड़ी हुई, तो इसको ज़रूर मौका दिया जाना चाहिये.

II. Circulars and Orders.

5. No Circulars or Departmental Orders with special reference to this Department, were issued in the year of report.

III. Work at Headquarters.

6. In addition to the ordinary routine of office the following work was done during the headquarter season:—

- (a) Annual Administration Report for Samvat 1980 was drawn up and submitted.
- (b) A resume of the Conservation and Exploration accomplished by the Department in the year 1923-24 (Samvat 1980) was contributed to the *Annual Report of the Archæological Survey of India*.
- (c) An illustrated article on Chanderi was contributed to the Birthday Special Number of the *Jayaji Pratap*.
- (d) A number of lantern slides were prepared to supplement the previous collection.
- (e) New acquisitions brought into the Archæological Museum were arranged and labelled.
- (f) A Hindi translation of the *Gwalior Fort Album* was prepared and published.
- (g) A detailed Circular for the preservation of Ancient Monuments in this State was drafted.
- (h) Magic lantern shows illustrating the Archæological monuments and sculptures in the State were given at two local centres of the Ganapati festival.

IV. Tours.

7. During the year under report I spent 124 days in camp, partly for

- (a) Listing monuments.
- (b) Annual inspection of the principal groups of monuments conserved already.
- (c) Supervising and directing the works of conservation in progress.
- (d) Collecting material and taking necessary photographs for the proposed publication of *A Guide to Chanderi*.
- (e) Carrying out excavations at Pawaya.

8. The following places were visited for listing monuments:—Khanpura, Naderi, Gurilako Pahad, Lakhari, Bithla and Rakhetra or Gadhelna. Visits of annual inspection were paid to conserved monuments at Gwalior, Bhilsa, Besnagar, Udaygiri, Badoh, Chanderi, Fatehabad, Ujjain, Bagh, Narwar and Surwaya. I visited Bagh and Chanderi each twice and Narwar four times in order to direct the conservation work in progress there. I also visited Udaypur, Budhi Chanderi, Mandasor, Sondni and Khilchipura in connection with the proposed conservation of the monuments at these places. I encamped at Pawaya for over two weeks in all during four visits in order to supervise and direct the excavation works at this ancient site, and at Chanderi for a week in order to collect material for the proposed publication of an illustrated Guide to this place. Detailed Diary of the tour is given in Appendix A.

9. During the year of report Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archaeology in India, paid a visit to Bagh Caves. Dr. J. H. Cousins, the well-known art critic, also visited these Caves in my company.

V. Conservation.

10. Conservation work was carried out at the following places at a total expenditure of Rs. 29,584-1-0 including the special grant for Narwar Fort :—

1. **Bagh** (District Amjhera).—The work of clearing debris from the Buddhist caves which had been going on for the last three years was brought to a completion. The work in cave No. 4 was specially difficult as it was also important. The main hall and the surrounding corridors were filled up almost to the ceiling with huge blocks of rock partly consisting of decayed pillars and partly fallen from the ceiling. The monolithic pillars supporting the ceiling, having disappeared for the most part, large spans of ceiling are overhanging and threatening to come down at any moment. To work under them was therefore attended with considerable danger. A small portion of the ceiling did come down, in spite of careful precautions, while the labourers were working below; but fortunately nobody was hurt and the work was completed without any serious mishap. A small portion of debris still remains inside cave No. 4 as it is dangerous to remove it unless the ceiling is re-supported on masonry pillars.

11. Last year a mound of debris in the joint verandah of caves Nos. 4 and 5 had been left over to serve as a scaffolding for the artists engaged to copy the frescoes on the back wall of the verandah. The copying work being over the mound was cleared off in the year under report.

12. Cave No. 3 also was completely freed from the enormous mass of debris choking its interior and particularly its entrance.

13. Caves Nos. 2, 3, 4 and 5, the only caves in this group that are worthy or capable of preservation, have now been freed from practically all the debris but caves Nos. 4 and 5, especially the former which is also the most interesting in the series, are immediately in need of masonry supports to prop up their overhanging ceilings and this work awaits being undertaken in the coming season.

14. Only a small portion of the vast expanse of frescoes that originally adorned the walls of the spacious verandah of caves Nos 4 and 5 is now surviving and this too is in a very precarious condition being badly exposed to weather, the protecting roof of the verandah having fallen away. And moreover being quite an out-of-the-way place, Bagh attracts but few visitors. Hence the question of removing the frescoes bodily and exhibiting them suitably at a central place like Gwalior with the double object of securing the valuable relics against total destruction and of making them easily accessible to visitors was under consideration.

15. Expert advice on this point was sought from Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archaeology in India, who very kindly took the trouble to examine the frescoes on the spot in February and advised that considering the condition of the paintings their removal would be both unjustifiable and impracticable. The idea of removing the frescoes has therefore been finally abandoned and it has been decided to carry out Sir John's recommend-

ations to erect a verandah of a simple design of timber and steel roofed over with suitable tiles, in front of the frescoes to protect them *in situ* from rain and dust.

16. **Chanderi.**—The monuments conserved at this place during the year of report are: (a) Katighati, (b) the Delhi gate, (c) Shahzadika Roza, (d) Madarsa tomb, (e) Battisi Baodi and some minor domes.

17. (a) Katighati is the name of a pass cut through a hill where it is crossed by the old road leading from Chanderi towards the South. In the middle of the cutting a screen of rock is carved in the form of a pointed archway which on its northern face is flanked on either side by a tapering tower or bastion also hewn in the living rock. In the eastern wall of the cutting a flight of steps is carved out for getting up to the roof over the gate. The gateway bears an inscription in Sanskrit as well as in Persian recording that it was made by Jimankhan, son of Sherkhan in Samvat 1547 (= A. C. 1490) during the reign of Ghias Shah of Malwa.

18. The gateway was over-grown with jungle including five or six rather big trees which had thrust their roots into the crevices of the rock and were threatening to split it. The jungle was cleared away, the trees cut off and their roots extracted. Heaps of debris blocked the site of the road on both sides all along the cutting. These were dug up and thrown away. Structural parapet walls and a room of rubble masonry built in later times on the top of the rock-cut gateway were in a dilapidated condition. A large mass of debris consisting of rubble mixed with earth, which came out of these ruins, formed an unnecessary weight on the top of the rock and was a constant source of trouble as it provided a favourable breeding ground to small vegetation and large trees. The debris was therefore cleared off. The top of the gateway was made proof against rain water entering the crevices or percolating in the rock, by laying a coat of stone concrete in lime over it. The parapet walls were restored to an average height of 2 feet above the level of the concrete roof. There was no means to ascertain in what manner the top line of the walls had originally been finished. The tops of walls were therefore left uneven so as to impart them an unfinished appearance. Stone spouts were provided to throw off the rain water on the roof clear of the gateway.

19. (b) Delhi Darwaza is the principal gate in the city wall of Chanderi and faces the north. The gateway is flanked by a circular bastion on either side. It bears a Persian inscription stating that it was erected in A. H. 814 (= A. C. 1411). It is thus one of the oldest monuments at this place.

20. It was freed from small jungle. Two small banyan trees growing on it were rooted out. The debris of a rubble hut put up on the top of the gate in later times to serve, it is said, as quarters for a police guard, was picked up and thrown away as it was causing a dangerous burden on the ceiling slabs of the gateway and was also serving as a breeding ground for vegetation and trees. A ceiling slab which had cracked was replaced by a new one.

21. (c) Shahazadika Roza—It is a small but fine specimen of a tomb. It consists of a single domed chamber standing on a high plinth. The loss of dome has deprived it of half its beauty but nevertheless its ornamental

features, namely, the cornices, the lines of eaves supported on wavy brackets, and the top course of decorative battlements on the exterior, as well as the pointed arches, the rosettes and the ornamented base of the dome in the interior make it a monument well worth preservation.

22. It was freed from grass and jungle of trees, small and large, with which it was enveloped both inside and outside. The inside of the chamber was full of debris fallen from the ruins of the dome above. It was cleared off, so as to expose the original lime floor. The grave stones which had got displaced were reset properly. The heaps of debris and rubbish in which the plinth was half buried were dug out and dressed up into a regular platform. As the interior view of the tomb is interesting, steps were provided leading to the entrance door at the top of the high plinth.

23. (d) Madarsa Tomb—This monument had been partially conserved two years ago. But the ground surrounding the monument sloped sharply on one side which helped rain water to wash away and undermine the foundations of its plinth. Partly to prevent this damage, partly to cover up the unsightly debris and thus to impart the tomb a neat and tidy appearance, an earth platform extending up to a width of 10 feet from the sides of the plinth, with a level top and regular slopes was put up. Boundary pillars enclosing a square area 25 feet all round the monument were set up and the intervening space cleared and tidied up. A line of jungle 10 feet wide was cut up and cleared away in order to make the monument visible and easily accessible from the adjoining shikar road which is motorable.

24. (e) Battisi Baodi—This is the largest and perhaps the most remarkable of all the baodis which are proverbially numerous at Chanderi. It is a square tank 60 feet each way and sinks by four stages or storeys. Besides the principal stairway which is in the south side there are two flights of steps in each of the four sides of each of the four storeys thus making the number of stairs thirty-two from which apparently the well takes its name. It is built of chisel dressed stone and is said to have originally stood in the midst of a beautiful park which perhaps justified the author of the inscription on the well, exclaiming 'if any one visits this place he will say "It is Heaven."' The inscription records that the well was built in A. H. 890 (= A. C. 1485) in the reign of Ghias Shah Khalji of Mandu.

25. The jungle growing on the masonry and within an area of 25 feet all round the well was cleared off. The rubble walls of a hut built in later times, stood in a dilapidated condition near the south-east corner of the well and disfigured its view. They were therefore dismantled and thrown away. The coping slabs on the top of the retaining walls of the well and the paving stones on the top of the platform in front of the principal stairs of the well which serves as a seat for visitors had sunk in places. They were raised up and properly reset.

26. Boundary stone pillars were set up enclosing an area of 25 feet all round the well including the main stairs and the platform which projects on the south side of the well. A fair weather road was laid out to connect the well with the shikar road between Chanderi and Budhi Chanderi and a notice board was erected at the junction to call attention of passers by.

27. (f) **Minor Monuments**—Besides these some minor monuments at Chanderi also received attention. For instance, the simple domed tomb known as Akol-ki-Bag-ka-Gumbaz was freed from jungle and petty repairs done to its compound wall. Another small tomb named Badaiyon-ka-Gumbaz also was freed from jungle and the masonry of its plinth wherever damaged was made good. Further the isolated but handsome gateway called Badal Mahal "Darwaza" which stood in the midst of dense jungle was liberated from it.

28. **Budhi Chanderi**.—The ruins of the old or pre-Muhammadan Chanderi which appears to have been deserted soon after the Muhammadan conquest of that tract of country in favour of the present site of Chanderi are now enveloped in large and thick jungle and have become a favourite haunt of wild beasts. The town is popularly believed to have been the capital of the Chedi king Sisupala who was the rival of Sri Krishna, but the existing vestiges of temples and houses do not carry the antiquity of the place beyond the 9th century A. C. The town possessed quite a number of temples in three different groups all of which with two solitary exceptions are now reduced to mere heaps of debris. The temples are predominantly of the Digambara Jaina sect. Judging from the style of architecture and sculpture they range between the 9th and 11th centuries. The conservation of the temples except perhaps of one or two is out of question. But the ruins contain many sculptures of the Jaina Tirthankaras, which, both from the artistic and iconographic point of view, are of great interest and hence too good to be left to themselves. It is therefore proposed to pick these up from the debris in which most of them lie buried and arrange them into groups near the temple to which they originally belonged. As a preliminary measure the most important group of the ruins which lies at the south-east corner of the site of the town was cleared of jungle to facilitate close examination of the sculptures and carvings. The open courtyard of one of the two temples which are standing was freed from jungle and debris with which it was choked and some beautiful sculptures of Tirthankaras exposed in the debris or lying scattered on the site were picked up and arranged in order against the wall of the court, to form a sort of open air museum. It is proposed to pursue this same process with regard to other important temples in this group. This work will be taken up as soon as convenient.

29. **Udaypur**.—It was stated in the last year's report that the famous Nilakanthesvar temple had been taken in hand for conservation and the repairs to the temple proper and the mosque near it had been mostly carried out. It was further stated that a proposal to acquire the *kacheha* houses which have trespassed into the original spacious compound of the temple and thus disfigured its appearance was under consideration. The proposal having been sanctioned proceedings were instituted to acquire the houses by compensating the owners under *Qanun Husul Arazi* (The Land Acquisition Act). The acquisition has now been effected and the work of throwing away rubbish and debris from the open areas and exposing the original pavement floor of the compound is in progress. The work of dismantling the houses themselves is postponed till after the rainy season.

30. **Narwar.**—Within the walls of the hill fort of Narwar stand the ruins of an extensive town of the Rajput period not more than half a dozen houses in which are now inhabited. It is well known that in pre-Muhammadan times Narwar teemed with Jaina and Hindu temples which were subsequently demolished by the order of Sikandar Lodi of Delhi. At present there is not a single pre-Muhammadan building on the fort except perhaps the large tank known as Makardhvaja Tal and the remains of a small medieval shrine near the Hawa Paur or Wind Gate, on the eastern road to the fort.

31. The eastern portion of the town on the fort was occupied by a group of *Mahals* or residential palaces of the ruling families, which are separated from the rest of the town, by means of a tall enclosure wall. These appear to have been built by the later Kachhawaha (or may be by Tomaru) chiefs and are thus not more than 300 years old. The style of architecture is Rajput. The pillars are fluted and tapering upwards. The arches are of multifoil designs. The ceilings and roofs are all flat and in places the walls and ceilings show remnants of paintings in which men and women in Rajput costume can be clearly traced. The buildings are mostly two-storeyed. There are a series of enclosures forming separate units containing audience halls, baths, garden pavilions, harems with screened windows and galleries and quite a number of swing-posts. One of these Mahals called Kachehri Mahal which possesses some fine ornamental work of plaster inlaid with glass, and part of which is set on the eastern verge of the fort, thus commanding a view of the valley of the Sindh river which after rounding the fort-hill flows in the eastern direction, appealed to the tasteful fancy of His late Highness who ordered that the whole of the Mahal should be cleared up generally and the eastern part of it should be thoroughly repaired and converted into a rest-house.

32. This work having been entrusted to this Department and a special grant sanctioned for this purpose, the necessary repairs are being carried out, due care being taken to preserve the original design of the general plan and the decorations as far as possible. Along with this the following works were carried out with regard to other old buildings of interest on the fort.

33. The approach-road was improved by making a fair weather road from the *Bazar* to the foot of the hill, repairing the *Kharanja* of the old paved road, providing supplementary stairs of masonry steps along side that portion of the old road where it was too steep and had become slippery with the wearing away of its pavement, dismantling and re-building one of the big bastions which had fallen and blocked the road and providing a fair weather road from the top-most gate of the fort up to the Kachehri Mahal, dangerous portions of buildings on both sides of this road having been either dismantled, repaired or tidied up.

34. The other old palaces which are of considerable architectural interest being in an advanced condition of ruin and covered up with jungle had become inaccessible to visitors. A decent foot-path giving access to most of the more interesting buildings and objects was therefore laid out after cutting the strips of jungle and clearing away the heaps of debris which came in the

way and dismantling or repairing the portions of masonry which appeared to be dangerous to the safety of the visitors.

34. (a) The Ladau Bungalow which is comparatively a later building and is almost intact was thoroughly cleared of jungle and debris. The damaged portions of the retaining walls of its plinth were repaired and the fallen pieces of the *Jali* enclosure were reset.

35. (b) The building known as Chhip Mahal was similarly cleared. The chief object of interest about this Mahal and from which the latter takes its name is a large monolithic trough carved out in the form of a trefoil oval in a block of pink-coloured stone. It is popularly known as Chhip. It is locally believed to have been used as the receptacle of pounded saffron, a mark of which was put on the forehead of each Rajput soldier before he proceeded to the fighting line. It may have been used for this purpose or else as a tub for royal bath. The area round about the Chhip was completely cleared, damaged portions of the masonry and the terrace close by were repaired and a flight of steps was provided to get up to the spot in place of a slippery and sloping path over heaps of debris.

36. (c) The retaining walls of the old tank known as Makaradhvaja Tal were repaired wherever they had been damaged. In the bed of the tank there are several wells from one of which it is proposed to take water to the rest-house by means of a hand-pump and a line of pipes.

37. (d) The big mosque built by Sikandar Lodi was freed from jungle and debris.

38. (e) The compound of a tomb known as Madar Shah-ki-Dargah was cleared of rubbish and tidied up.

39. (f) Another monument conserved at Narwar during the year of report is the *Jai Khamba* or pillar of victory, an inscription on which records the genealogy of the Tomara kings of Gwalior and Narwar. This monolithic pillar is about 20 feet high above the ground and stands nearly two furlong east of the road from Narwar to Magroni at a distance of about $1\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the north-east of the town of Narwar. It appears that there was originally some sort of a platform round the base of the pillar. But nothing survived out of it except a few stray boulders. Owing to the absence of any protection the earth round the base of the column was being gradually washed away and the foundations were in danger of being undermined. To ensure the stability of the pillar therefore, a platform $10' \times 10' \times 3'$ of dry rubble masonry was put up round its base with steps in the east face, the top being paved with stone slabs laid in lime. From the top of the new platform one can conveniently examine the inscription which is only $5\frac{1}{2}$ feet high above the platform. It is further proposed to fix up a tablet on the platform giving a substance of the original inscription in English and Hindi.

40. Mandasor.—Another group of monuments selected for conservation during the year of report consists of the huge sculpture of Siva in the fort of Mandasor, the famous inscribed pillars of Yasodharman at Sondni about two miles to the south-east of Mandasor and the Torana pillar at Khilchippura about two miles south of Mandasor. A detailed reference to this work

however had better been reserved for the next year's Report, as only a nominal beginning has been made this year.

41. A list of monuments conserved is shown in Appendix B.

VI. Annual Upkeep and Maintenance.

42. Annual clearance and maintenance were attended to in the case of all the important groups of conserved monuments.

43. There was an unfortunate case of vandalism in the year of report. It related to the famous Koshak Mahal near Chanderi. The lower subordinates of the P. W. D. and the contractors who worked under them were the offenders.

44. The case was referred to the Administrative Officer, P. W. D., for necessary disciplinary action.

45. It is further proposed to appoint a caretaker to look after the monuments at Chanderi.

46. It is requested that the public will be good enough to treat these National Relics with the reverence they deserve.

VII. Exploration.

(a) Excavations.

47. Trial excavations were made in the year of report at Pawaya. Pawaya is situated at the confluence of the Sindh and the Parvati about 40 miles to the south-west of Gwalior. The site has been identified as the ancient town of Padmavati, one of the three capitals of the Nagas (for a detailed description of the site and its antiquities see my article on 'The Site of Padmavati' in the *Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey of India* for 1915-16, pp. 104-105).

48. Naga coins, and sculptures dating from the Sunga and Gupta period (100 to 500 A. C.) have been found here. The ground in the whole area is studded with brick bats, and brick wallings are met with under ground. Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archaeology in India, visited the place in 1920 and agreed with me that it looked like a promising site for archaeological excavations. As the history of the Nagas is still veiled in obscurity it is hoped that systematic excavations of Padmavati may illuminate that obscure period (3rd-4th centuries) of Indian History. The work however is an expensive one and with the limited funds at our disposal we have but to work little by little and wait patiently for the fulfilment of the expectations.

49. The spot selected for the trial excavations this year is a conspicuous artificial mound about half a mile towards the north, outside the site of the city proper. The mound measures nearly 200 feet by 200 feet by 30 feet (high). The area around was studded with brick bats. The palm capital of a stone pillar was discovered lying at its foot some years ago. There was therefore every indication that the mound contained in its womb the ruins of an ancient structure.

50. The work of excavations was carried on for about six weeks in all. An average of 100 coolies a day was employed. On opening the mound by means of radiating trenches on all the four sides, the retaining walls of a big

square platform were lighted upon. The position of the four sides of the platform having been defined, digging was concentrated on the east side where the approach steps or a gate was expected to exist. So far we have been able to clear up the four corners of the platform, the immediate neighbourhood of the east retaining wall, and small portions here and there of the other three retaining walls. The platform is a solid one. It is constructed of large bricks laid in clay mortar. The average size of bricks is $18'' \times 9'' \times 3''$. The platform rises in a number of stages, each stage being marked by an offset. Each side measures 140 feet long approximately. The existing height of the platform is 30 feet. So far no approach stairs or gateway has been discovered. Remnants have been found of a smaller platform also square on plan and superimposed upon the lower one. This latter platform is also solid and measures 56 feet each way. The exterior of this platform is decorated with a horizontal moulding at the base and ornamental vertical pilasters at regular intervals all in brick. It appears that the exterior of the building was further decorated with *terra cotta* figures and carvings, a number of which have been found in the diggings. None of these however was found *in situ*.

51. On the evidence so far disclosed it has not been possible to decide once for all the nature of the monument that we have come upon. The solidarity and the dimensions of the platform point to its being a *stupa*. Instances of *stupas* with square plinths are not uncommon. But, on the other hand, no relics or sculptures distinctly Buddhist or Jaina have so far been found associated with this structure. A well sunk in the centre of the top of the platform and carried down right up to the ground level disclosed no trace of any kind of relics. Moreover, the few pieces of stone sculptures that have been unearthed in these excavations are all of a Brahmanical nature. For instance, fragments of a big lintel of a *Torana* gateway have been found; the subjects sculptured on which are all from Brahmanical mythology, namely, (1) the scene of Bali's sacrifice and Vishnu taking the three strides, (2) Karttikeya, (3) the scene of the churning of the ocean, etc. The subjects on the carved decorative bricks are all secular and afford no clue to distinguish the sectarian character of the monument. It may be that we have after all come upon a Brahmanical temple perched on the top of a huge platform. If this surmise is correct,—further excavations alone will show if it is so—there is no hope of finding the temple itself. It has already disappeared. There is however some hope of finding the remnants of its decorations, a gateway or gateways which gave access to the place and last but not least a stone column probably recording the history of this monument in an inscription. That one or more gateways and the pillar originally existed here is evident from the big piece of carved stone lintel unearthed in the excavations and from the stone palm capital which was found lying on the site some years ago.

52. Strangely enough not a single coin was found in the diggings although a number of them are found on the site of the city proper above the surface of the ruins, after rains. The age of the building discovered can, however, be determined with some certainty. It cannot be later than the early Gupta period, as the style of all the stone sculptures and of carvings on bricks unearthed point distinctly to that period.

53. A descriptive list of all the more important antiquities unearthed in these diggings is given in Appendix C.

54. Fuller details of the excavations must be reserved until the work makes further progress in subsequent years.

(b) **Listing.**

55. In the year of report 33 monuments comprising temples, groups of rock-cut sculptures, mahals, mosques, tombs, old wells, sati stones, etc. situated at 11 different places were listed. A list of these appears in Appendix D. The following is a brief description of the monuments.

56. **Chanderi.**—About a mile to the north-east of the town of Chanderi are the ruins of a large enclosure with two gateways, one in the centre of its east wall and the other in the centre of the north wall. The eastern gateway which is the better preserved of the two is a double arch built one over the other. Above the inner arch which forms the entrance is an arched window with projecting brackets which supported a balcony. The gateway is flanked on either side by a tall round *minar* the upper portion of which has fallen away. The northern gate was similar in design but is in a worse state of disrepair though its *minars* have still preserved their tops. The enclosure wall is of rubble and is now mostly fallen. The area enclosed is about 200 feet \times 200 feet. There are no traces of buildings inside and it is doubtful what purpose it was intended to serve. People call it *Mehman Sarai* or guest-house. If the tradition is correct probably tents were pitched inside the enclosure to accommodate the guests. It is curious that both the gates of this enclosure face away from the town.

57. A short distance to the north of this enclosure is a small *minar* and a square well called Bandar Baodi or Monkey well. Why it is so-called is not known.

58. Nearly a furlong further east is a mosque and a square Baodi in a grove known as Qazi's Bag. The mosque bears a Persian inscription recording its construction in the reign of Aurangzeb in A. H. 1113 = A. C. 1701.

59. A little further is a group of about a dozen small *maqbaras* or tombs only two of which have retained their domes. Interspersed in the tombs are three mosques. One of the mosques and one of the tombs bear inscriptions showing that they are works of the reign of Aurangzeb. Some of these tombs possess finely perforated stone screens which form the side-walls of their rooms.

60. Still further east about three furlongs on the other side of the Singhpur Road is a square step well called Chandai Baodi. It sinks in stages two of which were visible above water at the time of my visit. But I was told there were two more stages concealed under water. An ornamental horizontal band demarcates the highest storey from the one next below. Two stairs are provided in each face of every stage. At the top the well measures 54' \times 54'. In the second storey from above there is a niche in each of its three sides southern, eastern and western. The southern niche is empty. The eastern niche is occupied by a Sanskrit inscription and the western niche by a Persian inscription probably a translation of the former. The inscription

slabs are badly worn out by water and weather and the lower portions of the epigraphs are altogether lost. From the salutation to and praise of the *Jinas* in the opening lines of the Sanskrit record it would appear that the well is the work of a Jaina donor.

61. Chetan Baodi is a circular step well situated in the north-east portion of the town. Its diameter is 29'6". The construction of steps in the lower half portion of the well is peculiar. They are set obliquely instead of being at right angles to the wall.

62. The Jaina temple popularly known as Chaubisi in the town of Chanderi is remarkable for the life-size idols in Jaipur marble of all the 24 (*Chaubisi*) *Tirthamkaras* which are enshrined there, each in a cell crowned with a conical spire and arranged round a rectangular courtyard. Every idol is made in accordance with the specification as to *varna* (colour), *lanchhana* (symbol), etc., given in old works on Jaina iconography. The temple is however not very old being built in V. S. 1893=1836 A. C. by Hirde Sahai, a well-wisher (*Subha Chintaka*) of Mardan Singh, a Bundela king of Chanderi. Outside the quadrangle is a bigger shrine-room covered with a hemispherical dome sheltering a number of promiscuous images of *Tirthamkaras*. This is a few years older than the Chaubisi temple being constructed in V. S. 1857 or A. C. 1800.

63. There is another Jaina temple in the town which possesses some old images, namely, an image of Parsvanatha, dated V. S. 1252, a sculpture of goddess Padmavati, dated in V.S. 1291, and another idol of a *Tirthamkara* dated V. S. 1316.

64. Another temple listed in the year at the same place is a small domed shrine of Siva situated near what is known as Dariba Baodi, a short distance to the east of Paramesvari Tal. The shrine bears on the lintel of its door an interesting inscription in pure Sanskrit poetry (Kavya style) recording that it was constructed by Sri Manasimha, one of the Bundela kings, in V. S. 1784. The temple is called Manasimhesvarn after the name of its founder.

65. Other monuments noticed at Chanderi are the two mosques known as Hatpura-ki-Masjid and Mirza-ki-Masjid both with inscriptions, two tombs of Christian soldiers in the army led by J. B. Filose as the tablets on them are dated in A. C. 1816 and 1819, respectively, and a rectangular masonry-built tank named Visurkund or Vishnukund in the neighbourhood of another similar tank named Harakund.

66. **Singhpur.**—Three miles to the north-east of Chanderi stands one of the *Mahals* built by Bandela Rajas of Chanderi. It is picturesquely situated in the midst of charming mountain scenery overlooking a lake. But for its pleasant site it is in no way remarkable. It has been repaired and converted into a shooting box or rest-house by the order of the late Maharaja Scindia.

67. **Khanpura.**—Khanpura is a village about 4 miles to the east of Chanderi. On the eastern outskirts of the village stand a few Sati stones one of which bears an inscription, dated V. S. 1545=A. C. 1488.

68. **Gurila-ka-Pahad.**—About 8 miles to the south-east of Chanderi is the hill known as Gurila-ka-Pahad. On the top of the hill which is rather difficult of access are the ruins of two temples of the Digambara Jaina sect standing

in an enclosure of rough masonry. One of these consists of a shrine room and an entrance-porch facing west. On the shrine is a hemispherical dome of which the rubble frame is now exposed its plaster facing having peeled off. Enshrined is a big image of Santinatha 11' 9" tall but broken in twain across the neck.

69. Facing this is another temple consisting of an oblong shrine room with three entrance doors and a pillared verandah in front. The temple is 20' long and 17' 3" wide externally and has a flat roof. There are in all 26 images of Jaina *Tirthankaras* (some standing, others seated) leaning against the three walls of the shrine. The central image is that of Adinatha. None of the other images bears a *lanchhana* or distinctive symbol by which it can be identified.

70. Two lines of an obliterated inscription on a wall of the temple—probably a pilgrim's record—is dated in V. S. 1307. The temple therefore cannot be later than this date.

71. **Naderi.**—At the foot of this hill is the village called Naderi. It possesses a number of old relics. The earliest is a Sati memorial not less than five or six centuries old. The sculpture on it shows that it is the memorial of a man killed by a tiger, and his wife who cremated herself on his funeral pyre.

72. Another inscribed Sati pillar near a well called Dhimara is dated in V. S. 1545, which records that the Sati was a blacksmith's wife. This record gives the old name of the villages as Guler from which evidently the adjoining hill has derived its name Gurila-ka-Pahad by an interchange of letters. On the western extremity of the village is a ruined Jaina temple which itself appears to have been built out of materials partly taken from older Hindu temples, as sculptures representing the Dwarf and the Rama incarnations of Vishnu are seen in a wall and on a pillar, respectively.

73. Outside the village is a large step well known as *Ajwan Baodi* which bears in a niche a Sanskrit inscription recording its construction in V. S. 1577 (= A. C. 1520) in the reign of Mahmud Khilji of Malwa. Near this is another round well with a flight of steps reaching down to water.

74. **Mohanpur.**—About 6 miles to the north of Chanderi on the way to Budhi Chanderi is the village of Mohanpur. In this village is a comparatively modern but ruined temple of Nrisimha in which a few carved pillars and a door frame of mediæval temples probably brought from the ruins of Budhi Chanderi have been used. In the middle of the village is a small open enclosure in which some fragments of old Jain sculptures have been stored. Outside the village is a modern Jaina temple called Chaityalaya where an old image of a *Tirthankara* is enshrined.

75. **Budhi Chanderi.**—A fresh monument noticed at Budhi Chanderi is an inscribed Sati stone, dated in V. S. 1545 (= A. C. 1488) and giving the name of the place as Nasirabad, as Budhi Chanderi appears to have been named by the Muhammadan conquerors.

76. **Lakhari.**—Village of Lakhari is 5 miles north-west of Budhi Chanderi. It is surrounded on all sides by old relics.

77. On the west of the village are two small Saiva shrines standing in a row facing the east, on a common plinth and having a pillared porch in

front of each. The side walls of the shrine consist of single slabs. The door frame of one shrine is still standing and bears on its lintel the images of Brahma, Siva, Vishnu and *Navagrahas* and a Sanskrit inscription, dated V. S. 1000. The door frame of the other has fallen down and on the back of one of the loose door posts an image of Hanuman has been carved in relief in later times. Close to these shrines are two rectangular wells built of large blocks of stone which appear to be contemporary with the shrines. The bigger of the two wells measures 16' × 16'.

78. Nearly a furlong to the east of the village is an old temple locally known as *madh* facing the north. It consists of a shrine room 6' 3" × 7' 1" and a *Sabha Mandapa* 23' 6" × 16' 3" in front of it. Both the shrine room and the hall are covered with a flat roof supported on pillars and pilasters. The enshrined idol is rather unusual. It is a group of Brahma, Vishnu and Siva carved in relief on a stone slab. The central place is occupied by Siva flanked by Brahma on one side and Vishnu on the other. It may be that the slab originally formed the lintel of a door.

79. The temple appears to be seven or eight centuries old but has been repaired in later times.

80. About half way between this temple and the village is the site of an old Jaina temple of which the only remnants are two or three mutilated idols and a few architectural pieces.

81. A loose inscription slab, dated in V. S. 1124, was found in a well close by. This was removed to the Museum (see Appendix E. No. 22).

82. An isolated hill called Vindhya vasini *Tekri* to the north of the village is crowned with a modern rubble hut in which a small old idol of the goddess Mahishamardini is enshrined.

83. **Bithla.**—The village of Bithla lies about 5 miles to the south-west of Budhi Chanderi. Some two furlongs to the north-west of the village are a number of Jaina temples. Only one of these is standing at present, but there were at least four more. These latter are now fallen into heaps of ruins. The temple which is still standing faces roughly the west. It consists of a shrine room with a projecting entrance porch, the whole measuring externally 33' × 16'. The door frame is carved in the usual way. On the lintel are sculptured three *Tirthankaras* in a row the middle one being seated and the other two standing. In the back-ground are small figures of the *Navagrahas*. Over the lintel is a frieze in the centre of which is an image of a seated four-armed goddess probably Padmavati with a figure of a seated *Tirthankara* at either end. In the back-ground are small figures of standing *Tirthankaras*. Enshrined against the back wall of the cells is a big standing image of a *Tirthankara* whose head is half broken. There are five other small sculptures of *Tirthankaras* in the shrine room but the feet and pedestals of one and all having been buried in the debris their *lanchhanas* or distinctive symbols, if any, are not visible. It was not possible to expose these and identify the images, during my short visit. Part of the back-wall of the shrine and the *Sikhara* have fallen away. The exterior of the shrine shows the usual ribs and offsets but they are plain, *i. e.*, not decorated with sculpture.

84. In the ruins of the attendant temples referred to above are seen carved pillars, door jambs, lintels, roof-slabs and a number of damaged sculptures of *Tirthankaras* among which two could be identified as Sambhavanatha with the symbol of a horse and Munisuvrata with the *lanhhana* of a tortoise respectively.

85. Judging from the style the temples may be assigned to the 12th century approximately.

86. **Rakhetra or Gadhelna.**—Within the limits of the village Rakhetra about 2 miles to the south-east of Bithla, carved in the western face of a hill overlooking the Orr river is a series of rock-cut sculptures.

87. The biggest sculpture in the group is the seated image of the Jaina *Tirthankara* Adinatha popularly known as Bhaiyadant or Bhimasena. The height of the image is 10' 6" and the width at the seat is 7' 6." The head dress is somewhat uncommon for a Jaina sculpture being in the form of *Jata* or matted hair. The head is flanked on either side by an elephant which is unfinished. On the right side of the bust of the sculpture is an image of the goddess Padmavati and on the left is that of the goddess Chakresvari. On the seat which is in the form of a mattress is a small figure of a bull, the distinctive symbol of Adinatha. The seat also bears an inscription, dated in V. S. 1675. On the pedestal below the seat is carved a *Dharma-Chakra* or the wheel of the law between two scenes of a lion fighting with an elephant.

88. At the point where this sculpture is carved, the face of the hill is chiselled into a right angle. The sculpture of Adinatha described above is carved on one of the arms of the right angle which faces the south. On the other arm which faces the west, is carved a small niche crowned with a spire in outline enclosing a pair of foot-prints of Sri Visalaraja as is recorded in an inscription over the niche, dated in V. S. 1555. The back wall of the niche is decorated with lotuses carved in relief and a figure of *Svastika* is carved in the floor on either side of the foot-prints.

89. In front of these sculptures is a rough rubble platform. Adjoining the platform is a small plain doorway leading into a cavern which is a natural one, to all appearances. For want of time this cavern was left over for a search at some other time.

90. Proceeding southwards beyond the cavern along the facade of the hill we come to a small figure of seated Ganesa carved in the rock. At a distance of 5 feet further is a four-armed figure of Parvati seated on a couching lion. The head is crowned with *Jata* and has a lotus halo behind it. The ears carry large rings. Three of the hands hold a sword, a shield and a trident and the fourth is folded in the form of *Dharmachakramudra*.

91. Some 10 feet further south, in the same face of the hill, are three niches in a row each measuring 2' 2" × 1' 7½" approximately. The central niche contains a twelve-armed figure of Siva dancing, surrounded by his attendants Nandi and others. In the niche on the right of Siva is Brahma and in that on the left is Vishnu manifesting himself in the Boar incarnation.

92. On the other side of the big sculpture of Adinatha, *i. e.*, towards the north, one comes across two small niches carved in the rock containing unfinished groups of Hara-Gauri. Further on, there are traces of a similar

group. Still further north in the same facade, are two niches each sheltering a group of Siva and Parvati with their vehicles the bull and the lion under them. The top corners of both the niches are occupied by figures of Brahma and Vishnu. Over the principal images in one niche are two flying figures supporting a crown and in the other niche is a small group of dancing Siva and his attendants (*Tandava*). In the space between the two niches is a group of a god and goddess unfinished and a small but finished figure of Vishnu carved in the rock.

93. Further northwards is a tablet in the rock bearing a Sanskrit inscription in six lines dated in V. S. 999 and 1000 (see Appendix E., No. 32). Still further again are two niches each sheltering a group of Hara-Gauri and having a small structural porch in front of it.

94. A few carved pillars, brackets and pedestals are lying scattered on the ground in the neighbourhood attesting to the existence here of a structural shrine or shrines at one time.

95. The Hindu sculptures in this locality would appear to be contemporary with the inscription noted above, *i. e.*, of about the middle of the 10th century A. C. While the Jaina sculptures are more than five centuries later. The neighbouring hill-side has collapsed into a heap of debris which tempts one to surmise that there were perhaps some rock-cut caves in the locality.

96. The view of the collapsed hill-side with the river Orr flowing at its foot is strikingly similar to that of the excavated hill overlooking the Bagh river with this difference, however, that here is a dense and green jungle and an abundant stream of water while the landscape at Bagh is rather rugged.

VIII. Epigraphy.

97. Appendix No. E. shows an analysis of inscriptions noticed in the year of report and the numbers of inscriptions in this section refer to this Appendix.

98. Forty-eight inscriptions were copied or noticed during the year under report. Of these 28 are in Sanskrit or Hindi, 19 in Arabic or Persian and one in French. Classified according to the ruling dynasties two of these refer to early Hindu Kings, two to the Pathan kings of Delhi, seven to the Sultans of Malwa, six to the Mughal Emperors of Delhi, one to the Tomara Rajput dynasty of Gwalior and Narwar, one to the later Kachhwahas of Narwar, two to the Bundela kings of Chanderi and to the Scindias of Gwalior, while the rest mention no king. They were discovered variously at Budhi Chanderi, Chanderi, Khanpur, Lakhari, Rakhetra and Singhpur (in District Esaḡarh), Narwar Fort and town (District Narwar) and Ujjain city. Out of these Nos. 22 and 35 being loose slabs have been removed to the Museum and number 46 which came from the Mochiwada gate at Ujjain dismantled by the Town Improvement Trust is preserved in the Madhava College, Ujjain.

99. Among the Sanskrit inscriptions No. 32 is an important one. It is incised in the rock on the right bank of the river Orr within the limits of the village Rakhetra, not far from the old site of Chanderi. It is dated in V. S. 999 and again in V. S. 1000. It has not been satisfactorily interpreted so far but apparently it refers to the construction of some sort of water works connected with the Orr river perhaps at a cost of 95 or 96 crores of coins

by Vinayakapaladeva who was probably the same as his name-sake mentioned in the Chandela inscription at Khajuraho, dated V. S. 1011 (*Epi-graphia Indica*, Volume I, pp. 124 ff.). This place appears to have been included in the then Chandela kingdom. A king of Gopagiri (Gwalior) whose name however is not given is also mentioned. He was connected with these works in some way or other.

100. An inscription, dated in V. S. 1124, found at Lakhari mentions a Maharajadhiraja Abhayadeva and his son, prince Chandraditya but neither of these is known so far from other sources.

101. Two fragments of stone found at Ujjain appear to belong to a very large Sanskrit inscription of about the 10th to 11th centuries, extending over several hundreds of verses, written in the high flown *kavya* style. Unfortunately, however, the fragments discovered are too small to give us any idea of the purport of the inscription.

102. Of Musalman inscriptions No. 10 which is dated in A. H. 711 (= 1311 A. C.) is of importance, being the earliest Musalman inscription so far discovered at Chanderi. Allauddin Khilji invaded Chanderi in A. C. 1304 and the inscription under reference records the construction of a mosque here only seven years after this invasion.

IX. Numismatics.

103. One thousand four hundred and seven coins were examined in the year of report. Of these five were of gold, 101 of silver and 1,301 of copper. All these coins with the exception of 95 silver and 229 copper coins which were received from the State Museum as duplicates, came from treasure-trove finds. The gold coins were found at Sehora (District Esagarh) and the rest came from Dungarpur (District Narwar), and Shajapur (District Shajapur).

104. Out of these, all the five pieces of gold, 53 of silver and 63 of copper or, 121 coins in all, have been acquired for the Archaeological Museum.

105. Most important of these acquired coins are the five gold pieces, which belong to Chandragupta II of the Gupta dynasty (A.C. 375-413) and are of the type represented in the *Indian Museum Catalogue* plate XV, No. 12.

Of the silver coins 2 are of Shahjahan I (A. H. 1061) of Delhi mint, 10 belong to later Mughals up to Shah Alam II and range in date between A. H. 1207 and 1281, representing Benares and Bhuj mints.

106. The rest of the silver and some of the copper coins are from duplicates in the State Museum and have been acquired for our cabinet. Most of these belong to Scindia Rulers of Gwalior, European powers including Colonies and represent English, French, Italian, Portuguese, Austrian, and American (U. S. A.) currency. The copper coins belong to later Mughals or rather to Indian States who were subordinate to them including Orchha, Bhopal, Kota, Bundi, Jaipur and Dhar (*vide* Appendix No. F.).

X. Archaeological Museum.

107. Two stone inscriptions, one Sanskrit and the other Persian Nos. 22 and 35 of Appendix No. E, eight stone sculptures, nineteen old paintings, five gold, fifty-three silver and sixty-three copper coins and about eighty minor antiquities mostly brick carvings unearthed in the excavations at

Pawaya (old Padmavati) were added to the Museum in the year under report, and are detailed in Appendix No. C.

108. One sculpture in black (slate) stone representing Hara Gauri seated on their respective *vahanas* was purchased from outside the State. The rest were acquired from different parts of the State. All of them belong to the mediæval period. The most conspicuous among these are the huge sculptures of Siva slaying Gajasura, and his Sakti (Parvati) brought from Gyaraspur. The specimen of Matsya or Fish incarnation acquired in the year of report completes the series of the ten incarnations of Vishnu in our Museum.

109. All the nineteen miniature paintings were purchased locally. They represent the Mughal and Rajput Schools.

110. Among numismatic acquisitions, the five gold pieces of Chandragupta II are particularly noteworthy.

111. The Museum continues to be popular and attractive. 840 names have been signed in the Visitors' Book this year though the actual number of visitors must have been far greater. The number of European and American visitors exceeded 123. The addresses of Indian visitors represent all the provinces of British India and most Indian States. Among the distinguished visitors of the year may be mentioned Dr. Sten Konow, Dr. J. H. Cousins, Dr. A. K. Coomarswamy, Prof. Daruwala of Rajaram College, and Prof. A. Sen and historical party of Muzaffarpur (Behar) College.

XI. Visitors to Ancient Monuments.

112. The Buddhist rock-cut caves at Bagh (District Amjhera) are gradually emerging out of their obscurity and attracting more and more the attention of Indologists and sight-seers. With the publication of the monograph on these caves which is being carried through the press by the India Society of London in co-operation with this Department, the interest about this important group of caves is sure to be roused and it is expected that large numbers of visitors will hail not only from distant places in India but from all parts of the world, in spite of the fact that the caves are situated rather in an out-of-the-way place. But if we want to encourage travellers to visit these interesting relics of the past it is necessary that a branch road about three miles in length should be constructed to connect the caves with the Sardarpur-Kukshi Road and a small rest house be built close to the caves.

113. Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archæology in India, and Dr. J. H. Cousins, a well-known poet and art-critic, visited the caves in the year under report. The caves were also visited by a number of other visitors among whom about ten were Europeans who have recorded remarks of appreciations of what the Darbar have been doing to preserve and improve the condition of the caves. A few extracts from the remarks by the more distinguished visitors to these caves are quoted below :—

- (1) Remarks Sir John Marshall, the Director-General of Archæology in India : "India and all interested in Indian Art owe a deal of debt to His Highness the Maharaja for all that is being done for the preservation of these remains."

- (2) Writes Dr. J. H. Cousins: "This is one of the most important places in the history of Indian culture. Unfortunately time and human ignorance had gone too far in destruction before the Archaeological Department took in hand the preservation of the excavations. It is to be hoped that their labours (so wisely and enthusiastically guided by Mr. M. B. Garde) may result in the passing on to posterity of these priceless remnants of India's golden age in painting and architecture."
- (3) Says A. Abraham of Jobat, C.I.: "Most interesting. Just another confirmation of India's wonderful past, and inspiration to those who live in the present. It is said that these places have not been preserved although they are now being kept in at least a clean condition."

The Surwaya monuments also attracted a fair number of visitors both Indian and European from Shivpuri and Jhansi.

XII. Publication and Contribution.

114. (a) A resumé of the exploration and conservation work done in the State in Samvat 1980 (year 1923-24) was contributed to All-India Archaeological Survey Report.

(b) An illustrated article on Chanderi was contributed to the Birthday Special Number of the "Jayaji Pratap."

(c) An illustrated Guide to Chanderi is under preparation.

(d) In response to the demand of several non-English-knowing visitors to the Archaeological Museum who saw there the English Edition of the Gwalior Fort Album, a Hindi Edition of the book was published and made available for sale in the year under report.

(e) A monograph on the Buddhist Caves at Bagh and on their fresco paintings in particular is in the press. In order to ensure the best possible printing of the colour reproductions of the frescoes the printing has been entrusted to the India Society of London who are authorised to publish the volume as one of their series on behalf of the Darbar. Such distinguished *savants* as Sir John Marshall, Dr. J. Ph. Vogel, Mr. Lawrence Binyon, Mr. E. B. Havell and others are among the contributors to the volume.

XIII. Photography.

115. Two hundred and forty-nine photographic negatives and seventy-four lantern slides were prepared in the year under report (see Appendix No. H and I.).

XIV. Office Library.

116. One hundred and one volumes on Archaeology, Architecture, Art, History and allied subjects were added to the Office Library in the year under report (see Appendix No. J). Out of these sixty-eight were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and Governments of Indian States to whom our thanks are due.

XV. Income and Expenditure.

117. The Budget of the Department is the same as it has been for the last six years. Statements of income and expenditure under different heads are set forth in Appendices Nos. K and L from which it will be seen that the year's expenditure was Rs. 46,192 which includes part of the special grant for conservation and repairs of certain monuments on the Narwar Fort. The income is Rs. 177 only.

XVI. Concluding Remarks.

118. It is impossible to close the report without referring to the greatest and the saddest event in the modern history of Gwalior, namely, the untimely demise of our late lamented ruler Maharaja Sir Madhav Rao Scindia, which occurred about the close of the year under report. The versatile Maharaja had his personal impress on the work of every one of the Departments and it was under his personal command that this Department carried out repairs to certain monuments in the Narwar Fort in the year of report. His guiding mind and hand are, alas, no more! but it may be confidently hoped that the Department will continue to make slow but sure progress as in the past, under the fostering care of the new Council of Regency constituted as it is of the same wise and experienced Councillors of the late Maharaja.

119. In conclusion I cannot but express my gratitude to Shrimant Sadashiv Rao Khase Sahib Pawar, the Home Member, for the unfailing courtesy and valuable guidance which he continued to extend to me in the discharge of the duties of my office.

M. B. GARDE,
Superintendent of Archæology,
Gwalior State.

APPENDIX NO. A.

**Tour Diary of the Superintendent of Archaeology, Gwalior
State, for Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.**

Date, Month and year.	Movements and Halts.
July 1924.	
26th-27th ...	Gwalior to Udaygiri <i>via</i> , Bhilsa.
28th-29th ...	Halt at Udaygiri.
30th ...	Udaygiri to Bhilsa.
31st ...	Bhilsa to Gwalior.
September 1924.	
14th ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
15th-17th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
18th ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
22nd ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
23rd-24th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
25th ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
November 1924.	
9th ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
10th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
11th ...	Shivpuri to Narwar, Magroni and back to Shivpuri.
12th-14th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
15th ...	Shivpuri to Surwaya.
16th ...	Surwaya to Shivpuri.
17th ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
December 1924.	
9th ...	Gwalior to Lalitpur.
10th ...	Lalitpur to Chanderi.
11th-16th ...	Halt at Chanderi.
17th ...	Chanderi to Naderi, Gurila-ka-Pahad, and back.
18th ...	Chanderi to Mohanpura.
19th ...	Mohanpura to Lidhora.
20th-21st ...	Halt at Lidhora.
22nd ...	Lidhora to Chanderi.
23rd-24th ...	Halt at Chanderi.
25th ...	Chanderi to Lalitpur.
26th ...	Lalitpur to Gwalior.
31st ...	Gwalior to Mhow.
January 1925.	
1st ...	Mhow to Bagh.
2nd ...	Halt at Bagh.
3rd-4th ...	Bagh to Bhilsa <i>via</i> , Mhow.
4th ...	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.
5th ...	Bhilsa to Kulhar, Badoh and back to Kulhar
6th ...	Kulhar to Gwalior.
20th-21st ...	Gwalior to Mhow.
22nd ...	Halt at Mhow.
23rd-24th ...	Mhow to Gwalior.
February 1925.	
7th ...	Gwalior to Narwar Fort <i>via</i> , Satanwada.
8th ...	Halt at Narwar Fort.
9th ...	Narwar Fort to Gwalior <i>via</i> , Satanwada.
18th ...	Gwalior to Dabra.
19th ...	Dabra to Pawaya.
20th-27th ...	Halt at Pawaya for excavations.

Date, Month and year.	Movements and Halts.
28th ...	Pawaya to Dabra and thence to Gwalior.
March 1925.	
8th ...	Gwalior to Pawaya <i>via</i> . Dabra.
9th-13th ...	Halt at Pawaya.
14th ...	Pawaya to Gwalior <i>via</i> ., Dabra.
18th ...	Gwalior to Narwar <i>via</i> . Satanwada.
19th-21st ...	Halt at Narwar Fort.
22nd ...	Narwar to Gwalior <i>via</i> . Satanwada.
31st ...	Gwalior to Bhilsa.
April 1925	
1st ...	Halt at Bhilsa.
2nd-3rd ...	Bhilsa to Mhow.
3rd ...	Mhow to Bagh.
4th ...	Bagh to Bagh Caves.
5th-8th ...	Halt at Bagh Caves.
9th ...	Bagh to Tanda.
10th ...	Tanda to Sardarpur.
11th ...	Sardarpur to Mhow.
11th-12th ...	Mhow to Mandasor.
12th ...	Mandasor to Sondni and back.
13th-14th ...	Halt at Mandasor.
15th ...	Mandasor to Ujjain.
16th ...	Ujjain to Astronomical Observatory and back.
17th ...	Ujjain to Kaliadeh and back.
18th ...	Ujjain to Bhairongarh and back.
do. ...	Ujjain to Mungaoli <i>via</i> . Bina.
19th ...	Mungaoli to Chanderi.
20th-21st ...	Chanderi to Gwalior <i>via</i> . Mungaoli.
27th ...	Gwalior to Dabra.
28th ...	Dabra to Pawaya.
29th ...	Halt at Pawaya.
30th ...	Pawaya to Dabra.
May 1925.	
1st ...	Dabra to Gwalior.
6th ...	Gwalior to Narwar <i>via</i> . Satanwada.
7th-8th ...	Halt at Narwar.
9th ...	Narwar to Gwalior <i>via</i> . Satanwada.
11th ...	Gwalior to Dabra.
12th ...	Dabra to Pawaya.
13th-14th ...	Halt at Pawaya.
15th ...	Pawaya to Gwalior <i>via</i> . Dabra.
28th ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
29th-30th ...	Halt at Shivpuri.
31st ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.
June 1925.	
20th ...	Gwalior to Narwar <i>via</i> . Satanwada.
21st-22nd ...	Halt at Narwar.
23rd ...	Narwar to Gwalior <i>via</i> . Satanwada.

Statement of expenditure incurred on monuments conserved during Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

Serial No.	Place.	Name of monument.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.		Total.	AMOUNT SPENT.		Total.	REMARKS.									
			Current year.	Last year.		Current year.	Last year.											
			Rs.	Rs. a. p.		Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.											
1	Chanderi	Katighati	825	...	825	0	0	739	15	0								
2	"	Delhi Gate	17	...	17	0	0	16	8	0								
3	"	Madarsa	144	...	144	0	0	136	5	0								
4	Sondni	Yasodharman's Pillars.	2,584	...	2,584	0	0	24	0	0								
5	Ranod	Khokhai	51	40	91	0	0	50	6	0								
6	Budhi Chanderi,	Jam Temple	16	...	16	0	0	15	8	6								
7	Bagh	Buddhist Caves	2,656	4	0	9	2,099	5	6	6								
8	Chanderi	Minor Monuments	441	...	441	0	0	428	7	6								
9	Mandasour	Gupta Image	698	...	698	0	0	28	0	0								
10	Bagh	Copying Frescoes	...	344	0	7	337	4	6							
11	Udaypur	Udayesvar Temple	2,228	...	2,228	0	0	...	2,074	5	0							
12	Budoh	Jaina Temple	...	34	5	6	25	0	0							
13	"	Solah Khaumbhi	...	19	6	6	8	0	0							
14	"	Gadarnal Temple	...	75	6	6	62	8	0							
15	Bhilsa	Gumbaz-ka-Maqbara.	...	6	0	0	6	0	0							
16	"	Bijamandal Mosque.	...	5	7	6	5	7	6							
17	Ujain	Observatory	...	7,000	0	0	6,568	10	0							
18	Narwar	Fort Narwar	30,732	...	30,732	0	0	16,824	13	6	Special grant.							
19	"	Minor Monuments	142	...	142	0	0	39	10	3								
	TOTAL	...	38,206	9,756	48,062	48,062	11	4	20,402	15	3	9,131	1	9	29,5	4	1	0

APPENDIX No. C.

LIST OF SELECTED ANTIQUITIES UNEARTHED IN
EXCAVATIONS AT PAWAYA DURING SAMVAT 1981.

Stone finds.

1. Piece of a big lintel of gateway. Length $6' 5\frac{1}{2}''$ × height $2' 2''$ × thickness at ends $2' 2''$ and at middle $1' 6''$. Two faces and underside carved into sculptures. The top side has rectangular socket holes which held sculptures or ornamental pieces. Three whole and parts of two socket holes exist in the present piece. This piece appears to be almost a half of the original. Beginning from the end the measurements of the holes are (1) length broken × breadth $9\frac{1}{4}''$ × depth $3\frac{1}{4}''$ (2) length $1' 5''$ × breadth $11''$ × depth $1\frac{1}{2}''$ (3) length $6''$ × breadth $4\frac{3}{4}''$ × depth $3''$ (4) length $6\frac{3}{4}''$ × breadth $5''$ × depth $3\frac{1}{4}''$ (5) length $4\frac{1}{2}''$ × breadth $4\frac{1}{2}''$ × depth $3\frac{1}{2}''$.

One of the faces has the following sculptures (1): A dance scene (2) Bali's sacrifice (3) Trivikrama Vishnu.

The other face has (1) Scene of the churning of the Ocean (2) Karttikeya (?)

2. Torso of a female.

Ht. $1' 8''$ × br. $13\frac{1}{2}''$ × thickness $1'$. Existing portion shows waist and thighs. A close fitting *lahanga* and a jewelled girdle with a buckle in the form of two crocodile heads are worn. The figure is in the round.

3. Lower part of a pot bellied figure (Kubera ?) sitting cross-legged on a pedestal. One leg only preserved. A scarf is tied round belly with a knot in front. Breadth $2' 2\frac{1}{2}''$ × height $2' 1''$ × thickness $16''$.

4. A Triratna or Trisula (?)

Ht. $2' 3''$ × br. $2' 1\frac{1}{2}''$ × thickness $7\frac{1}{2}''$, tenon $4''$ × $4\frac{1}{2}''$ × $5''$. Top damaged. The two side limbs are finished in the form of foliage. A tenon at bottom to show that it was fixed on something probably on the lintel of some gateway.

5. End of a lintel (?)

A socket or tenon at end. Both faces carved. Section oval. Each face shows a female's hand holding a twig of mango tree, surely fragment of a woman under tree which was a common *motif* of a bracket of a gateway. Height $1' 8''$ × breadth $1' 6''$ × thickness $1' 4''$, tenon $7''$ × $5''$ × $4\frac{1}{4}''$.

6. Piece of a lion conventionally carved. Length $2' 3\frac{1}{2}''$ × breadth $9''$ × height $1' 2''$.

7. A water spout in the form of a crocodile's head *in situ* in the eastern face of the brick platform.

8. Several small pieces of stone sculptures.

9. Dwarf bracket lying on top of mound.

Height $1' 7''$ × breadth $1' 5''$ × thickness $1' 8''$ bottom broken. Busts of *Kichakas* or dwarfs with upraised hands on three sides. Fourth side undressed. Faces and hands of dwarfs damaged. They wear jewelled necklaces round their necks (Gupta style), knot of a scarf is seen on the front of one of the dwarfs.

10. Sculpture of a female with a waist cloth No. 2. ...
 11. Sculpture of a torso with hand No. 4,
 12. A sculpture (piece) showing lion and snake No. 14,
 13. A sculpture No. 53
 14. A sculpture (conch) No. 71
 15. A sculpture No. 89
 16. A sculpture (head) No. 171

Terra Cotta.

17. Head of male with open mouth No. 6
 18. Head of male with beard and hair No. 7
 19. Head of male with locks of hair No. 8
 20. A piece of moulded corner brick No. 11
 21. A torso No 17
 22. A piece of a moulded brick No. 18
 23. A piece of round moulded brick No. 24
 24. A sculpture with broken feet No. 31... ..
 25. A sculpture of Varaha (man) No. 32
 26. A sculpture of elephant No. 34
 27. A head with beard No. 37
 28. A head with an ear ornament No. 43
 29. A bird without head No. 44
 30. A round moulded brick No. 47
 31. A neck with ornaments No. 48
 32. A man pierced with an arrow No. 58... ..
 33. A piece No. 59
 34. A bird No. 67
 35. A moulded brick No. 69... ..
 36. A head No. 76
 37. „ „ 80
 38. „ „ 82
 39. „ „ 84
 40. „ „ 83
 41. A torso „ 85
 42. A hand „ 87
 43. Pieces No. 88
 44. A conch piece No. 90
 45. A head No. 91
 46. A piece of pottery No. 95
 47. A piece of iron flat bar No. 96
 48. An iron nail No. 99
 49. A torso on horse back No. 100
 50. A moulded brick No. 102
 51. „ „ „ 104
 52. A torso kneeling No. 105
 53. A moulded brick No. 111
 54. A head with ear ornament No. 112
 55. A long foot No. 114

56.	A piece No 115
57.	A brick with leaf mouldings No, 116			...
58.	A torso with a piece of arms and spear No. 117			...
59.	A piece of moulded corner brick No. 118			...
60.	A finely moulded piece No. 120
61.	A laughing face No. 121	
62.	A moulded brick No. 122	
63.	„ „ with lead mould No. 123			...
64.	A piece of carving No. 124
65.	A moulded brick No. 125	
66.	A finely moulded brick No. 127
67.	„ „ „ „ 130
68.	A torso No. 131
69.	„ „ 132
70.	A head of parrot No. 135	
71.	A head with open mouth No. 136
72.	A torso with holy thread No. 137
73.	A piece of moulded brick No. 139
74.	A torso No. 141
75.	A piece with ornament No. 142
76.	A moulded brick No. 143	
77.	„ „ „ 144	
78.	„ „ „ 146	
79.	A hand with ornament No. 149
80.	Head of a female No. 153
81.	Head of a fish No. 157
82.	A moulded brick No. 164
83.	A head with hair plated No. 172
84.	A moulded brick No. 173

APPENDIX No. D.

Monuments listed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	Ownership.
District Esagarh.				
1	Chanderi.	Mehman sarai or guest house and its gateways. ...	II	Government.
2	"	Bandar Baodi or monkey well ...	III	
3	"	Qazi-ka-Beg-ki-masjid (mosque) with inscription and baodi (square) ...	III	
4	"	Maqbara close to above ...	II	Government.
5	"	Chandai Baodi ...	II	
6	"	Visurkund (Vishnukund ?) ...	III	Local Chaudhari & Jaina community.
7	"	Hatpure-ki-masjid with inscription ...	III	
8	"	Jaina temple called chaubisi ...	II	
9	"	Domed shrine of Siva with inscription ...	III	
10	"	Mirza-ki-masjid with inscription.	III	
11	"	Smaller Jaina temple with two old images ...	II	
12	"	Chetan Baodi ...	III	
12a	"	Tomb of a Christian soldier near Harakund ...	III	
12b	"	Tomb of a Christian soldier near Chaudhari's house ...	III	
13	Singhpur.	Raja's mahals ...	III	Government.
14	Khanpura.	Sati stones with inscriptions ...	III	
15	Gurilakapahad.	Two Jaina temples...	III	"
16	Naderi.	Sati stones with inscriptions ...	III	"
17	"	Ajwan Baodi with inscription ..	III	"
18	"	A ruined Jaina temple ...	III	"
19	Mohanpur.	Fragments of Jaina sculptures in an enclosure ...	III	Government.
20	"	Nrisimha temple in village in which some old pillars and door frames are built ...	III	
21	"	Jaina Chaityalaya outside village.	III	
22	Budhi-Chanderi.	Sati stone with inscription ...	III	
23	Lakhari.	Two Saiva shrines one with an inscription ...	III	
24	"	An old well close by ...	III	
25	"	Another square baodi (old) ...	III	
26	"	An old temple known as Madha.	III	
27	"	Ruins of a Jaina temple ...	III	
28	Bithla.	Jaina temple ..	II	
29	"	Ruins of three other Jaina temples.	III	
30	Rakhetra or Gadhelna.	A large rock-cut Jaina image known as Bhiyadant or Bhimasena with inscriptions ...	I	Government.
31	"	A number of rock-cut Hindu sculptures and an inscription...	I	
32	"	A natural cavern and fragments of Hindu sculptures ...	III	

APPENDIX No. E.

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No. of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	B u d h i - Chanderi	Pedestal of an image of Hanuman.	4	Nagari.	District Hindi.	Esagarh. V. S. 1795 = A. C. 1738.	Durjan Singh Deva, Bundela of Chanderi.	Records the installation of the idol (?).	
2	"	A wall of a Jaina temple ...	7	"	"	"	"	"	Illegible.
3	"	A Sati stone flanking the passage to river on west.	15	"	Hindi.	V. S. 1545 Jyeshtha Vadi 5 Saturday.	Rajadhiraja Gayasuddin of Mandu.	Records Sati of (name illegible) at Nasirabad (as Budhi Chanderi was renamed by the Muhammadans). The post was erected by Ratana son of the deceased.	
4	Chanderi.	The central niche of Mirzon-ki-masjid.	5	Corrupt Nastaliq.	Persian.	"	"	"	Partly damaged.
5	"	A slab in the wall of a house on the Fort Road.	5	"	"	15th Rabi- ul-sani A.H.1051 = A. C. 1641.	Shahjahan I Mughal Em- peror of Delhi.	"	"
6	"	The lintel of door frame of a tomb in the N. E. corner of the grave yard of Nizam u-d-din's family.	3	Naskh.	"	A. H. 828 = A. C. 1424	Hoshang Shah of Malwa.	Records that the tomb was built during the reign of Hoshang Shah and gives the name of a saint of the time who is obviously inmate of the tomb.	

8	Chanderi.	A Christian tomb	...	4	Nastaliq.	Persian.	A. H. 1232 = A. C. 1816	Nil.	Records the death of one Yunis on 16 Jamadi-ul-sau A. H. 1232 and that the tomb was erected by the Colonel's order.
	"	A lintel of the mosque near Mardan smith's house in bazar.		4	Naskh.	"	A. H. 795 = A. C. 1392.	Mubammad Shah s/o. Firozshah of Delhi.	Consists of 8 verses arranged in 4 lines and records that the mosque was erected during the reign of Mubammad Shah s/o. Firozshah in A. H. 795. It describes Dilawar Khan as a favourite courtier. The name of the builder though given is not clear.
9	"	A pillar of the left hand porch of the same mosque.		6	Nastaliq.	"	Illegible.
10	"	A room in the house of a Brahman named Ram Bharose.		4	Suls.	"	A. H. 711 = A. C. 1311	Ala-ud-din Mubammad Khilji of Delhi.	Records the construction of a mosque by Ismail s/o. Abdulla during the reign of Mubammad Shah in A. H. 711.
11	"	A well known as Chandai Baodi.		12	Naskh.	Persian.	...	Mubammad Sultan of Mandu.	Worn out and illegible.
12	"	"		20	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	...	"	The lower portion worn out and illegible.

APPENDX No. E

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.—(contd).

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No. of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	Purport.	REMARKS.
13	Chanderi.	The central niche of Shekhan-ki-masjid. Piece No. 1	3	Nastaliq.	Arabic.	Holy text.	
		" 2	3	" "	"	Records that Hamid-ud-din s/o Shekh Firoz-ud-din descendant of Shekh Suleman built the mosque and the tomb in his life time during the reign of Aurangzeb the conqueror in A. H. 1094.	
		" 3	4	"	Persian	A. H. 1094 A. C. = 1682	Aurangzeb		
14	"	The arch of door frame of a tomb in the graveyard of Shekhas.	1	"	"	A. H. 1064 A. C. = 1653	Not legible.
15	"	The central niche of Kazi-ki-masjid in Kazi-ka-bagh. Piece No. 1	4	"	"	
		...	4	"	"	A. H. 1113 A. C. = 1701	Durjan Singh, Bundela of Chanderi.	Records that Raja Durjan Singh owner of the estate bestowed this garden. And that through God's grace the mosque and well reached completion during the reign of Alamgir. Further records that Abda s/o Suleman built a tomb near	

16	" ३	4	"	"	"	Regnal year 45 of Alamgir.	Aurangzeb of Delhi.	...	Not yet deciphered.
17	"	8	Naskh.	"	Persian,	Not yet deciphered.
17	A niche in Kazini Baodi...	6	Nastaliq.	"	"	A. H. 1102 = A.C.1690	Aurangzeb.	Records that a well, mosque and a garden were completed by Azam Khan during the reign of Aurangzeb A. H. 1102. Regnal year 35.	Not yet deciphered.
18	"	6	Roman.	French ?	"	1819 A. C	Not legible
19	"	7	Nagari.	"	"	V. S. 1743 = A.C.1686	Not legible
20	"	23	"	Sanskrit.	"	Monday Magha Sudi 8 V.S.1724 = A. C. 1667.	...	A Prasasti recording the installation of a Siva Ling known as Manasimhesvara by Sri Manasimha s/o Sri Kusivara Chakravarti Vikramaditya, while he was Yivaraja, Composed by Giridhara Jyo- tirvid devotee of Jagesvari and engraved by Devitaksi.	Not legible
21	Khanpur.	9	"	"	"	V. S. 1545 (4)	Illegible.
22	Lakhari.	6	"	Incorvet Sanskrit.	"	V. S 1124 = A.C.1067	Sri Abhayadeva (?)	The purport is not clear. Mentions king Abhayadeva (?) Prince Chandraditya and Jalhnade [vi] (?).	Writing is mostly illegible.

APPENDIX 'No. E.
Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.—(contd).

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No. of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	Purport.	REMARKS.
23	Lakhari.	The lintel of a door frame of a ruined temple.	2	Nagari.	Incorrect Sanskrit.	V. S. 1000[?]	Not clear.	Apparently a pilgrim's record. Records 3 names Sri Gabhin Thakur, Sri Yavakasya Devn and his mother Chhita (Sita ?)	The date is recorded but in a very confused manner. The wording is <i>Sannat sara sat esha 100, 10 salasre-sha</i> Literally it means ten thousand years. What the writer probably meant to express was Samvat 1000. Sayvat Abm Shah reigned at Delhi from 1443 to 1451 A. C. He was perhaps the Governor at Chanderi at the time of our inscription. In the date the figures showing the century are not expressed; from the style of letters the record is not less than 5 or 6 centuries
24	Naderi.	Sati stone near a well known as Dhimra.	6	"	Sanskrit.	Thursday Jyeshtha vadi 14 V. S. 1485 Saka 1350 = A. C. 1428.	Sahi Alim (Sayyed of Dehli.)	Records the Sati of a Lumar (black-smith) at village Gular from which the neighbouring hill probably takes its name Gurli-ka-Pahad.	
25	"	Another Sati on a platform in village.	4	"	"	V. S. 0066	...	A Sati record.	

27	Rakhetra (Bhiyadant)	Pedestal of a big rock cut Jaina sculpture of Adinatha	1	"	...	Khilji of Malwa or per- haps his son,	bsodi by (names illegible; genealogy of donor given).	mostly illegible.
28	"	A tablet above foot- prints in rock near the big Jaina sculpture.	5	"	Friday Phalguna Sudi 2 V.S. 1555 = A.C. 1498	Sultan Gyaas- ud-din,	Pilgrim's record, Records the making of the foot-prints of Sri Visala Raj pupil of Upadhyaya Manika Sundara pupil of Upadhyaya Malaya Chanda Suri by Muniraja.	Illegible.
29	"	The seat of a big Jaina image of Adinatha. See No. 27 above.	2	"	Saturday Ashadha vadi 8 V.S. 1675 = A.C. 1618	...	Pilgrim's record. Mentions Chanderi and Bithla which is the same as the present Vithala Village.	Illegible.
30	"	Rock	1	"	Pilgrim's record.	"
31	"	"	1	"	"	"
32	"	A tablet in rock	5	"	Sanskrit. Asvina vadi 30 V. S. 999 = A.C. 942 Bhadrapada sudi 3 V.S. 1000 and Kartika V. S. 1000 = A. C. 943	Not clear.	The parent is not quite clear. Apparently records the con- struction of some water or irrigation work in connection with the Orr river by Sri Vinayaka Pala Deva whose identity is uncertain. He may perhaps be the prince of the same name as men- tioned at the end of the Khajuraho stone inscription of Samvat 1011 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> Vol. I. P. 124.	

APPENDIX No. E.

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.—(contd).

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No. of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	Purpose.	REMARKS.
33	Singhpur a hamlet near Ram- nagar Mahal.	A baodi known as Raja- mati.	36	Nagari.	Sanskrit and Prakrit.	Thursday Magha sudi 5 V. S. 1525 = A. C. 1468	Gayas-ud-din Sultan of Mandu.	Mentions a Sri Gopagindva i. e., king of Gwalior whose name however is not recorded. Records an amount namely 95 crores in figures and 96 crores in words, but of what coin is not clear. Perhaps it refers to the amount spent on the works. The Prasasti was written by Bhaladaman son of Sri Krisnaraja.	
34	"	A Sati near Chanderi, on Mungoli-Chanderi Road.	18	"	Sanskrit.	V. S. 1682 = A. C. 1625	...	Records the construction of a well.	A Sati record of a Srivastava Kayaatha lady whose name is illegible.
35	Singhpur (this is an- other village 2 m. north- east of Chanderi.)	A loose slab dug out of the tank in front of Singhpur Mahal.	11	Naskh.	Persian.	A. H. 836 = A. C. 1432	Hoshang Shah of Mandu.	Records that the tank was completed on 10th Sha'val A. H. 836 during the reign of Hoshang Shah.	

36	Bara.	A sati pillar...	6	Nagari.	Incorrect Sanskrit.	Jyeshtha vadi 15 V. S. 1539 = A.C.1482 Wednesday Bhadrapada vadi 9 V. S. 1856 Saka 1751 = A.C.1799	Illegible.
37	Narwar Town.	The shaft of Ek-khambi chhatri in bazar.	11	"	...	Daulat Rao Scindia.	...	Records that a Chhatri (शशि) on one pillar was made during the reign of Daulat Rao Scindia when Ambaji Ingle was Governor and when Viswas Rao was Desha-mukha.	
38	Narwar Fort.	A pillar of a baradari near Kotora tank.	7	"	...	Maharaja Ramasinha (Kachha abha).	...	Records the construction of a Baradari Maharaja Ram Simha (Kachhawa).	
39	"	The western retaining wall of Makaradhvaj tank.	9	Nagari.	...	Maharaj Birmaada.	...	Records the construction of a Chabutara or platform.	Mostly illegible.
40	"	A sati on bank of Makaradhvaj tank.	5	"	Mentions name of the mason who made the pillar (?).	"
41	"	The pedestal of Garuda image in a Chhatri on the N. E. bank of Makaradhvaj tank.	9	"	Illegible.
42	"	The pedestal of the image of Hanuman in above chhatri.	15	"	"
43	"	In a mosque on the way to Urwah gate from Makaradhvaj tank.	5	Naskh.	Arabic and Persian.	A. IL 902 = A.C.1554	...	The first two lines are Arabic quotations from the holy texts. The next three lines contain 5 verses in Persian which record the construction of mosque by order of Shamsheer Khan (a Governor (?) of Narwar) in A. H. 962.	"

APPENDIX No. E.

Inscriptions copied or noticed in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25--(contd).

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	No of lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	Name of ruling king.	Purpose.	REMARKS.
44	Narwar Fort.	A loose slab found in the yard of Durgah of Madar Shah.	10	Naskh and Nastaliq.	Arabic and Persian.	A. H. 960 = A.C.1552	Muhammad Adil (of Suri Dynasty of Delhi) and Dilawar Khan as his assistant (i. e., Governor).	The inscription consists of 10 lines, 6 of which are in Naskh characters and Arabic language and are quotations from holy texts. The remaining 4 are in Nastaliq and Persian and record the construction of mosque by order of Dilawar Khan during the reign of Muhammad Adil. (I.A. Vol. L VII P. 101).	
45	"	Over the mihrabs of prayer hall in a mosque near Hava Pour.	Not copied yet.
		Central mihrab	4	Naskh.	Arabic.	Quotation from holy texts,	
		" (below the above)...	4	"	Persian.	900 A. H. = A.C.1494	...	Bears date and some name not deciphered yet.	
		North mihrab	4	"	Arabic.	Quotation from holy texts.	
		South mihrab	4	"	"		

APPENDIX No. F.

List of coins examined during Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Name of king and dynasty.	Metal.	No. of coins examined.	Remarks.
Gupta Dynasty.				
1	Chandragupta II	Gold	5	
Sultans of Jaunpur.				
2	Muhammad Shah	Copper	13	
Mughal Emperors of Delhi.				
3	Shahjahan I	Silver	2	
4	Shah Alam II	"	15	
5	Muhammad Akbar III	"	1	
Miscellaneous.				
6	Modern coins of Europe including Portugal, Austria, France, U. S. A., and colonies.			
7	" " " "	Silver	12	
8	Scindias of Gwalior, from Mahadaji to Madhav Rao	Copper	28	
9	Jiwaji Rao Scindia	Silver	27	
10	Bhopal State	Copper	697	
11	Hyderabad State	"	66	
12	Dhar State	"	1	
13	Indore "	"	1	
14	Bharatpur State	"	1	
15	Tonk "	"	2	
16	Kotah "	"	2	
17	Bundi "	"	1	
18	Jaipur "	"	1	
19	Orcha "	"	4	
20	Damaged and undecipherable	Silver	44	
21	" "	Copper	483	
		Total ...	1,407	only.

APPENDIX NO. G.

List of antiquities added to Archaeological Museum in
Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Remark.
		Old Paintings.	
1		A Muhamadan king seated on throne under <i>chhatra</i> (supposed to be Aurangzeb).	
2		Maharaja Amarsingh standing.	
3		A princess going to meet her expected lover in her garden house, with maids etc.	
4		Lord Krishna playing on his flute.	
5		A fairy leading a tiger driven by a bull-headed demon.	
6		A river side scene with a water bird pounced upon by a hawk.	
7		A seated noble.	
8		Two nobles with attendants seated (upper panel), naked boys (?) playing (middle panel), three ladies (lower panel).	
9		River goddess Ganga mounted on crocodile.	
10		A lady worshipping a tree followed by her maid-servant.	
11		A noble man in arms on horse back with attendants.	
12		Lakshmi Narayana.	
13		A seated noble.	
14		Ganesa and Parvati.	
15		Ganesa seated on a throne with Sarasvati on a swan.	
16		A Nawab of Jhajhar driving in a four wheeled carriage followed by mounted body-guards.	
17		Fortress of Gwalior (water colour painting by General Popham, A. D. 1780.)	Printed.
18		Fortress of Gwalior in water colour, south side view published 1787.	
19		" Wood carving.	
20		A piece of carved bamboo, size, 10" x 4 $\frac{3}{4}$ "	
		Stone sculptures.	
21		A black stone sculpture of Siva and Parvati size 8 $\frac{3}{4}$ " x 6 $\frac{1}{2}$ " x 2".	
22	Gyaraspur.	Parvati standing.	
23	"	Siva killing demon Gaja.	
24	"	Fish incarnation of Vishnu.	
25	Bhilsa.	Jaina <i>Tirthamkara</i> .	
26	Gurilakapahad.	Bhairava.	
27	Jharna.	A Trisula.	
		Inscriptions.	
28	Lakhari.	A Sanskrit inscription dated V. S. 1124	
29	Singhpur.	A Persian inscription dated A. H. 828. ...	
		Coins.	
30-150		Gold, Silver and Copper.	

APPENDIX No. H.

List of photographs taken in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh.	Caves,	general view from north ...	Full.
2	"	Cave No. 2	" " " "	"
3	"	" "	another " " "	"
4	"	" "	view of verandah pillars ...	"
5	"	" "	front view of verandah ...	"
6	"	" "	interior view, central ...	"
7	"	" "	" cross view showing pillars ...	"
8	"	" "	right hand row of pillars in interior ...	"
9	"	" "	Dagoba and Bodhisattvas flanking door of chapel...	"
10	"	" "	group of sculptures of Buddha and attendants on the right side wall of antechamber ...	"
11	"	" "	" " left side "	"
12	"	" 4	view of facade from north- west ...	"
13	"	" "	principal doorframe ...	"
14	"	" "	interior view showing a frieze ...	"
15	"	" "	interior " " pillar...	"
16	"	" "	" " " bracket.	Half.
17	"	" "	newly discovered fresco painting ...	"
18	"	" "	part of newly " "	"
19	"	" "	sculpture of a Naga king and queen ...	Full.
20	"	" "	chapel of Nagas ...	"
21	"	" "	sculpture of Kubera (P) ...	"
22	"	" 4 & 5	general view from north.	"
23	"	" 5	facade from north east...	"
24	"	" "	interior view, general ...	"
25	"	" "	" showing pillars ...	"
District Bhilsa.				
26	Badoh.	Gudarmal temple	general view from north- west.	"
27	"	" "	" " " east.	"
28	"	" "	near view from north ...	"
29	"	" "	near view from north- east ...	"
30	"	" "	porch from north-west ...	"
31	"	" "	basement from north- east ...	Full.
32	"	Jaina temple,	general view from north- west ...	"

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS.
33	Badoh.	Solah khambi, general view from south-west	Full.	
34	Besnagar.	Khamb-baba, general view from south-west	"	
35	Udaygiri.	Cave No. 5, sculpture of Varaha (Boar incarnation)	"	
36	"	Cave No. 5, Sculpture of the goddess of Earth being lifted up by Boar ...	Half.	
37	"	Cave No. 6, door frame ...	Full.	
38	"	" image of Vishnu ...	Half.	
39	"	" another image of Vishnu ...	"	
40	"	" image of Mahishasuramardini ...	"	
41	Udaypur.	Udayesvar temple after repairs, view from south east ...	Full.	
42	"	" " back view ...	"	
43	"	" " vedi after repairs ...	"	
District Esagarh.				
44	Rakhetra.	Rock-cut sculpture of a Jaina Tirthamkara locally known as Bhimasena or Bhiyadant	Half.	
45	"	Rock-cut group of Brahma, Vishnu (Varaha) and Mahesa.	"	
46	"	" " of a Siva and Parvati in a niche... ..	"	
47	Bithla.	Jaina temple, general view from south-west	Full.	
48	Budhi Chanderi	Group of Jaina temples, general view from south west ...	"	
49	"	" " a door frame ...	Half.	
50	"	Jaina sculptures in ruins	Full.	
51	"	" " arranged in the courtyard of a temple.	"	
52	"	" " " " " " " "	"	
53	"	" " big image of Santinatha in the interior of a temple ...	"	
54	"	" " attendants of Santinatha ...	Half.	
55	Chanderi.	Town, bird's eye view from Fort ...	Full.	
56	"	" another view from top of a house.	Half.	
57	"	Fort, general view (near) from west.	Full.	
58	"	" " " (distant) " " "	"	
59	"	" " " from Dhobi Talao...	"	
60	"	" Rest house from south-west ...	"	
61	"	" Rajaka mahal from south-west ...	"	
62	"	" " " " " " " "	Half.	
63	"	" Mosque, carved niches in interior...	Full.	
64	"	Madarsa, before repairs, general view from south east ...	Full.	
65	"	" after " " " " south east ...	"	
66	"	" after repairs, another view ...	"	
67	"	Shahzadika Roza, before repairs, general view south-east ...	"	
68	"	" after " " " "	"	
69	"	" " interior view ...	"	

Nr.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS.
70	Chanderi	Delhi gate, view of north ...	Full.	
71	"	" " inscription ...	Half.	
72	"	Tombs of Nizamuddin's family, a door frame.	Full.	
73	"	" " " part of a door frame.	"	
74	"	" " " a carved niche.	"	
75	"	" " " carving work on a wall.	Half.	
76	"	Jhinjharia Pir, interior view ...	Full.	
77	"	Parmesvari tal, view from East ...	"	
78	"	A carved tomb stone ...	"	
79	"	" " " another view ...	"	
80	"	A lamp post in a tomb ...	Half.	
81	"	Panchmadhi, general view from north-east ...	Full.	
82	"	Mehmansarai, east gate ...	"	
83	"	" north gate ...	"	
84	"	Textile Institute, view of machinery ...	"	
85	"	Gate way near Chandhari's house, from north-east ...	"	
86	"	Chandai baodi, a corner view ...	"	
87	"	Kati ghati, before repairs, from south ...	"	
88	"	" " after " " " "	"	
89	"	" " " " " north ...	"	
90	"	Battisi baodi, corner view from n.-east.	"	
91	"	" " " " n.-west.	"	
92	"	" " inscription over lintel ...	Half.	
93	"	" " in niche ...	Full.	
94	"	" " in another niche ...	"	
95	"	Shekhon-ka-maqbara, carving work ...	Half.	
96	"	Christian tomb, near Chaudhari's house.	"	
97	"	" " near Hara kund ...	"	
98	"	Idgah, inscription ...	"	
99	"	Gol baodi, Inscription in niche ...	"	
100	"	" " in another niche, ...	"	
101	"	Hanuman temple on fort hill, inscription.	"	
102	"	Ram Bharose's house, inscription	"	
103	"	Jamah masjid, inscription ...	"	
104	"	Horse's tomb ...	"	
105	Fatehabad	Koshak mahal, general view from north east.	Full.	Duplicate.
106	"	" " front view ...	"	
107	"	" " interior corner view.	"	
108	"	" " interior big arches from west.	"	
109	Pancham-nagar.	Old palace after repairs, general view from north-east.	"	
110	Singhpur.	" " repairs, general view from south.	"	
111	Gurila Hill	A group of sculptures in a ruined Jaina temple.	Half.	

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS.
201	Archæological Museum.	Two elephants, from Gwalior ...	Half.	
202	"	Fragment of an image, from Badoh...	"	
203	"	A man playing on a tabor, from Badoh	"	
204	"	Varahi and a female bust "	"	
205	"	Torso of a female and another piece, from Badoh.	"	
206	"	Marriage of Siva and Parvati, from Padhavli.	"	
207	"	Siva standing, from Kotah ...	"	
208	"	Bust of Trimurti, from Padhavli ...	"	
209	"	Bust of Indra, from Badoh ...	"	
210	"	Hari-Hara standing, from Ghusai ..	"	
211	"	Nrisimha standing, from Besnagar ...	"	
212	"	Kumara standing, from Kota (Ud.)...	"	
213	"	Kaumari standing " " ...	"	
214	"	Brahmani standing " " ...	"	
215	"	Siva and Parvati ...	"	
District Mandasor.				
216	Khilchipura.	Yamuna on Torana pillar Sravan Kawad	"	Dupli.
District Ujjain.				
217	Kaliadeh.	Water palace, distant view from north-east.	Full.	
218	"	" " near view from south- west.	"	
219	"	" " near view from south- east.	"	
220	"	" " near view from north- east.	"	
221	"	" " near view from north- west.	"	
222	"	" " interior arcade of water chambers.	"	
223	Ujjain	Chaubis Khamba, from north ...	"	
224	"	Vridha Kalesvara, from south-east.	"	
225	"	Mahakalesvara, from south-east ...	"	
226	"	Persian inscription (loose) preserved in Madhava College.	"	
227	"	Sanskrit inscription (loose) preserved in Madhava College.	"	
228	"	Jaisingh's Astronomical Observatory, general view from north.	"	
229	"	Jaisingh's Astronomical Observatory general view from south-west.	"	
230	"	Jaisingh's Astronomical Observatory, showing Digsha Yantra from north.	"	
231	"	Jaisingh's Astronomical Observatory showing Nadivalaya Yantra and Dakshina Vritti Yantra from north-east.	"	

No.	Place.	Subject.	Size.	REMARKS.
Miscellaneous.				
232	Sanchi (Bhopal State)	Buddhist stupa No. 1, general view from south-east.	Full.	
233	"	" " general view from north-east.	"	
234	"	" " eastern gateway	"	
235	"	" " eastern gateway another view.	"	
236	"	" " detail of a pillar	"	
237	"	" No. 3 general view from south.	Half.	
238	"	Gupta temple, general view from north-east.	Full.	
239	Muradpur (Kurwai State)	Varaha (animal shaped)	...	"
240	"	A seated monkey goddess	...	Quarter.
241	Chanderi.	Topo sheet copied	...	Full.
242	"	Topo sheet copied	...	Half.
243		Astronomical instruments	...	Full.
244		Painting showing a bird flying over a river.	"	
245		" " lion led by a fairy and a demon.	"	
246		" " a Muhammadan saint and a she-buffalo,	Half.	
247		" of Radha Krishna	...	"
248		" showing (1) Krishna and cows and (2) scene of bathing.	"	
249		" showing Siva with two females on throne and three female attendants.	"	

Dupli.

APPENDIX No. I.

List of lantern slides made during
Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Description.	Copying negative if any.	REMARKS.
Gateways.			
1	North gateway of Buddhist stupa No. 1 at Sanchi.		
2	Elephant gate, Gwalior Fort.		
Rock-cut caves.			
3	Interior of cave No. 2, at Bagh.		
4	Varaha cave at Udaygiri.		
Temples.			
5	Temple No. 1 at Surwaya ...	1	
6	" " " Doorframe.		
Buddhist Sculptures.			
7	Bodhisatva Maitrya seated ...	1	
8	" " standing ...	1	
9	" " Simhanada ...	1	
10	" seated (Gandhara) ...	1	
11	Buddha (seated) Lucknow Museum ...	1	
12	" in abhaya mudra ...	1	
13	" in dharma-chakra mudra ...	1	
14	" standing ...	1	
15	" practising penance ...	1	
16	" leaving his capital in renunciation ...	1	
17	" Mara's army marching to disturb penance of.	1	
18	Kubera and Hariti ...	1	
19	Naga Raja ...	1	
20	Manjusri or goddess of wisdom...	1	
21	Dvarapala from a gateway of stupa No. 1 at Sanchi.	1	
Jaina sculptures.			
22	Tirthamkara Parsvanatha standing from Budhi Chanderi.		
23	" " seated " "		
24	" " " Gwalior Museum ...	1	
25	A seat of a Tirthamkara, Gwalior Museum...	1	
26	A Chaumukha, Gwalior Museum ...	1	
27	A goddess ...	1	
Hindu sculptures.			
28	Brahma ...	1	
29	Vishnu Seshasayi (sleeping on serpent) ...	1	
30	Vishnu riding on Garuda ...	1	

No.	Description.	Copying negative if any	REMARKS.
31	Siva standing, from Gwalior Museum ...	1	
32	" " another " ...	1	
33	" " Tandava (in bronze) ...	1	
34	" " (another) ...	1	
35	" " Linga ...	1	
36	" " and Parvati standing ...	1	
37	Marriage of Siva and Parvati ...	1	
38	Siva and Parvati seated ...	1	
39	Hari-Hara ...	1	
40	Trimurti (bust) ...	1	
41	" standing ...	1	
42	Ganesa dancing ...	1	
43	Kurma avatara ...	1	
44	" " from Gwalior Museum ...	1	
45	" " " ...	1	
46	Varaha " (animal) ...	1	
47	Nrisimha " ...	1	
48	Vamana " ...	1	
49	Trivikrama avatara ...	1	
50	Balarama " ...	1	
51	Buddha avatara of Vishnu ...	1	
52	River goddess Ganga ...	1	
53	River goddess Yamuna ...	1	
54	Surya seated ...	1	
55	Surya seated in chariot ...	1	
56	Goddess Mahishasuramardini ...	1	
57	Yama standing ...	1	
58	Agni " ...	1	
59	Kubera standing ...	1	
60	Indrani " ...	1	
61	Kumara " ...	1	
62	Ashta Dikpalas ...	1	
63	Nava Grahas (nine planets) ...	1	
64	Rahu and Ketu ...	1	
65	Nandi standing ...	1	
66	Varahi and a female bust ...	1	
67	Flying angels ...	1	
68	Mother and child on a couch ...	1	
69	Kumara standing ...	1	
Miscellaneous.			
70	Bagh painting discourse in outline ...	1	
71	H. H. M. Jayaji Rao with a Hindi motto ...	1	Co
72	" " " Balaravi ...	1	Dupl.
73	Welcome ...	1	
74	Goodnight ...	1	

**List of books added to the Office library, during
Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.**

No.	Title.	Remarks.
Archaeological Survey Reports, Memoirs etc.		
1	Archæological Survey of India, Annual Report for 1921-22.	Presented.
2	Report of the Suptd. of Arch. Surv. of Burma for the year ending 31st March 1925.	"
3	Arch. Surv. of Ceylon, Annual Report for 1922-23.	"
4	" " " " " " " 1923-24	"
5	Annul Report of the Mysore Arch. Department for 1924.	"
6	Arch. Surv. of India, Index to Annual Reports for 1902-16.	"
7	Memoirs No. 13 (Kannad Poets mentioned in inscriptions.	"
8	" No. 16 (The temple of Siva at Bhumara by R. D. Banerji).	"
9	" No. 17 (Pallava Architecture Part I by A. H. Longhurst).	"
10	" No. 19 (Hindu astronomy).	"
11	" of the Arch. Surv. of Ceylon, Vol. I, by A. M. Hocart.	"
12	" of the Arch. Surv. of Kashmir No. 1. (Antiquities of Marve-Wadwan) by R.C. Kak.	"
13	" (Stone age in Kashmir), by R. C. Kak. ...	"
14	Annual Report of the Watson Museum of Antiquities for 1923-24.	"
15	Archæology in Gwalior, published by Arch. Deptt. Gwalior.	"
16-17	Ruins of Desert Cathey Vol. I and II by M. A. Stein.	Purchased.
Art, Sculpture and Painting.		
18	Conference of Indian Art held at the British Empire Exhibition on 2nd June 1924.	Presented,
19	Some reflections on an Indian Art Renaissance by the Earl of Ronaldshay.	"
20	The Influence of Indian Art... ..	"
21	Indian Art and letters Vol. I, May 1925... ..	"
22	Indian Art at the British Empire Exhibition 1924 ...	"
23	Indian Paintings under the Mughals by Percy Brown.	Purchased.
24-25	Catalogue of the Indian Collections in the Museum of Fine Arts Boston, Part I and II, By. Dr. Coomarswamy.	"
26	Do Part IV. by Dr. Coomarswamy ...	"

No.	Title.	Remarks.
27	The Himalayas in Indian Art by E. B. Havell ...	Purchased.
28	Indian Images vol. I by B.C. Bhattacharya ...	"
29	Grundzuge Der Indischenkunst by St. Kramrisch ...	"
30	The Buddha story in stone by A. H. Hargreaves ...	Presented.
Bibliography.		
31	Supplement to the Catalogue of Books in the Secretariat General Library at Moti-mahal Part I.	"
32	Catalogue of Books in the Secretariat General Library at Shivpuri.	"
Epigraphy.		
33	Epigraphia Indo Moslemica year 1915-16... ..	Purchased.
34	" " " " 1917-18... ..	"
35	" " " " 1919-20... ..	"
36	" " Indica Vol. X Part VII. July 1924 ...	Presented.
37	" " Vol. XV. No. VIII. Oct. 1924 ...	"
38	Annual Report on South Indian Epigraphy for the year ending 31st March 1924.	"
History.		
39	The travels of Fa-Hien retranslated by H. A. Giles ...	Purchased.
40	Sind the Unhappy Valley by E. A. W. Budge.	
Journals and Periodicals.		
41-54	Indian Antiquary from May 1924 to June 1925 ...	"
55	Index to Vol. LIII. 1924 Indian Antiquary ...	"
56-58	Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland for January, July and October 1924.	"
59-62	Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XIV No. 4 and Vol. XV. No. 1, 2, 3.	"
63-74	Modern Review from July 1924 to June 1925 ...	"
75-77	Rupam Nos. 18, 19 and 20	"
78	The Indian Historical Quarterly Vol. I No. 1, March 1925.	"
79	Shama' a Magazine of Art, Literature etc. Vol. IV. No. 4. July 1924.	"
80	The Times of India, Annual 1925 ...	"
81	The Illustrated London News Sept. 27, 1924 ...	"
82	" " " " " 20, 1924 ...	"
83	The Madras Mail Annual 1924	"
Literature.		
84	Samaranganasutradhara Vol. I By King Bhojadeva ...	"
85-86	The Kadambari of Banabhatta two volumes by P. V. Kane.	Purchased.
87	Classical Sanskrit literature by A. B. Keith ...	"
88	Sanskrit Drama its Origin, Development, Theory and Practice by A.B. Keith.	"

No.	Title.	Remarks.
Numismatics.		
89	Numismatic Notes and Monographs edited by Sydney P. Nots,	Purchased.
90	Catalogue of the coins of the Guptas, Maukharis etc. in the Provincial Museum, Lucknow.	"
91	Lectures on Ancient Indian Numismatics 1924, by D. R. Bhandarkar.	"
Iconography.		
92	Buddhist Iconography by B. Bhattacharya ...	"
State Publications.		
93	Administration Report of the Gwalior State during the year 1921-22	Presented,
94	" " " 1922-23...	"
95	General Statistics of Gwalior State for Samvat 1974 ...	"
96	List of villages by J. N. Datta.	"
97	Memorandum No. 32 बाबत न डंडे होने ताजिये बरोज अदरह व मुकाम उज्जैन.	"
98	" No. 33 बाबत खास फरायज ऑफिसरान	"
99	" 34 ऑफिसरान की अदम् तबज्जह और लापरवाही की चन्द नजीरे.	"
100	" No. 35 हिदायत व ख्यालात दरबार बाबत हासिल ब्रीडिय फार्म व दीगर कारखाने जात.	"
101	मेथिया कानफेन्स.	"
102	Selections of Darbar orders for Samvat 1980 ...	"
Miscellaneous.		
103	Bibliotheca Asiatica No. 452, year 1924 ...	"

APPENDIX No. K.

Statement of income realised in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Heads.	Amount.	REMARKS.
		Rs. a. p.	
1	By sale of Gwalior Fort Albums ...	70 5 0	
2	,, photo prints ...	83 13 0	
3	,, tender forms ...	16 0 0	
4	Auction of mango grove at Khokhai monastery, Ranod.	6 14 0	
	Total	177 0 0	

List of expenditure incurred in Samvat 1981, Year 1924-25.

No.	Heads.	Amount spent current year.			Amount spent last year			Total.		
		Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	
1	Salaries	8,491	9	5	8,491	9	5	
2	Travelling allowances ...	2,542	4	9	2,542	4	9	
3	Contingencies ...	1,060	8	2	13	6	6	1,073	14	8
4	Books and Periodicals ...	392	13	3	65	7	9	478	5	0
5	Museum ...	1,001	10	0	98	0	0	1,099	10	0
6	Works
	(1) Conservation proper	739	15	0
	(a) Katighati at Chanderi	739	15	0	739	15	0
	(b) Delhi gate " ...	16	8	0	16	8	0
	(c) Madarsa " ...	136	5	0	136	5	0
	(d) Yasodarman's pillars at Sondni.	24	0	0	24	0	0
	(e) Jaina temple at Budhi Chanderi.	15	8	0	15	8	0
	(f) Clearance of caves at Bagh.	2,099	5	6	3	14	9	2,103	4	3
	(g) Minor monuments at Chanderi.	428	7	6	428	7	6
	(h) Fixing sign-boards ...	5	0	0	5	0	0
	(i) Gupta sculpture in Mandasor fort.	28	0	0	28	0	0
	(j) Gumbaz-ka-maqbara	6	0	0	6	0	0
	(k) Bijamandal mosque	5	7	6	5	7	6
	(l) Copying frescoes at Bgha.	337	4	6	337	4	6
	(m) Udayesvar temple	2,074	5	0	2,074	5	0
	(n) Khokhai temple ...	50	6	0	40	0	0	90	6	0
	(o) Gadarmal temple at Badoh.	62	8	0	62	8	0
	(p) Sola khambi at Badoh	8	0	0	8	0	0
	(q) Ujjain Observatory...	6,568	10	0	6,568	10	0
	(r) Jaina temple at Badoh	25	0	0	25	0	0
	(s) Minor monuments at Narwar.	39	10	3	39	10	3
	(2). Salaries of work charged staff.	307	0	6	307	0	6
	(3) Dr. J. H. Cousin's visit to Bagh caves.	298	11	0	298	11	0
	(4) D. G. A.'s visit to Bagh caves,	199	14	0	199	14	0
	(5) Excavations ...	1,096	9	0	154	6	9	1,250	15	9
	(6) Sending frescoes to England.	187	9	0	187	9	0
7	Publication of Gwalior Fort Albums	146	10	6	146	10	6
8	Special grant for Narwar Fort works.	16,824	13	6	16,824	13	6
9	Miscellaneous ...	414	13	9	2	14	0	417	11	9
10	Expenditure over and above Budget grant ...	159	0	0	159	0	0
	Grand Total.	36,570	6	1	9,621	15	3	46,192	5	4

(a) Cave No. 2 at Bagh, interior corner view.

(b) Cave No. 2 at Bagh, Dagoba shrine.

(a) Cave No. 4 at Bagh, facade.

(b) Cave No. 4 at Bagh, a porch.

(a) Katighati (rockcut gateway) at Chanderi.

(b) Badal Mahal gateway at Chanderi.

(b) Sabazadi ka Roza at Chanderi, interior view.

(a) Carved mihrab in a tomb at Chanderi.

(a) Jain Images at Budhi (old) Chanderi.

(b) Rockcut Sculptures at Gadhelna

ANNUAL REPORT
OF THE
ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT
GWALIOR STATE
FOR
SAMVAT 1982, YEAR 1925-26.

GWALIOR :
ALIYAH DARBAR PRESS,—GWALIOR.

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF THE
DEPARTMENT OF ARCHÆOLOGY,
Gwalior State,
FOR THE
Year ending 30th June 1926, Samvat 1982.

PART I.

OFFICE NOTES.

Charge.

1. During the year of report the undersigned held charge of the Department except for a month between the 18th of December 1925 and the 17th of January 1926, while he was on privilege leave. During the period of leave the charge of the current duties of the post remained with R. S. Saksena, the Archaeological Overseer.

Leave.

2. The Superintendent availed himself of one month's privilege leave from the 18th of December 1925 to the 17th of January 1926.

3. Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows:—

- (a) Archaeological Overseer: Privilege leave of 7 days from the 1st October to the 7th October 1925.
- (b) Photographer-Draughtsman: Privilege leave of 29 days from the 1st July to the 8th July 1925 and from the 29th May to the 18th June 1926, sick leave on medical certificate for one month and eight days from the 9th July to the 16th August 1925 and leave without pay for 12 days from the 19th to the 30th June 1926.
- (c) General Assistant: Privilege leave of 39 days from the 11th to the 27th July 1925 and from the 19th December 1925 to the 9th January 1926.
- (d) Officer Accounts: Privilege leave of 10 days from the 2nd to the 11th September 1925.
- (e) Officer Correspondence: Privilege leave of 26 days from the 18th to the 27th August 1925 and from the 27th January 1926 to the 11th February 1926.
- (f) Record-keeper: Privilege leave of 47 days in the several months of the year.

New Post.

4. A new post of the Record-keeper which was sanctioned in the last year's budget was filled up during the year of report. B. B. Chauhan, a Maratha young man who had already put in a year's service in the *Khasgi Karkhana*, being appointed to it.

Promotions.

5. On the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Coronation an increment of Rs. 5 per month was made in the salary of the Officer Accounts and of the Officer Correspondence, as a result of the general order promoting such officers all over the State.

Cash Reward.

6. A Cash Reward of Rupees one hundred (Rs. 100) was conferred on R. S. Khandalkar, Officer Correspondence, on the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Coronation.

General.

7. All the Office Staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

II, Circulars and Orders.

8. Circular No. 1/1982, Home Department (Section Archaeology), was issued in the *Gwalior Government Gazette* of August 8, 1925. It warns the public against injuring or disfiguring Ancient Monuments in the State or removing any carvings or inscriptions from the ruins of or lying loose on sites of such monuments. Further it advises officers of other Departments in the State to send information to the Archaeological Department whenever they come across cases of violation of the aforesaid order.

III, Work at Headquarters.

9. In addition to the ordinary office routine the following work was done during the Headquarter season :—

- (a) An Annual Administration Report for Samvat 1981 was drawn up and submitted.
- (b) A resumé of the conservation and exploration work accomplished by the Department in the year 1924-25 was contributed to the *All-India Archaeological Survey Report*.
- (c) New acquisitions of antiquities in the Museum were arranged and labelled.
- (d) A circular letter was printed and circulated among the *Jagirdars* and *Thikanedars* in the State inviting them to take interest in, and to co-operate with the work of the Department.
- (e) A similar letter was printed and circulated among the *Zamindars* of the several villages in which ancient monuments are situated.
- (f) A short report of the work of the Department for the last ten years was prepared and printed for free distribution.
- (g) Tourists' agencies such as Messrs. Thos. Cook and Son and the American Express Company were moved for including Gwalior and other places of interest in the State in the programmes of foreign tourists which they arrange.
- (h) Arrangement was made with the G. I. P. Railway for exhibiting photographs of our Archaeological Monuments in the higher class carriages and at stations in the vicinity of which monuments are situated.

- (i) Albums of photographs of interesting monuments were prepared and presented to Their Majesties the King and Queen of Belgians at the time of Their Majesties' visit to Gwalior and to His Highness the Maharaja Sahib Scindia on the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Coronation.
- (j) A magic lantern show was given to the boys of the Sardars' School at the Gwalior Fort and another to the Jagirdars assembled at Gwalior on the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Coronation.

IV. Tours.

10. During the year of report I spent 77 days in camp while my Assistant who officiated for me during my leave toured for 16 days.

11. The tours were undertaken for directing and measuring the conservation works in progress, for annual inspections of monuments already conserved and for exploration of fresh monuments. Thus all the conserved monuments at Gwalior, Narwar, Surwara, Ranod, Chanderi, Badoh, Udaypur, Bhilsa, Udaygiri, Ujjain, Mandasor and Bagh were inspected in the year of report. We visited Udaypur four times, Mandasor thrice, Narwar, Padhavli and Bagh twice each, and Suhania once, for the supervision and measurements of conservation works going on there. Devadungri in the Ujjain District, Indhar in the Narwar District, and Mahuwan, Deokani and Mamon in the Esagarh District were visited for exploration purposes.

12. I accompanied Prof. Dr. J. Ph. Vogel of the Leiden University (Holland) during his visits to Bagh and Udaygiri caves as State guest.

13. Moreover with the sanction of the Home Member I visited the ruins of the ancient city Vijayanagar (modern Hampi) in the Ballery District of the Madras Presidency and the wonderful rock-cut caves at Ellora, the Fort of Daulatabad and the monuments at Aurangabad in the Hyderabad State. A visit to these important monuments added considerably to my knowledge of Ancient Indian Architecture. I was also benefited by what I saw of the measures of conservation and upkeep carried out at these places by the local Archaeological Departments.

14. A detailed tour diary is given in Appendix No. A.

V. Conservation.

15. Conservation works were carried out at Bagh, Mandasor, Sondni, Udaypur, Narwar, Padhavli and Suhania at a total cost of Rs. 19,254-6-6 including part of the special grant for Narwar Fort.

16. The statement of monuments conserved in the year of report is set forth in Appendix No. B.

17. **Bagh.**—At Bagh the facade of cave No. 2 was freed from the crust of mud and cow-dung with which it was disfigured in modern times by *sajhus*, *bairagis* and others. The front wall has suffered a number of gaps and fissures especially near the doors and windows, by the decaying of the rock. The northern half of the facade was repaired in the year of report. The decaying edges of the rock were carefully cut out and the gaps filled up

by inserting masonry of dressed stone in lime. Towards the northern end large patches of both the inner and outer faces of the wall have had to be thus renewed. The doorway of the cell at the northern end of the verandah had badly decayed. It was also restored in masonry.

18. A few cells in cave No. 2 are filled up almost to the ceiling with bats' dung. They have defied clearance so far as the workmen find it impossible to work continuously for any considerable length of time in an atmosphere surcharged with the filthy dust. A beginning was made this year to clear up the cells and the work will be accomplished gradually in a few years.

19. With a view to develop the work of repairs the collection of building stone was commenced in the year of report and is progressing slowly owing to the want of good building stone in the locality and the absence of easy means of communication between the quarries and the caves.

20. **Mandasor.**—The excellently carved and imposingly large sculpture of Siva (Gupta period) which had been excavated in a ravine at the south-east corner of the Mandasor Fort three years ago, was lifted out of its unseemly abode and planted up decently on a secure foundation in front of the new building of Subat (Collector's Office) in the same fort. A masonry buttress has been set up behind the sculpture to hold it in position and it is further protected by means of a rectangular fence consisting of a course of iron chains carried on stone posts.

21. The excavations indicated that the sculpture, as it was found, was not *in situ* but had been re-erected there some time during or after the medieval period. Further, as it stood deep in a ravine which carried away the rain water from the major portion of the fort area and got silted up year after year, it would have been very difficult to maintain the sculpture in a clean and tidy condition on that spot. Moreover there was no point in preserving it in that obscure and dirty place. It was therefore shifted to its present site where it occupies a conspicuous position in clean and spacious surroundings so as to attract the attention of visitors.

22. Another piece of sculpture also of the Gupta period which has been brought to the same premises and for similar reasons, is a *Torana* pillar locally known as *Sravan-ki-Kavad*. It originally stood in the narrow, dirty compound of a modern temple in the village Khilchipura about 2 miles to the South of the Mandasor Fort. It is one of the two pillars of a *Torana* or gateway belonging probably to a Saiva temple of the Gupta period. The excavations carried out on the site showed traces of a brick structure probably a part of the original temple. But there were difficulties in preserving the pillar on its original site. Its original ground level was about 6 feet below the present ground level. It was therefore necessary to make a sink 10 feet × 10 feet × 6 feet in order to make the whole pillar visible and accessible to visitors. To make such a pit with retaining walls of masonry on all sides and also to provide a long *pucca* drain to carry away rain water would have been an unnecessarily expensive task. Moreover the pillar stood in an out-of-the-way obscure place. So it was preferred to shift it to the compound of the Subat building in the Mandasor Fort, so as to be in a safe and conspicuous place, and easily accessible.

23. There it has been erected on a strong foundation and fenced round with iron chains carried on stone posts. The original site of the pillar will be marked with an inscribed tablet.

24. **Sondni.**—The heaviest and most arduous work of conservation carried out in the year was that relating to the huge monoliths of Yasodharman lying in a field at Sondni about $2\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the south-east of Mandasor Fort. The columns are inscribed in Gupta characters and record the eulogy of king Yasodharman who flourished about the middle of the 6th century A. C. There are two such columns, exact duplicates of each other, with shafts about 40 feet in length and $3\frac{1}{2}$ feet in section surmounted each by two capitals besides a double faced figure as the crest. For a detailed description of the columns see Dr. Fleet's *Gupta Inscriptions*, pp. 142-46. The columns were lying prostrate in a broken and uncared for condition half buried in earth. The shaft of one of these is broken into two pieces, both the pieces being intact. The shaft of the other column is split into a number of pieces some of which are missing. All the four capitals were lying scattered in a neighbouring field. A double faced head of one of the crowning figures was recovered in the excavations. In order to save these valuable relics from further damage and oblivion all these heavy pieces were dug up, lifted, properly arranged, and exhibited on a strong masonry platform 60 feet \times 15 feet specially constructed for the purpose on the site. As some of the pieces weighed as much as 250 maunds it was no easy task to move them to their new position.

25. Two big sculptures of *Dvarapalas* which are contemporary with and very probably belonged to this monument in some way or other were lying half buried in the same field. These were picked up and set up to flank the approach to the platform.

26. A rectangular area of 155 feet \times 115 feet in the centre of which the platform is located has been freed from jungle, levelled, tidied up and fenced round with three lines of wire carried on stone posts, entrance being provided through a revolving gate. As the locality is rather barren it is proposed to plant trees at the corners of the compound and provide a few stone seats for visitors.

27. A stone inscription giving a brief account of the pillars both in Hindi and English has been set up close by, for the information of visitors. The original foundations of the pillars which were exposed during the excavations carried out here three years ago, have been marked by inscribed stone slabs. Thus every care has been taken to protect the monument from further damage, to mark its original site, and to present it in an attractive and intelligible form.

28. **Udaypur.**—The *kachcha* houses trespassing into the original compound of the Udayesvar temple were acquired by Government towards the end of the last year. As these houses blocked up and disfigured the view of the great temple, they were dismantled and their debris removed to a safe distance. The original compound has thus been freed from all unnecessary and ugly encumbrances. After the removal of these houses it was found that in the compound wall the original portion survives only here and there and the varied patches of restorations made in later times have themselves become dilapidated or damaged in several places. To dismantle the whole wall and

rebuild it in a uniform pattern of masonry though desirable would entail enormous expenses. It is therefore proposed to repair only the badly bulging or dilapidated portions, to reduce the wall to a uniform height by levelling down taller and raising up shorter portions and making the top water-tight.

29. The original entrance to the enclosure flanked by an elaborately carved figure of *Dvarapala* on either side has been exposed in the East enclosure wall. This passage will be cleaned up and properly maintained.

30. **Narwar.**—In continuation of the repairs to ancient monuments on the Fort carried out last year, the small Roman Catholic Church erected by a company of European gunners employed by the Rajas of Narwar in the middle of the 18th century and referred to by General Cunningham (*C. A. S. R.*, Vol. II, pp. 322-23) was attended to in the year of report. The enclosure wall of the compound in which the chapel stands was repaired and the enclosed area was freed from jungle and tidied up.

31. Two tombs of Armenian missionaries, one inside and the other outside the town of Narwar, were liberated from jungle and rubbish with which they had been covered. Their surroundings were further tidied up.

32. Stone inscriptions in Hindi and English giving the names and short descriptions (wherever necessary) were put upon or near most of the important monuments conserved.

33. **Padhavli.**—In the small ruined fort (*gadhi*) at Padhavli about 20 miles to the north of Gwalior are the remnants of a 10th century Siva Temple. This temple stood on an extensive platform in the midst of a set of attendant shrines. Three or four centuries ago when the temples had fallen into ruins the present *gadhi* was built so as to cover and conceal the whole platform the limits of which are perhaps marked by the present quadrangle. The portion of its northern face which is still visible testifies to its massive construction and fine carving. Only the hall (*sabhamandapa*) of the main temple has survived but this also was converted into a room by running up walls on three sides of it and an open balcony with domical roof was built upon it. The ceiling and the architraves of the *sabhamandapa* which are still intact bear panels of beautiful carving representing Surya, Siva's dance, Kali, Brahman, Vishnu, Siva and other gods of the Hindu Pantheon. There are also other sculptures some of which can be identified as scenes from the Ramayana and so on.

34. In view of the superb sculpture on the original temple and the dilapidated condition of the *gadhi* which is now a deserted place it was thought desirable to dismantle the modern structures so as to expose to view the existing portion of the original temple, to clear up the jungle, and tidy up the place.

35. The clearance of the jungle and the dismantling of the modern structures were carried out in the year of report. The work of exposing the plinth of the main temple which is buried in earth, of providing drainage, and of tidying the place is in progress.

36. **Suhania.**—Suhania was a large and flourishing town in the mediæval period. It possesses quite a number of ruins of temples both Hindu and Jain dating from the 10th to the 12th century A. C. covering an extensive area round the present village which lies about 30 miles north of Gwalior.

By far the largest and most important of these monuments is a temple of Siva locally known by the name of Kakanmadh. It is popularly believed to have been built by the order of a Queen named Kakanavati from whom the temple derives its name. But a verse in the Sanskrit inscription on the Sasbahu temple on Gwalior Fort records that Kirttiraja, a Kachhawaha King of Gwalior (who reigned about 1000 A. C.), erected a large temple of Siva at Simhapaniya. Simhapaniya is modern Suhania and the temple referred to is obviously the Kakanmadh temple.

37. The temple stands on a ruined and spacious platform which is now completely buried in a mound of earth. The main temple was surrounded by a set of attendant shrines which have now left nothing more than mere traces. The pyramidal roof of the *sabhamandapa* is supported on majestic pillars and the whole exterior of the temple was decorated with fine sculpture. The shrine is surmounted by a spire which rises to a height of nearly 100 feet above the surrounding ground level and is seen from a distance of several miles.

38. The temple is in a much ruined condition. The facing of the *sikhara* has all disappeared. Some of the pillars have disintegrated and portions have flaked off. The roof is damaged and a few lintels have cracked. One and all the attendant shrines have disappeared. The high platform is in ruins and is literally buried in the debris and covered with a jungle of shrubs.

39. As this is one of the finest and largest old temples in this part of the country it is well worthy of being conserved and maintained in permanent good order. This work was sanctioned towards the end of the year, and could only be started when the year under report came to a close.

VI. Upkeep.

40. Annual clearance of jungle and petty repairs were carried out to all important groups of conserved monuments.

VII. Exploration.

Excavations.

41. No excavations were undertaken in the year of report. The excavations at Pawaya could not be resumed as the necessary procedure for the permanent acquisition of the piece of land in which the excavations have proved fruitful was not completed before the excavation season.

Listing.

42. In the year of report 52 ancient monuments were listed. They are located at 17 different places and comprise ruins of temples, sculptures, memorial pillars, Sati stones, tombs and old guns. Appendix No. C gives a list of these monuments and the more important of them are described below.

43. **Narwar.**—Below the Urwahi gate (western approach) of the Narwar Fort is a Jain temple the present building of which though perhaps hardly two centuries old shelters images of *Tirthankars* very much older. There are five images in all, four of black and one of white marble. Three of the former are of Neminatha and the fourth perhaps represents Rishabhanatha. This last is the earliest and bears on its pedestal an inscription, dated V. S. 1213. The other three of black marble bear dates V. S. 1316 and 1340 and 1348, respectively. The sculpture of white marble has no inscription.

44. **Narwar Fort.**—This Fort still possesses a number of old guns. Some of these have already been listed. Three more guns were listed this year. The longest of these is that known as Betwali lying on the southernmost bastion in the Gujrat *ahata* of the Fort. It is 14 feet and 6 inches long 1 foot and 1½ inches in diameter at the mouth and has a bore of 3 inches diameter. It is numbered 20. Superior in workmanship is another gun called Jaldar bearing the number 19. It is placed on the south-west bastion of the Gujrat *ahata*. It is 14 feet in length, 3 feet and 6 inches in circumference at the mouth, the diameter of bore being 4½ inches. The barrel of the gun is decorated with foliage designs incised on it. It is attended by a smaller gun No. 21 lying on the ground close by which is 6 feet and 6 inches in length. The diameter of the barrel at the mouth is 10 inches and that of the bore is 3 inches.

45. **Siroha** (3 miles north-west of Narwar).—This village was visited for a second time in the year of report and a few more antiquities came to my notice during this visit. There are three old images of Hanumat, a sculpture of Agni, and an intertwined coil of four serpents, lying in front of the temple of a goddess who is popularly called Anjana, the mother of Hanumat, probably by virtue of the three sculptures of the monkey god which are lying in front of the temple, but who really appears to be the goddess Parvati carrying the child Kartikeya, or the Jain goddess Ambika. There is a round well built of large blocks of stone as usual in the mediæval period. Two old big Siva Lingas and two broken sculptures of Nandi are lying near the village.

46. **Indhar.**—Indhar is an old village about 20 miles to the south-east of Kolaras on the left bank of the river of the same name. Large size bricks and fragments of pottery are found under ground on the western outskirts of the village and traces of brick dwellings and a circular brick well are seen on the banks of the river about a furlong to the north of the village. The place seems to have possessed also a number of Hindu and Jain temples the sites of which marked with fragments of old sculptures are seen along the bank of the river a furlong or two to the north and east of the village. Judging from the fragments, the ruins appear to date from the 8th century onwards. The sculptures seen above ground are detailed in this list (Appendix No. F). But I was told that quite a large number of sculptures are concealed under water in the pool of the river at the Nayaghat where people bathe. It would be worth while to make a search for these during a hot season when the water of the river reaches its lowest ebb. The *Haveli* of the *Zamindar*, a temple adjoining it and a temple of goddess in a grove outside the village all built by the grandfather of the present *Zamindar* are good specimens of modern carving work. They are, however, shabbily kept.

47. **Baghoria.**—A village about 4 miles east of Indhar. On the south-west outskirts of the village there are a number of old *sati* stones the inscriptions on which have been obliterated hopelessly. The ruins of a Mohammedan tomb with a few well carved grave stones in the Chanderi style stand about a furlong to the north-east of the village. But they are of little interest. It is said that a Mohammedan chief had first settled at this place and later on shifted to Ranod which is about 10 miles further east.

District Tawarghar.

48. **Khera**.—On the Morena-Ambah Road near the village Khera about 7 miles from Morena is an old site. Here to the north of the road on a prominence marking the site of an old Hindu temple of about the 10th century is a group of sculptures of goddess Mahishamardini, Ganesa, Surya, Siva and other gods which, though finely carved, are now very badly damaged.

49. **Bavdipura**.—In and about the village of Bavdipura which is about 3 miles to the north-west of Suhanja are scattered a number of old sculptures and architectural pieces mostly brought from the ruins of Suhanja. Among one of these groups was a rather good fragment of a sculpture of a woman holding her hands overhead as if in an attitude of shaking off sloth. The feet are broken off. This has since been brought to the Museum.

50. **Rithora**.—Near this village close to the Railway Station of the same name about 16 miles north of Gwalior, on the Gwalior-Bhind line stand a few interesting stone pillars commemorating warriors killed in battle. Four of these are near a well on the eastern outskirts of the village and judging from the deep carving of the fighting scenes on them they may be assigned to the 8th or 9th century A. C. The group of so many contemporary memorial pillars in one place perhaps indicates that they mark the site of a battle.

51. About a furlong to the west of these is another isolated memorial pillar. Close by are the ruins of a temple in which is seen a four-faced stone pillar peculiarly carved. On one of the faces is carved a sword, on another face is a *Trisula*, on the third a bow and arrows, and on the fourth a *Chakra* (?).

District Esagarh.

52. **Mahuwan**.—Mahuwan is an old village about 10 miles to the north of Esagarh. Scattered around it are a number of fragments of Hindu and Jain sculptures, architectural pieces belonging to temples and a few *sati* stones all dating from the 11th century onwards. The sites of some of the temples can yet be traced. But with the exception of a small shrine locally known as Madhi with ruins of a small Nandi pavilion in front, situated about a quarter of a mile to the south-west of the village, none of them is standing. The old name of the place was probably Madhubana.

53. **Deokani**.—This village situated about 3 miles to the south-east of Esagarh was also visited for a second time and some fresh monuments came to light during the search. Near a deserted and dilapidated *gadhi* were found the ruins of about a dozen small shrines standing in a row facing the east. The shrines are severally dedicated to Vishnu, Siva and Devi and may date from the 12th or 13th century A. C. In the ruins are seen two *sati* pillars one of which bears an inscription dated in Samvat 1387. In the front of these shrines is a *baodi* or step-well contemporary with them.

54. About a quarter of a mile to the east of these stands a temple with a shrine and a *sabhamandapa* attached to it, facing to the east. The shrine measures 5 feet by 5 feet 2 inches and the *sabhamandapa* 11 feet 4 inches by 12 feet 1 inch inside. The *sikhara* has fallen. Over the lintel of the shrine door are Brahman, Vishnu and Siva while the pedestal of the idol inside the shrine is empty.

55. A short distance further east is a small shrine also facing to the east. It is called Ganesa Madhi, for on the central (dedicatory) block of the lintel is Ganesa flanked by Brahman at one end and Siva at the other.

56. Flanking this shrine on the left are the traces of another shrine and a memorial pillar is standing near the latter.

57. **Mamon.**—Mamon is a mere hamlet consisting of a few huts of Gujars about 4 miles to the south of Esagarh. Between the huts and the foot of the hill on the west is the old site of the village. Both on the north and south of this site are the ruins of a few mediæval Hindu and Jain temples, the latter predominating.

58. These temples were in three groups. At present only one Jain temple in the southernmost group is standing, but the sites of about half a dozen other temples are visible. The standing temple has a shrine measuring 8'10" by 5'7" internally and facing to the west. There was a porch in front of the shrine. This porch and the *sikhara* of the shrine have disappeared. The basement of the shrine is old but the upper portions of the walls are a later restoration. At present the shrine has no roof. Inside is a big idol of a *Tirthamkara* 8'10" from head to feet. The pedestal is concealed in debris and so the *lanchhana* if any is not seen. The *Tirthamkara* is attended by two *Yakshas* and five other smaller figures of *Tirthamkaras* standing in the shrine. The principal idol which has a halo behind the head, though slightly damaged is on the whole a good specimen of a 10th century sculpture. The lintel of the shrine door frame also bears images of *Tirthamkaras*. Flanking the door on the north is a fine sculpture of seated Parsvanatha. In a niche at the north-west corner of the exterior of the shrine is a sculpture of Ambika and in a corresponding niche at the south-west corner is a sculpture of Chakresvari. A number of broken images of *Tirthamkaras* are lying in the debris.

59. The ruins of other temples may be passed over but a group of Hindu sculptures collected in a rubble enclosure on the site of the old hamlet are worth a mention. Among them are a sculpture of Vishnu, another of Mahishamardini, a third of an eight-armed goddess and a fourth of Brahman. But the most interesting among the lot are three images of women each carrying a lamp. I had never before seen such a representation.* These are worth being preserved in the Museum.

60. About 2 furlongs to the south-east of Mamon stands a small shrine facing to the west and traces of another close by. A sculpture of Siva-Parvati is lying in the ruins.

District Mandasor.

61. **Khilchipura.**—In the village Khilchipura near Mandasor I noticed two small but nicely carved sculptures of *Dvarapalas* (Gupta period) stuck up in the walls of a newly built Jain temple. The trustees of the temple have agreed to the removal of the sculptures to the Museum of Archaeology.

District Ujjain.

62. **Ujjain.**—About a mile to the east of the Ujjain Railway Station, built up in the southern embankment of the Railway line between telegraph

*NOTE—Since this was in type I came across a somewhat similar design of an old brass lamp.

wire posts Nos. $\frac{633}{3}$ and $\frac{633}{4}$ are two big old water spouts of black trap carved into the shape of the heads of *makaras*. Permission has been obtained from the Railway authorities concerned for removing the sculptures to our Museum,

63. Under a tree on a prominence, a short distance to the east of the astronomical observatory are lying two or three old sculptures one of which is a *naga* figure. It is in the form of a human bust with folded hands, the head is shaded under a canopy of serpent's hoods and the lower half of the body is shaped like a serpent's tail. Though considerably damaged, the carving is a specimen of good sculpture and may be taken to the Museum.

64. **Devadungari.**—Devadungari is a small barren hill 13 or 14 miles to the north-west of the Unhel Station on the Ujjain Nagda Section of the B.B. and C. I. Railway. On the southern slope of the hill is a hamlet of a few houses mostly inhabited by the *Pujaris* or caretakers of a local temple.

65. I visited the place with a view to see if it could be identified with Devagiri mentioned by Kalidasa in the *Meghaduta*. On examination of the site I was satisfied that it was the place meant by the poet.

66. My reasons for the identification are:—

(i) The name of the place, namely, Devadungari, is identical with the name Devagiri, the vernacular word *dungari* being an equivalent of the Sanskrit word *giri* as both mean a hill or mountain,

(ii) The geographical position of *Devadungri* fits in exactly with that of Devagiri as described by Kalidasa in the *Meghaduta*. For, Devadungari is situated between the two rivers the Gambhira (Gambhira) a tributary of the Sipra, and the Chambal (Charmanvati), on the direct route from Ujjain (Ujjayini) to Mandasor (Dasapura).

(iii) Kalidasa refers to a temple (abode) of Skanda on the hill Devagiri. Skanda was the generalissimo of the army of gods in their campaign against the demon Taraka. Now one of the two modern temples which crown the summit of the Devadungari hill is sacred to Devadharmaraja who is represented in stone as a warrior god riding a horse and carrying a spear. The attributes of Skanda and Devadharmaraja are so similar that one is justified in recognising in the latter a survival of his prototype the former. (The worship of Skanda survives probably also in the modern cult of Khandoba in Maharashtra who like Devadharmaraja in Malwa is represented as a warrior god riding on a horse). The modern temple of Devadharmaraja on Devadungari hill therefore, very probably marks the site of the ancient temple of Skanda referred to by Kalidasa. It is true that no traces of the old temple such as carved stones are seen on the site to this day. But this is in no way strange; for, a similar fate overtook so many other ancient temples in Malwa in the turbulent and intolerant days of Muhammadan invasions. Old fanes were demolished and their existence was completely effaced by the removal of their material to be used up in buildings elsewhere.

District Bhilsa.

67. **Badoh.**—Nearly a mile due east of the village Badoh is a group of ruined temples known as Satmarhi or seven shrines. At present only six shrines are standing but the ruins indicate the previous existence of many more. Two shrines only have preserved their door frames one previous of which has the image of Vishnu on the dedicatory block of the lintel and the other has that of Siva. In the former is enshrined a seated idol of the Buddha avatara of Vishnu. A similar but bigger and more elaborately carved sculpture is seen in another (southernmost) of the existing shrines, and a third such sculpture is seen in the ruins of still another shrine. One of the standing shrines has preserved only the pedestal of its idol. From the short fat foot on the pedestal and from the figure of an attendant playing on a tabor which still survive it would appear that the idol which occupied the pedestal was that of Ganesa dancing.

68. **Pathari.**—At the south-west point in the hill between Badoh and Pathari four or five rooms have been built in rough rubble masonry on a high platform against the natural rock. The structures are not very old; carved stones and sculptures brought from the ruins of old temples which abound in the neighbourhood have been utilised in them. In the last but one room from the west a panel 1'10" long by 1'8" broad containing the figures of the Seven Mothers and Siva is cut in the living rock which serves as the back wall of the room. Close to the panel of sculptures is an inscription in 10 lines of Gupta characters (5th century A. C.) engraved on a tablet in the same rock and recording the excavation of the sculptures.

VIII. Epigraphy.

69. Sixteen inscriptions were copied or noticed in the year of report. Out of these thirteen are in Sanskrit, two are in Hindi and one is partly in Arabic and partly in Persian. Classified according to ruling dynasties, one of the inscriptions refers itself to a local chief or Maharaja of the country round about Bhilsa, probably a tributary of the Gupta Empire, one to the Paramaras of Dhar, one to the Jajapellas of Narwar, one to the Tughlaqs and another to the Surs of Delhi, and the remaining mention no king or ruler.

70. The earliest of these is an inscription engraved on a rock tablet in a hill between Badoh and Pathari (District Bhilsa). The characters are Gupta, the language Sanskrit and the object of the inscription is to record the excavation of a panel of sculptures of the Sapta Matrikas or Seven Mothers near which the inscription is engraved. The inscription mentions Maharaja Jayatsena who is styled—Vishayesvara (Lord of the District). But the inscription being badly damaged owing to the peeling off of the rock the name of the District is lost. The date was recorded but is lost with the exception of words showing the day of the month which in this case is the 13th day of the bright half. It is likewise not certain whether the inscription dates from the reign of Maharaja Jayatsena or goes down to that of one of his descendants as the words following *Jayatsenasya* are missing.

71. The next in date is the stone inscription found in a *Dhimar's* house near the Chatua Darwaza at Udaypur (District Bhilsa). It is in Nagari characters and 27 lines of Sanskrit verse engraved on a complete stone slab. This is the latter half of the inscription known as *Udaypur prasasti*

the first half of which on another slab was found at Udaypur and published 34 years ago in the *Epigraphia Indica*, Vol. I, pp. 222 ff. Owing to good many abrasions which the stone has undergone a major portion of the inscription has become obliterated and undecipherable. In the first line it eulogises the military exploits of the Paramara king Udayaditya and specially mentions the total destruction (*samhara*) of the king of Dahila or Chedi (*Dahiladhisa*) at his hands. The genealogy of the Paramaras stops here with Udayaditya. Next follows the panegyric of the family of Nemaks. The names cannot be made out clearly owing to the imperfect condition of the stone. The object of the inscription would appear to be to record the construction of a temple or temples by a scion of the Nemaka family. No date is given. Thus the inscription adds very little to the historical information which we already possess from the first half of this *prasasti* already published.

72. The third in chronological order is a stone inscription originally coming from Barah in the Narwar District and now in the possession of Mr. B. R. Bhalerao. The inscription is on a fragment of stone and forms the concluding portion of a *prasasti* recording the construction of a temple of Vishnu by (name lost). Then follow a few names of traders (*vanik*) by caste who were partners in the work. The names of the engravers (*sutradhara*) and the composer (*kavi*) are given as Sthirarkka and Narayana. At the end the date V. S. 1098 is given in figures.

73. The next in importance would be the stone inscription found built up in a vegetable vendor's (*kurjda's*) house at Narwar. This inscription is in Nagari characters and consists of 18 lines of Sanskrit verse incised on a slab of stone. The stone is complete but the record is left unfinished by the engraver. Further a large irregular patch of the inscribed surface has peeled off owing to which only a portion of the inscription is decipherable. The inscription records the genealogy of the Jajapellas of Narwar down to Asaladeva. Then it describes a family of Mathura Kayasthas originally coming from Gopagiri (Gwalior). The founder of the family was Bhuvanapala who is described as having been a minister of King Bhoja of Dhara. His son was Vasudeva and the latter's son Damodara whose wife was a daughter of Pithana. This couple had five sons the eldest of whom was (name lost). The inscription closes with the panegyric of this man.

74. One more Sanskrit inscription discovered this year is of interest. It is recorded on a memorial pillar lying in the ruins of a series of small shrines in front of a ruined *garhi* (fort) near the deserted village of *Deokani (District Esagarb). It records the death of Rauta Sahajana-deva in a fight over the kidnapping of cows (*go-graha yudhitah*) and the *sahagamana* of his wives in V. S. 1387 during the reign of Mahmood Tughlaq of Delhi. What is interesting in this inscription is that it explains the relation between the panels representing a row of cows and a scene of fight, often met with on memorial pillars of warriors killed on battle fields. The explanation is that these fights took place over attempts to kidnap cows (Cf. *Uttaragograhana* in the *Mahabharata*). This representation of cows on memorial pillars was a puzzle to me till it was solved by this inscription which showed its connection with

*NOTE—See page 9, para 53 above.

the scene of fight depicted. The other Sanskrit inscriptions are mostly votive or *sati* records and are of no special importance.

75. The Arabic-Persian inscription found in debris at Narwar Fort records the construction of a mosque (at Narwar) by Dilawar Khan who styles himself as a Viceroy of Mahmood Shah Adil (of the Sur Dynasty of Delhi) in A. H. 960-1522 A. C.

76. An analysis of all the inscriptions is given in Appendix No. D,

IX. Numismatics.

77. In all 941 coins were examined during the year of report out of which one was of gold, 690 of silver and 250 of copper. The pre-Muhammadan coins included two silver punch-marked pieces and 250 copper coins commonly known as Gadhia which are a debased imitation of Indo-Sessanian coinage. The Muhammadan coins comprised one gold Mohar of Akbar the Great, dated A. H. 981, one silver coin of Nadir Shah and the rest were silver coins of the later Mughal Emperors of Delhi. The mints represented are Allahabad, Balvant Nagar, Kora, Ahmedabad, Surat, Seronj, Etawah and Alamgirpur (Bhilsa). The gold coin was purchased, 419 silver coins were received as treasure-trove finds from three different places in the State, while 271 silver and 250 copper coins were received from the Central Treasury where they had been lying for some years. For a list of coins examined see Appendix No. E.

78. A change in the procedure of dealing with coins found as treasure-trove in the State was sanctioned by the Council of Regency. Hitherto the surplus coins in the treasure-trove finds used to be sent through the Resident at Gwalior to the Superintendent in charge of the Archaeological section of the Indian Museum, Calcutta, who examined and distributed them as necessary among the different Museums in British India and returned the rest. In future the examination and distribution of treasure-trove finds will be done by this Department.

X. Museum.

79. Seven stone sculptures, three stone inscriptions, eighteen metal images, four copper-plates inscriptions, twenty-eight old paintings and one hundred and thirty-seven coins, or one hundred and ninety-seven antiquities in all were acquired for the Archaeological Museum, in the year of report. All the stone sculptures and stone inscriptions and two copper plates were collected from different places in the State. Two copper plate inscriptions were received from the Office of the Law Member, 20 silver, 3 billon and 6 copper coins were received in exchange from Mr. Jaisuriya of Ceylon, and 125 coins were acquired from the treasure-trove. One gold coin, 18 metal images and 28 old paintings were purchased.

80. Among these acquisitions, the three stone inscriptions, namely, (1) the second slab of the Udaypur *prasasti* of the Paramara king Udayaditya, (2) the incomplete inscription of the reign of Asalladeva of Narwar and (3) the Arabic Persian inscription of the reign of Muhammad Shah Adil of Delhi, two copper plate grants from Kuretha in Tawarghar District, one of Malayavarman a Pratihara king of Gwalior and the other of his brother Nrivarman, dated in V. S.

1277 and 1304 respectively and described in the *Annual Administration Report* of Samvat 1972 (year 1915-16), the gold Mohar of Akbar, the tantric image of ten-headed and multi-armed Siva, the image of a goddess riding a lion and the two images of Bodhisattvas are of historical, iconographic or artistic interest. Among the coins received in exchange and added to the Museum are a silver coin of Menander, one of Siladitya, a tribal copper coin from Taxila, one of Azes I, two of Azes II and two of Kadphises, two billon coins of Ranjubala and one Kushan coin. The detailed list of antiquities added to the Archæological Museum is set forth in Appendix No. F.

81. One hundred and fourteen European and 608 Indian visitors have recorded their signatures in the Visitors' Book at the Archæological Museum though many more must have actually visited the institution.

82. The following were some of the distinguished visitors. Their Majesties the King and Queen of Belgians, H. H. the Maharaja of Baroda, the Chief of Jamkhandi, Maharani Sahiba of Satara, Atiya Begum of Bombay, Sir M. Visvesvarayya, Rao Bahadur C. V. Vaidya, Prof. Dr. J. Ph. Vogel of Holland, Mr. S. Fyzee Rahamin of Bombay and Mr. Jaisuriya of Ceylon.

XI. Photography.

83. Ninety-nine photographic negatives and forty-two lantern slides were prepared in the year, lists of which appear in Appendices G and H. Besides the prints for record in Office and for illustrating the resume of work contributed to the All-India *Archæological Survey Report* more than 300 prints were prepared for sale to Dr. A. K. Coomaraswamy of the Boston Museum and to Dr. Prof. J. Ph. Vogel of Holland. An album of important photographs of the year was prepared for being submitted to the Council of Regency. Another album was prepared for being presented to Their Majesties the King and Queen of Belgians during their visit to Gwalior and a third for being submitted to His Highness the Maharaja Sahib as an humble and loyal coronation present from the Department.

XII. Office Library.

84. Ninety-nine books and journals on History, Architecture, Art and allied subjects were added to Office Library in the year of report. Out of these fifty were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and Governments of Indian States to whom our thanks are due. The list of books is given in Appendix I.

XIII. Income and Expenditure.

85. Statements of income and expenditure of the Department under different heads during the year of report are set forth in Appendices J and K from which it will be seen that the annual expenditure was Rs. 36,066-4-11 including part of the special grant for repairs to certain monuments on the Narwar Fort, sanctioned already. The income amounted to Rs. 214-2-0.

XIV. Important Events.

86. On the auspicious occasion of the Coronation of His Highness the Maharaja Sahib Scindia a beautiful album was submitted as an humble and loyal present from the Department.

37. Their Majesties the King and Queen of Belgians visited the Museum and other archaeological monuments on the Gwalior Fort when a picture album prepared by the Department was presented as a memento to Their Majesties by His Highness the Maharaja Sahib.

38. His Highness the Maharaja Sahib of Baroda visited the Archaeological Museum.

39. The Department was At Home to His Highness. The Resident, the Members of the Majlis-i-Am, the principal Officers and gentry of Gwalior were among the guests. Owing to a slight indisposition His Highness was not able to attend the function. Mr. L. M. Crump, the Resident at Gwalior, was therefore in the Chair. A brief account of the work accomplished by the Department during the last ten years was read and printed copies were distributed among the guests. A magic lantern show was also given illustrating important archaeological monuments in the State.

XV. Concluding Remarks.

90. In conclusion I am grateful to Sir Appaji Rao Sahib Shitole, K. C. S. I., Amir-ul-Umra, etc., the Offg. Home Member, for the keen interest which he is taking in the work of this Department. I also beg to thank Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar for the unfailing courtesy and valuable advice with which he continued to favour me with regard to the discharge of my official duties, till he proceeded on a long leave.

M. B. GARDE,
Superintendent of Archaeology,
Gwalior State.

APPENDIX No. A.

**Tour Diary of the Superintendent for the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.**

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.
October 1925.	
25th	Gwalior to Satanwara.
"	Satanwara to Narwar.
26th	Halt at Narwar.
27th	Narwar to Satanwara.
"	Satanwara to Gwalior.
November 1925.	
11th-12th	Gwalior to Bareth.
12th	Bareth to Udaypur and back.
"	Bareth to Bina.
12th-13th	Bina to Mhow.
14th	Mhow to Bagh.
15th-18th	Halt at Bagh.
19th	Bagh to Mhow.
20th	Mhow to Mandasor.
21st	Mandasor to Bhilsa.
22nd	Bhilsa to Sanchi and back.
23rd	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.
24th	Bhilsa to Bareth.
"	Bareth to Udaypur and back.
25th	Bareth to Gwalior.
December 1925.	
18th
January 1926.	
17th	On leave.
18th-19th	Bombay to Hospet <i>via</i> Hubli.
20th	Hospet to Hampi.
21st	Halt at Hampi.
22nd	Hampi to Hospet.
22nd-23rd	Hospet to Bombay.
24th	Bombay to Aurangabad.
25th	Aurangabad to Ellora Caves.
26th	Halt at Ellora Caves.
27th	Ellora caves to Daulatabad.
"	Daulatabad to Manmad.
27th-28th	Manmad to Gwalior.
March 1926.	
27th	Gwalior to Satanwara.
"	Satanwara to Narwar.
28th to 3rd April	Halt at Narwar.
4th	Narwar to Satanwara.
"	Satanwara to Gwalior.
27th	Gwalior to Morena.
"	Morena to Kunwari river and back.
28th	Morena to Ambah.
29th	Ambah to Suhania.
30th	Suhania to Padhavali.

APPENDIX No. A —(concl'd.)

Date month and year.	Movements and Halts.
May 1926.	
1st	Padhavali to Rithora.
"	Rithora to Gwalior.
6th	Gwalior to Kalhar.
7th	Kalhar to Badoh.
8th	Badoh to Udaypur.
9th	Halt at Udaypur.
10th	Udaypur to Bareth.
"	Bareth to Ujjain.
11th	Ujjain to Unhel.
12th	Unhel to Devadungari and back.
"	Unhel to Mandasor.
13th-15th	Halt at Mandasor.
16th	Mandasor to Mhow.
17th	Mhow to Sardarpur.
18th	Sardarpur to Bagh.
19th	Bagh to Bagh Caves.
20th	Bagh Caves to Bagh.
21st	Bagh to Mhow.
22nd-23rd	Mhow to Ujjain.
23rd-24th	Ujjain to Bhilsa.
24th	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.
25th	Bhilsa to Gwalior.
June 1926.	
2nd	Gwalior to Shivpuri.
3rd	Shivpuri to Surwaya and back.
4th	Shivpuri to Kolaras.
5th	Kolaras to Indhar.
6th	Indhar to Ranod.
7th	Halt at Ranod.
8th	Ranod to Mahuwan.
9th	Mahuwan to Esagarh and thence to Mamon.
10th	Mamon to Maholi.
11th	Maholi to Chanderi.
12th	Chanderi to Mungaoli.
12th-13th	Mungaoli to Gwalior.
16th	Gwalior to Rithora.
"	Rithora to Padhavli.
17th	Padhavli to Rithora.
"	Rithora to Gwalior.
Officiating Superintendent's Diary of Tour for Samvat 1932.	
December 1925.	
18th	Gwalior to Bareth.
19th	Bareth to Udaypur.
20th	Udaypur to Badoh.
21st	Badoh to Udaypur.
22nd	Udaypur to Bareth.
23rd	Bareth to Bhilsa.
24th	Bhilsa to Ujjain.
25th	Ujjain to Mandasor.
26th	Mandasor to Sondni.
27th	Halt at Sondni.
28th	Sondni to Mandasor.
29th-31st	Halt at Mandasor.
June 1926.	
1st	Mandasor to Ujjain.
2nd	Ujjain to Gwalior.

APPENDIX No. B.

Statement of Expenditure on Monuments conserved during Samvat 1982.

Serial No.	Place.	Name of Monument.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.		Total.	AMOUNT SPENT.		Total	REMARKS.
			Current year.	Last year.		Current year.	Last year.		
1	Gwalior Fort	...	Rs.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	
2	Bagh	Gujari Mahal	182	...	182 0 0	156 9 9	...	156 9 9	
3	Udaypur	Bagh Caves	1,000	556 10 6	1,556 10 6	175 9 0	...	175 9 0	
4	Padbhavi	Udayesvar Temple	2,142	134 12 9	2,276 12 9	2,133 15 9	134 2 0	2,268 1 9	
5	Suhania	Temple in Gadhi	420	...	420 0 0	420 0 0	...	420 0 0	
6	Mandasor Fort.	Kakanmadh Temple	2,413	...	2,413 0 0	9 8 0	...	9 8 0	
7	Sondani	A. Gupta Sculpture	320	670 0 0	990 0 0	317 9 9	656 12 6	974 6 3	
8	Do.	Yasodharman Pillars	...	3,021 0 0	3,021 0 0	...	3,018 12 8	3,018 12 8	
9	Khitchipura	Inscription stone	...	150 0 0	150 0 0	...	103 5 6	103 5 6	
10	Narwar	Torana Pillar	...	352 0 0	352 0 0	...	327 15 7	327 15 7	
11	Badoh	Jait Khambha	...	102 5 9	102 5 9	...	87 2 9	87 2 9	
12	Do.	Sola Khaambhi	...	11 6 6	11 6 6	...	11 0 6	11 0 6	
13	Do.	Jain Temple	...	9 5 6	9 5 6	...	9 0 0	9 0 0	
14	Narwar	Gadarnal Temple	...	12 14 6	12 14 6	...	12 0 0	12 0 0	
15	Gwalior Fort	Narwar Fort near Museum Building.	...	13,906 15 0	13,906 15 0	82 14 6	11,698 0 9	11,698 0 9	
16	Chanderi	Notice Board providing descriptive inscriptions to minor monuments.	83	...	83 0 0	82 14 6	
		TOTAL	6,560	18,935 6 6	25,495 6 6	3,296 2 9	16,068 4 3	19,632 7 0	

APPENDIX NO. C.

Monuments listed during the year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Locality.	Name of monument.	Class.	Ownership.
District Narwar.				
1	Narwar.	Jain temple below the Urwahi gate of the Fort	III	Jain community.
2	"	An old Baodi on the Magroni road with inscription dated Samvat 1822	III	
3	" Fort.	A gun known as Jaldar	I	
4	" "	Another smaller gun lying close to above.	I	
5	" "	" gun known as Betvali	I	
6	Siroha.	A group of old sculptures in front of the temple to Anjana	III	
7	"	An old round stone built well	III	
8	"	Two big Siva <i>lingas</i> and two broken Nandins	III	
9	"	Some fragments of Jain images	III	
10	Indhar.	Several sites of old Hindu and Jain temples marked with old carved stone fragments	III	
11	"	A memorial pillar inscribed, at the western entrance of the village	II	
12	"	A group of sculptures on the bank of the river near the Naya ghat	III	
13	"	Another group of sculptures placed on a <i>kachcha</i> platform in the north east portion of the village	III	
14	"	A big idol of standing Jain <i>Tirthamkara</i> in the bed of the river about $\frac{1}{4}$ mile to the north east of the village	III	
15	"	Traces of old buildings and a circular brick well on the bank of the river close to the above	III	
16	"	A badly damaged but remarkable Jain sculpture in a lane in the western part of the village... ..	III	
17	Baghorla.	<i>Sati</i> stones outside the village, on the south west of it	III	
18	"	A ruined Muhammadan tomb outside the village, on the north east of it	III	
District Tonwarghar.				
19	Khera.	A group of sculptures lying on the site of an 11th century temple	III	
20	Baodipura.	Sculptures placed on a <i>kachcha</i> platform outside the village (one furlong to the north)	III	
21	Rithora.	A memorial pillar in a field to the south of village	III	
22	"	Site of an old temple marked by carved architectural pieces	III	
District Esagarh.				
23	Mahuwan	A shrine known as Madhi	III	
24	"	Three shrines and a sculpture of Kubera on a small <i>tita</i> on the bank of the river.	III	
25	"	A big roof slab of an old shrine	III	
26	"	Two <i>sati</i> stones one bearing an inscription dated Samvat 1443	III	
27	"	Site of another shrine	III	

APPENDIX No. D.

List of Inscriptions copied or noticed during the Year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	Purport.	REMARKS.
1	Narwar.	A stone slab built as a threshold in a <i>kanyāda's</i> house.	18	Old Nagari.	Sanskrit.	...	Asalla of Narwar.	<p>The inscription is left incomplete by the engraver. Verse 22 has been finished and a word or two of the next verse bring the last line to a close. Further the engraved portion is seriously damaged by weathering and a wholesale peeling off of the surface of the stone. Hence the existing portion also is only partly decipherable. It opens with the words <i>ॐ नमोति मयादात्</i>. After invoking a blessing, it proceeds to describe the genealogy of the local kings (of the Jajapalla dynasty) and brings it down to Asalla whose father and predecessor <i>वृषभंशु</i> is extolled as having exacted a tribute even from the proud king of Dhari.</p> <p>Next it gives the genealogy of a family of <i>माधुर्य कश्यप</i> originally coming from <i>गोपमिर्हि कुंग</i> (Gwalior). The founder's name is mentioned as <i>सुवर्णाळ</i> who was a minister of king <i>शेख</i> of <i>शार</i>. His son was <i>वासुदेव</i> and his son <i>दामोदर</i> whose wife wasdaughter of <i>शेख</i>. This couple had five sons, of whom the eldest was.....A panegyric of this man brings the existing portion of the inscription to a close.</p>	

APPENDIX No. D.—(contd).

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	Purpose.	REMARKS.
2	Narwar.	On a loose stone slab found in debris in the compound of the Dargah of Madar Shah on Narwar Fort.	10 and $\frac{1}{2}$ on left margin.	Naksh & Nastaliq.	Arabic & Persian.	A. H. 960 = 1552 A. C.	Mohammed Adil Shah of Dehli.	The Arabic portion is mere quotations from the <i>Koran</i> and <i>Hadith</i> . The Persian portion records the construction of a mosque by Dilawar Khan who styles himself Viceroy of Mohammed Shah Adil (of Dehli) in A. H. 960. It also gives names of the composer, writer and engraver as Syed Ahmad, Nazir Shattari (a follower of Mohammed Ghous) and Khanjahan respectively.	
3	"	On the pedestal of a शिवलिंग in a Jain temple at western foot of the Narwar Fort.	...	Nagari.	...	V. S. 1213	...	Records the installation of the idol. सं० १२१३ अष्टाव सुदी [९].	
4	"	" another image	...	"	...	V. S. 1316	...	Records the installation of the idol. सं० १३१६ अष्ट कृती ५ सोम.	
5	"	" another.	...	"	...	V. S. 1340	...	Records the installation of the idol. सं० १३४० वैशाख सुदी ७ सोम.	
6	"	" "	V. S. 1368	...	Records the installation of the idol. सं० १३६८ वैशाख सुदी ७ सोम.	
7	"	In a <i>कदम्ब</i> on the <i>अष्टाव</i> in the	10 and $\frac{1}{2}$ on left margin.	Nagari	Hindi.	V. S. 1324 = 1408	...	Records the construction of the well during the reign of Sir Raja Sada Kashyap of Narwar on Sunday the 17th of the bright half of <i>शुक्ल</i> in V. S. 1324 Saka 168.	

APPENDIX No. D.—(contd.)

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	Purport.	REMARKS.
8	Bara.	On a stone slab now in the possession of Mr. B. R. Bhaletno.	8	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	V.S. 1098	The inscription is fragmentary being the ending portion of a शक्ति. The existing portion is well preserved and can be completely read. It records the construction of a temple of Vishnu (<i>Garudasana</i>) by—(name lost) then follows a list of names of traders (शक्ति) by caste who were partners in the work. The names of the सूत्रार (engraver) and the कवि (composer) are given as स्थिरक and नारायण respectively. The date is given in figures at the end.	
9	Indhar.	On a memorial pillar half buried at the western entrance of the village.	7	"	"	V.S. 1345	...	Purport not made out.	The inscription is weathered and could not be properly deciphered from the stone during the short visit.
10	Mahuwan	On a Sati post.	...	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	V.S. 1443	...	Do.	Steadily weathered
11	"	On another Sati post.	...	"	Hindi.	V.S. 1724	...	Do.	Do.

APPENDIX No. D.—(contd.)

No.	Place.	Object inscribed.	Lines.	Script.	Language.	Date.	King.	REMARKS.
16	Udaypur.	On a loose stone slab found in a house near Chattral Gate.	27	Nagari.	Sanskrit.	Not given.	Udayaditya Paramara	<p style="text-align: center;">P U R N O R T .</p> <p>This inscription is the latter half of the Udaypur <i>prasaśi</i> of the reign of Udayaditya, the first half of which was found several years ago and published in the <i>Ep. Ind.</i> Vol. I, pp. 222 ff. The inscription is badly worn out and has therefore not been completely deciphered. The genealogy of the Paramara kings ends with the reign of Udayaditya only. In the course of the eulogy of Udayaditya it records his several military exploits among which his complete destruction of the king of Dahala (<i>वहल</i>) in line 2 is worthy of note. Then follows the panegyric of the family of Neenakas whom the king had put in charge of the town of Udaypur. Owing to the imperfect decipherment of the inscription so far, it has not become possible to make out definitely the object of the inscription but it appears from some of the expressions and phrases that have been deciphered that it records the construction of a temple or temples by Damodara a scion of the Nemaka family. No date has been recorded in the inscription. So the new find does not add much to the historical information which we already possess about the Paramaras.</p>

APPENDIX No. F.

List of antiquities added to the Archaeological Museum during
the year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
Stone Sculptures.				
			Ht. Br.	
1	Suhania.	A woman (feet broken off) ...	2'1" × 9"	
2	"	A head of a woman ...	6 $\frac{3}{4}$ " × 6"	
3	"	Another head of a woman ...	5" × 5 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	
4	Narwar.	A canopy of a Jain image flanked on either side by an elephant.	3'1" × 1'5"	
5	Gohad	A <i>chakra-vyuha</i> ...	3' × 3'	
6	Indhar.	A small image of Balarama ...	1'2" × 6"	
7	Surwaya.	A human skull ...	4"	
Stone Inscriptions.				
8	Udaypur.	A Sanskrit inscription ...	2'7" × 2'5"	
9	Narwar.	" " ...	2'2" × 2'	
10	"	A Persian " ...	2'3" × 1'6"	
Metal Images.				
11		An elephant with drums being played on by a rider.	3 $\frac{3}{4}$ " × 3"	Pur-chased.
12		An ornamental lamp with a figure of Gaja-Gauri on the back and horse-men at sides.	6 $\frac{1}{2}$ " × 5"	
13		A standing goddess holding an object perhaps a bell in her right hand.	7 $\frac{1}{2}$ " × 3 $\frac{1}{4}$ "	"
14		A standing goddess holding an object (a flower bud) in left hand.	7" × 2 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
15		A standing goddess holding a lotus flower in right hand.	4 $\frac{1}{4}$ " × 2"	"
16		A four armed god (perhaps Siva?) with arrow and sword in right hands and a bow and club in left hands and a garland of skulls round the neck and flanked by a male and female attendant.	8 $\frac{1}{4}$ " × 5 $\frac{3}{4}$ "	"
17		Hanuman shaped handle of a bell ...	5 $\frac{1}{2}$ " × 1 $\frac{3}{4}$ "	"
18		A horseman piercing a wild animal (conventional tiger) with a lance.	5" × 2" × 3 $\frac{1}{2}$ "	"
19		A <i>Bodhisattva</i> in <i>dhyani mudra</i> ...	6 $\frac{3}{4}$ " × 4 $\frac{3}{4}$ "	"
20		A bull (Nandi) ...	3 $\frac{3}{4}$ " × 4"	"

APPENDIX No. F.—(contd.)

N o.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
21		A quadruped (perhaps a mouse with a seat on back for an idol).	$3\frac{3}{4}'' \times 3\frac{1}{2}''$	Purchased.
22		A devotee seated with folded hands ...	$3\frac{3}{4}'' \times 2\frac{1}{2}''$	„
23		A <i>tantric</i> image with 10 heads and sixty hands, standing.	$1'8'' \times 1'1\frac{1}{4}''$	„
24		A seated image of Vajrapani <i>Bodhi-sattva</i> .	$1'1'' \times 9\frac{1}{2}''$	„
25		A four armed goddess seated on a lion.	$1'1\frac{1}{2}'' \times 5''$	„
26		An ornamental duck	$8'' \times 7\frac{1}{2}''$	„
27		A horse	$1' \times 8\frac{1}{2}''$	„
28		A swing supported by two elephants.	$11\frac{1}{2}'' \times 7\frac{1}{2}''$	„
Copper-plates.				
29		A grant of land dated Samvat 1719.	$7'' \times 5\frac{3}{4}''$	Received from Muntazim Jagirdaran Office.
30		A grant of land dated Samvat 1740.	$7'' \times 5\frac{1}{2}''$	„
31	Kuretha.	Copper-plate inscription of Malayavarman dated Vikrama Samvat 1277.	$1'2'' \times 10\frac{3}{4}''$	
32	„	Copper plate grant of Nrivarman dated Vikrama Samvat 1304.	$11\frac{3}{4}'' \times 7\frac{3}{4}''$	
Old Paintings.				
33		A woman doing her toilet ...	$9\frac{3}{4}'' \times 7\frac{3}{4}''$	Purchased.
34		A picture of the month of Chaitra showing hero and heroine (Krishna and Radha?) seated facing each other flowers in hand.	$8\frac{1}{4}'' \times 5\frac{1}{2}''$	„
35		A picture of the month of Vaisakha. Hero and heroine seated outside a bungalow, flowers in hand, attended by a maid servant holding a fan.	„	„
36		A picture of the month of Jyeshtha. hero and heroine seated in a bungalow in the midst of a garden attended by a maid servant bearing a fan.	$8\frac{1}{4}'' \times 6''$	„
37		A picture of the month of Ashadha. hero and heroine standing outside a bungalow. The hero holding the left hand of the heroine with his right. The heroine pointing a finger of her right hand up to clouds in the sky.	$8\frac{1}{4}'' \times 6''$	„
38		A picture of the month of Margasirsha. The hero and heroine standing outside a bungalow. The hero is offering flowers to the heroine who also is holding a bunch of flowers in her right hand. A maid servant is preparing a bed inside the bungalow.	„	„

APPENDIX No. F.—(contd.)

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
39		A picture of the month of Pausha. The hero and heroine attended by a maid servant warming their hands on a fire in an open bungalow	8½" × 6"	Purchased.
40		The hero and heroine riding a trotting camel in a mountainous tract of country, accompanied by a horseman. A footman with fiddle in hand walking in advance. The heroine is shooting an arrow at one of two horsemen seen beyond a hillock in the rear ...	1' × 1¼" × "9¾"	"
41		The hero and heroine on horse back. The hero pointing out his hand towards the rear	9½" × 7¼"	"
42		Two chiefs seated on two separate carpets facing each other. The senior chief advising and the junior listening	8" × 6¼"	"
43		An Emperor and Empress on horse back. A hawk on the Emperor's hand. (Baz Bahadur and Rupamati ?).	10¼" × 9½"	"
44		A boar hunt. A horseman wounding a boar with his sword	8¼" × 5½"	"
45		Two ladies seated facing each other. One smoking a <i>hukkah</i> and the other playing on a lute (<i>tambora</i>)	6½" × 11¼"	"
46		A Rajput chief seated on a throne sword in hand	10' × 8"	"
47		Picture of Asavari a Ragini of Sriraga showing a man and a woman seated facing each other outside a house in a garden. The woman is holding a cobra in either hand and the man is playing on a flute	10" × 7¾"	"
48		A blind Emperor (Shah Alam II ?) seated on a throne attended by a chowri-bearer at the back and another servant in front	11¾" × 8¾"	"
49		A picture of Bilawal a Ragini of Hindol Raga showing a heroine seated on a coach and putting on ear jewels. A maid servant in front showing her a looking glass	10" × 7¾"	"
50		A picture of Purvi a Ragini of Dipaka Raga. A heroine seated on a pedestal and attended by two maid servants with folded hands	11" × 7¾"	"

APPENDIX No. F.—(concl'd.)

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.	Remarks.
51		A picture of Soratha Raga. Heroine seated in her <i>mahal</i> arranging her hair. A maid servant seated in front showing a looking glass. Another maid servant standing at the back holding articles of toilet (?) ...	10" × 6½"	Purchased.
52		A picture of Malasari a Ragini of Bhairava Raga. Heroine seated on a pedestal in a garden house and conversing with a maid ...	10½" × 7½"	"
53		A picture of Malakansa Raga. Hero and heroine seated on a coach in a <i>mahal</i> , attended by four maids bearing <i>chouri</i> and <i>pandan</i> and other objects ...	8" × 10"	"
54		A <i>fakir</i> seated on a mattress, telling beads of a rosary. Another seated facing him ...	7½" × 5"	"
55		A saint wearing a <i>Ramanandi safa</i> is seated leaning against a cushion and telling on a rosary ...	10" × 8"	"
56		A heroine seated on a cushion, a maid servant standing in front flowers in hand (?) ...	11" × 7"	"
57		On a raised platform outside a bungalow on the bank of a tank a goddess (?) is seated on a tiger skin. Another goddess (?) is standing near her with her hands on a swing. Another woman is sitting behind her. A king with folded hands is sitting in front. Five other chiefs are standing down below. A <i>sadhu</i> accompanied by a dog is also standing close by. ...	11¾" × 9½"	Purchased.
58		A hunting scene. An Emperor riding an elephant and party hunting two wild boars. A number of attendants on foot and horse back are moving about in the jungle and shooting arrows ...	1'2" × 11½"	"
59		A Maratha Raja of Tonjore (Sarfoji ?) is seated on a mattress leaning against a <i>lod</i> ...	8¾" × 6¾"	"
60		Mirza Sidu Sahib is riding on a horse followed by four Sardars also on horse back. Three soldiers on foot are at the head of the cavalcade ...	1'7¼" × 1'1¼"	"
		Old Coins.		
61-197		Old coins ...	137	

APPENDIX No. G.

List of photo negatives made during the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh.	Cave No. 3, after clearance ...	Quarter	
2	"	" " " " another view	"	
District Bhilsa.				
3	Besnagar.	Khambaba pillar, after conservation ...	Full	
4	Udaygiri.	Caves Nos. 5 and 6, general view ...	"	Dupl.
District Gird.				
5	Gwalior.	Hathiapaur gate, general view from west ...	"	
6	"	Khandaura Khan mosque from north west, back view ...	"	
7	"	" " " " distant view from north west ...	Half	
8	"	" " " " a mehrab...	Full	
9	"	Sarai gateway, general view from north west ...	"	
10	"	A ruined tomb near Khandaura Khan's mosque ...	Half	
11	Archl. Museum	Bodhisattva Padmapani (a bronze statue)	Full	
12	"	A Tantric figure " "	"	
13	"	A goddess (riding on a lion) front view ...	"	
14	"	" " " " side view ...	"	
15	"	Siva (?) " "	Half	
16	"	A goddess standing carrying a bell (?) in right hand.	"	
17	"	A horse (a bronze statue)	"	
18	"	A lamp with a figure of Gaja Gauri on back (a bronze statue) ...	"	Dupl.
19	"	A swing supported on two elephants (a bronze statue) ...	"	
20	"	A goddess standing and carrying a lotus bud in left hand (a brass statue) ...	"	
21	"	A duck (a brass statue) ...	"	
22	"	A Bodhisattva seated (a brass statue),	"	
23	"	A goddess standing and carrying a lotus in right hand (a brass statue) ...	Quarter	
24	"	A Drummer riding on elephant (a brass statue) ...	"	

No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	Size.	Remarks.
25	Archl. Museum.	A mouse (?), vehicle of a god (a brass statue).	Quarter.	
26	"	A horseman hunting a tiger with his lance (a brass statue)	"	
27	"	A bull (Nandi) ... " "	"	
28	"	A Hanumat shaped handle of bell ... " "	"	
29	"	A devotee seated with folded hands ... " "	"	
30	"	Siva slaying Gajasura (a stone sculpture)	Full	Dupl.
31	"	Parvati standing " "	"	
32	"	Kurma <i>avatara</i> fragment " "	Half	
33	"	A Jain <i>chaumukha</i> . " "	"	
34	"	Kubera ... " "	"	"
35	"	Bhairava standing " "	"	
36	"	A female standing " "	"	
37	"	A goddess in a niche	Quarter	
38	"	Another goddess in a niche ...	"	
District Mandasor.				
39	Sondani.	Yasodharman's pillars, view from south west after conservation ...	Full	
40	"	Yasodharman's pillars, view from north or east after conservation ...	"	
41	"	Two <i>Dvarapalas</i> after conservation ...	"	
42	Chorpura.	An old temple in ruins from south west.	"	
District Narwar.				
43	Narwar Fort.	Fort, a view from south east ..	"	
44	" "	" another view from east ...	"	
45	" "	" " " " south east	"	
46	" "	" " " " " "	"	
47	" "	" " " " " "	"	
48	" "	Makaradhvaj Tal, after repairs, view from north east ...	"	
49	" "	Makaradhvaj Tal, after repairs, view from north west ...	"	
50	" "	Chhip Mahal after clearance ...	"	
51	" "	A stone trough known as Chhip, after repairs	"	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	Remarks.
52	Narwar Fort.	Ladau Bungalow after repairs ...	Full.	
53	" "	Jamah Masjid after repairs ..	"	
54	" "	" " inscription central panel.	Half	
55	" "	" " " northern "	"	
56	" "	" " " southern "	Half	
57	" "	Dargah Madarshah from north east.	Full	
58	" "	Kachehri Mahal or new Dak Bungalow, after repairs from north east.	"	
59	" "	Kachehri Mahal or new Dak Bungalow, after repairs, interior view showing pillars ...	"	
60	" "	Kachehri Mahal or new Dak Bungalow, interior pillars and ceiling, after repairs ...	"	
61	" "	Kachehri Mahal or new Dak Bungalow, Jali work, after repairs ...	"	
62	" "	Kachehri Mahal Baradari from south west ...	Half	
63	" "	Kachehri Mahal general view from west ...	Full	
64	" "	Kachehri Mahal old gardenplot ...	"	
65	" "	" entrance gate ...	"	
66	" "	" " " " ...	Half	
67	" "	Mosque near Havapaur inscription, central panel ...	"	
68	" "	Mosque near Havapaur inscription, northern panel ...	"	
69	" "	Mosque near Havapaur inscription, southern panel ...	"	
70	" "	An old door jamb built in a wall near Havapaur ...	"	
71	" "	Havapaur gate, front view ...	Full	
72	" "	" " side view ...	"	
73	" "	A temple door frame near Havapaur.	"	
74	" "	A Burj after repairs ...	"	
75	" "	Interior of a bastion near Dholapaur.	"	
76	" Town.	Ek-Khamba Chhatri. ...	"	
77	" "	An Armenian tomb near Inspection Bungalow ...	Half	
78	" "	A row of sculptures in the interior of Dehra ...	Full	
79	" "	A sculpture in the interior of Dehra.	"	
80	" "	Jait Khamba after conservation ...	"	
81	" "	Sati Sundar Das, after conservation ...	"	Dupl.
82	" "	Devi on bank of Lakhna Tal ...	Quarter	
District Tawarghar.				
83	Padhavli.	Temple in <i>gadhi</i> before conservation from north west ...	Full	
84	"	Temple in <i>gadhi</i> interior, before conser- vation, another view ...	"	
85	"	Temple in <i>gadhi</i> , another view ...	"	
86	Rithora.	A group of Sati and Memorial pillars.	"	

APPENDIX No. H.

List of lantern slides made during the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Copying negative, if any.	Remarks.
		Pillars.		
1	Besnagar.	Khambaba pillar ...	1	
		Gateways.		
2	Sanchi.	Eastern gate of Stupa No. 1 ...	1	
		Stupas.		
3	"	Stupa No 1, near view ...	1	
4	"	Stupa No. 1, distant view ...	1	
5	Barobodur. (J A V A)	Stupa.		
		Rock-cut Caves.		
6	Udaygiri.	Cave No. 5, Varaha ...	J	Duplicate
7	"	" " 5, and 6, general view ...	1	
8	"	" " 6, Door frame ...	1	
9	"	" " 6, Mahishasuramardini ...	1	
10	"	" " 6, Vishnu ...	1	
11	Bagh.	" " 2, Facade ...	1	
12	"	" " " Interior pillars ...	1	"
13	"	" " " A Dagoba chamber ...	1	
14	"	" " " Buddha with attendants. ...	1	
15	"	" " " " " another group ...	1	
16	"	" " 4, Facade ...	1	
17	"	" " " Door frame ...	1	
18	"	" " " Upper part of above ...	1	
19	"	" " " Pilaster ...	1	
20	"	" " " Frieze ...	1	
21	"	" " " Lion bracket ...	1	
22	"	" " 5 General view, interior ...	1	
23	"	" " 5 and 6 general view ...	1	
		Buddhist Sculptures.		
24	Rorobodur. (J A V A)	A scene in Buddha's life ...	1	
25	"	" " " " ...	1	
26	"	" " " " ...	1	
27	"	Buddha ...	1	
		Brahmanic Sculptures.		
28	Gyaraspur.	Siva slaying Gajasura ...	1	
29	Kota.	" " " " ...	1	
30	Badoh.	Yasoda Krishna (?) ...	1	
31	"	" " " another view ...	1	
32	"	Sri Krishna (?) ...	1	
33	"	Surya ...	1	
34	"	Vishnu ...	1	
		Miscellaneous.		
35	Ujjain.	Observatory, general view ...	1	
36	"	" " Samrat Yantra ...	1	
37	Bagh.	Outline of fresco Discourse ...	1	
38	"	" " " 'Music in the air' ...	1	
39	"	" " " Dance ...	1	
40	"	" " " Elephant procession. ...	1	
41	"	" " " Wall decoration ...	1	
42	"	Cave No. 2, elevation drawing of Dagoba ...	1	

APPENDIX NO. I.

List of Books added to the Office Library
during the year 1925-26, Samvat 1982.

No.	Title.	Remarks.
Archaeological Survey Reports, Memoirs, Etc.		
1	Arch. Surv. of India, Annual Report for 1922-23 ...	Gratis.
2	" " " " " " For 1923-24 ...	"
3	Report of the Superintendent Archaeological Survey of Burma for the year ending 31st March 1926 ...	"
4	Memoirs of the Archæological Survey of India, No. 15. The Drawing of Geometric Patterns in Saracenic Art by E. H. Hankin ...	"
5	Memoirs of the Archæological Survey of India, No. 19. The Jami Masjid at Badaun and other buildings in the United Provinces by J. F. Blakiston ...	"
6	Memoirs of the Archæological Survey of India, No. 20. The Origin and Cult of Tara by H. Shastri ...	"
7	Memoirs of the Archæological Survey of India, No. 21. The Baghela Dynasty of Rewah by H. Shastri ...	"
8	Memoirs of the Archæological Survey of India, No. 22. An Historical Memoir of the Qutb: Delhi by J. A. Page.	"
9	Memoirs of the Archæological Survey of India, No. 27. Pageant of Kings of Mindon by Chas-Duroiselle ...	"
10	Memoirs of the Archæological Survey of Ceylon, Vol. II, year 1926 ...	"
Art and Architecture.		
11	Indian Art and Letters Vol. 1, No. 2, November 1925. India Soc. Publication ...	"
12	The Architectural Antiquities of Western India by H. Cousins ...	"
Dictionaries.		
13	Persian English and Urdu Dictionary by S. C. Paul ...	Purchased.
14	" into Urdu Dictionary by Maulvi Karimuddin ...	"
Epigraphy.		
15	The Indo-Summerian Seals deciphered by L. A. Waddell.	"
16	Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum Vol. I, inscriptions of Asoka by E. Hultzsch, Ph. D. ...	Gratis.
17-20	Epigraphia Indica Vol. XVIII, Nos. 1 to 4, year 1925 ...	"
21	Annual Report of South Indian Epigraphy for the year ending 31st March 1925 ...	"
Engineering.		
22	P.W.D. Hand Book, Bombay, containing specifications, rates, tables, plates and notes on work Vol. I, by E. L. Marryat.	Purchased.
Geography.		
23	Cunningham's Ancient Geography of India edited by S. N. Majumdar ...	"
Guides.		
24	The Seven Pagodas by J. W. Coomber ...	"
25	Guide to Benares by P. Seshadri ...	"
26	" Prayag or Allahabad ...	"
27	" Tanjore by Major H. A. Newell ...	"
28	" Rameswaram by ...	"
29	" Trichinopoly ...	"
30	" Madura ...	"
31	" The collection of the Colombo Museum, Ceylon, Part I.	"

No.	Title,	Remarks.
32	Guide to Ajanta frescoes	Purchased.
33	" the Caves of Ellora	"
34	" to the Madras and S. M. Railway (illustrated)	"
History.		
35	Ancient India by Codrington	"
36	" " by Merindle	"
37	History of Caste in India by S. V. Ketkar	"
38	Some Kshatriya Tribes of Ancient India by B. C. Law	"
39-41	History of the Maratha People, Vol. I, II and III, by Kincaid and Parasnis	"
42	History of Mediaeval India, Vol. II, 'Rajputana' by C. V. Vaidya	"
43	Ancient Mid-Indian Kshatriya Tribes, Vol. I, by B.C. Law.	"
44	Hindu Pad Padshahi by V. D. Savarkar	"
45	Dravidian India, Vol. I, by T. R. Sesha Iyengar	"
46	आर्योंचे सगुांचा प्राचीन व अर्वाचीन इतिहास, ऋगवेदी कृत	"
47	मराठी रियासत मध्य विभाग ३ गो. स. सरदेसाई कृत	"
Journals and Periodicals.		
48-58	Indian Antiquary for July 1925 to May 1926	"
59-70	Modern Review for July 1925 to June 1926	"
71	Index to Vol. LIV of Indian Antiquary	"
72	The Quarterly Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XV, No. 4	"
73-76	" " " " XVI, Nos. 1 to 4	"
77-79	The Indian Historical Quarterly, Vol. I, Nos. 2 to 4	"
80	" " " " II, No. 1, for March 1926	"
81	The illustrated London News, dated 4th October 1924	"
82	मालव मयूर मासिक, अंक जुलाई १९२५	"
Literature.		
83	Samarangana Sutradhara by King Bhojadeva, Vol. II, edited by Ganapati Shastri	"
84	Notes of a study of the Preliminary Chapters of the Mahabharata by V. V. Iyer	"
85	महाराष्ट्रीय वाङ्मय सूचि (१८१०-१९१७) डा. श्री. स्व. केतकर कृत	"
86	लेखन कला व लेखन व्यवसाय, वा. गो. आपटे कृत	"
Miscellaneous.		
87	Indian After Dinner, Stories by A. S. P. Iyer	"
88	My Pilgrimages to Ajanta and Bagh by M. C. Dey	"
89	The Arctic Home in the Vedas by B. G. Tilak	"
90	Orion or Antiquity of Vedas by B. G. Tilak	"
91	Hindu Law by S. V. Ketkar	"
92	Things Indian by William Crooke	"
93	South Indian Shrines by P. V. Jagadisa Iyer	"
94	Kautilya Arthashastra edited by R. Sharma Shastri	"
95	" " English Translation by R. Sharma Shastri with an introductory note by the late Dr. J. F. Fleet	"
Numismatics.		
96	Occasional Memoirs of the Numismatic Society of India, II, Historical Studies in Mughal Numismatics by Hodiwala	Purchased.
State Publications.		
97	प्रोसोडिगज मन्त्रालय खास मुद्रणालयक होम डिपार्टमेंट, मिन इन्डतदाय संमत १९६२ लुगायत १९८१	Gratis.

APPENDIX No. J.

**Statement of income realised during the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.**

No.	Heads.	Amount.			Remarks.
		Rs.	a.	p.	
1	By sale of Gwalior Fort Albums ...	175	6	0	
2	„ Tender forms	11	0	0	
3	„ Water colour tubes ...	6	4	0	
4	„ photo prints	7	8	0	
5	By auction of building material at Udaypur	14	0	0	
	TOTAL ...	214	2	0	

APPENDIX No. K.

Statement of Expenditure incurred during the year 1925-26,
Samvat 1982.

No.	Heads.	Amount cur-	Amount last	TOTAL.
		rent year.	year.	
		Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.
1	Salaries	8,820 13 1	...	8,820 13 1
2	Travelling allowances	2,133 3 0	4 6 0	2,137 9 0
3	Contingencies	1,476 6 3	399 15 0	1,876 5 3
4	Books and Periodicals	381 7 0	6 8 0	387 15 0
5	Museum	1,018 6 0	...	1,018 6 0
6	Works.—			
	(a) Conservation of Monuments	3,296 2 9	4,368 2 6	7,664 6 3
	(b) Presenting an album to H. H. the Maharaja Scindia on the auspicious occasion of his coronation	140 1 3	...	140 1 3
	(c) Presenting an album to Their Mm. the King and Queen of Belgians during Their Mm.'s visit to Gwalior	96 11 0	...	96 11 0
	(d) Publication of a guide to Chanderi	319 1 9	...	319 1 9
	(e) Exhibiting photographs of Archaeological Monuments in G. I. P. Ry. carriages	400 0 0	...	400 0 0
	(f) Compensation of land acquired at Badoh (District Bhilsa)	42 14 0	...	42 14 0
	(g) Departmental At-Home	499 9 3	...	499 9 3
	(h) Salaries of work charged staff	273 0 0	...	273 0 0
	(i) Sending Bagh frescoes to England.	63 5 0	63 5 0
	(j) Publication of Bagh frescoes	48 2 0	...	48 2 0
7	Upkeep of conserved monuments	333 12 9	82 10 6	416 7 3
8	Sanitation, hot weather and garden charges (over and above budget grant)	163 0 0	...	163 0 0
9	Repairs to buildings on Narwar Fort (Special grant)	11,698 0 9	11,698 0 9
	TOTAL Rs.	19,442 10 1	16,623 0 9	36,065 10 10

(a) Yasodharman's Pillars at Sondni, before conservation.

(b) Yasodharman's Pillars at Sondni, after conservation.

(b) Siva slaying Gajasura or elephant demon,
from Gyaraspur.

(a) Siva at Mandasor, after conservation.

(a) River goddess Yamuna in a panel on the Toran Pillar at Khitchipura.

(b) Toran Pillar (locally known as Sravan ki kavadi) at Khitchipura, after conservation

(c) Another panel of sculpture on the Toran Pillar at Khitchipura.

(b) A decorated arch in the Kacheri Mahal, at Narwar Fort.

(d) Sikandar Lodi's Mosque, at Narwar Fort, after clearance.

(a) The hill Fort at Narwar, general view.

(c) A monolithic trough known as chhip, at Narwar Fort.

(E) A tantric image of a goddess riding a lion ☉, brass, height 1'8"

(A) A tantric image of Siva ☉, brass, height 1'4"

(b) Bodhisattva, copper, height 6 $\frac{3}{4}$ "

(a) Bodhisattva Vajrapani, copper, height 1 $\frac{1}{4}$ "

